

EDU4
Standards.eu

D3.1

Pilot Design Report

Project title	Education for Standardisation in the EU
Project Acronym	EDU4Standards.eu
Project Number	101135705
Type of project	HORIZON.2.4 - Digital, Industry and Space
Topics	HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01
Starting date of project	1 January 2024
Duration of the project	31 December 2026
Website	https://EDU4Standards.eu/

D3.1 – Pilot Design Report

Work Package	WP3 – Implementation
Task	T3.1 – Pilot Design
Lead authors	Hugo Parada (UPM) José del Álamo (UPM)
Contributors	Rudi Bekkers - (TUE) Paul Wiegmann - (TUE) Robert Link – (FRE) Magnus Hakvåg (HoK) Håvard Almås (HoK) Sokol Tominaj (TUB) Elisabeth Staudegger (UGZ) Nizar Abdelkafi (POLIMI) Knut Blind (FHG) Ivana Mijatovic (UB) Geerten van de Kaa (TUD) Sury Bravo (UPM) David Rodriguez (UPM) Mihaela Andreea David (SBS) Björn Lundell (SKO) Vladislav Formin (VU)
Peer reviewers	Geerten van de Kaa Nizar Abdelkafi Knut Blind
Version	1.3 Final
Due date	31.05.2025
Submission date	

Dissemination level:

	PU: Public – fully open
	SEN: Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
	RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED (R-UE/EU-R), - (Commission decision 2015/444)
	CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL (C-UE/EU-C), - (Commission decision 2015/444)
	SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET (S-UE/EU-S) (Commission decision 2015/444)

Versioning History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
V0.3	2025.03.20	Hugo A. Parada G.	The stable draft uploaded to Sharepoint and shared with consortium partners
V0.3a	2025.03.20	Jose M. del Álamo	Comments on Introduction and Pilot Design Methodology sections
V0.5	2025.03.21	Hugo A. Parada G.	Updated Introduction and Pilot's Design Methodology
V0.5a	2025.03.21	Rudi Bekkers	Added the content to the section <i>Edu4Standard Teaching Support Tool</i> , including references to the sharing of online teaching materials.
V0.6	2025.03.23	Robert Link	Added the content to the section 2.2.2 Pilot indicators
V0.6a	2025.04.04	Håvard Almås Magnus Hakvåg	Added the content to the section "Serious game for teaching standardisation"
V0.6b	2025.04.04	Hugo A. Parada G.	Added the content to the section 3.1 and 3.2
V0.6c	2025.07.04	Robert Link	Added the content to the section "2.2 <i>Pilot Indicators and Self-Assessment</i> " and "4.8 Open Call for Pilots"
V0.7	2025.10.04	Hugo A. Parada G.	Updated content to the section "4. <i>Pilot Desing</i> ", including the Pilot Desing Template for Bachelor, Summer school, Extracurricular, In-company training and Pan European EHARTO pilots.
V0.7a	2025.04.24	Ivana Ivana Mijatovic	Added the content on the section 2.5.2 "EDU4Standard teaching support tool"
V0.7b	2025.04.25	Björn Lundell	Added the content on the section 2.5.3 "License of outcomes from the pilots"
V0.7c	2025.04.28	Hugo A. Parada G.	Added the pilots leader's contribution on the section 2.3 "Addressing the detected gaps through pilots design"
V1.0	2025.05.06	Hugo A. Parada G.	Executive summary and conclusions
V1.0a	2025.05.13	Geerten van de Kaa, Nizar Abdelkafi, Knut Blind	Revised version with comments
V1.0b	2025.05.18	Robert Link	Addressing comments of the reviewers; section 2.2 moved to section 4.6
V1.1	2025.05.18	Hugo A. Parada G.	Addressing comments of the reviewers; sections 2 and 2.1 moved to Pilot Design section (currently, section 3)
V1.1a	2025.05.28	Hugo A. Parada G.	Addressing the Vladislav Formin comments
V1.3	2025.05.29	Jose M. del Álamo	Final version

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CC BY-NC-SA	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
DIN	German Institute for Standardisation
EARTO	European Association of Research and Technology Organisations
EC	European Comision
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
EQF	European Qualification Framework
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FOSS	Free and Open Source Software
FRE	freesia innovation E.U.
GVC	Global Value Chain
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
HFDT	Human Factor in Digital Transformation
HLI	High-level-indicator for Standardisation Education
HoK	House of Knowledge
ICT	Information and Communications Technologies
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ILOs	Intended Learning Outcomes
IP	Intellectual Property
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITCoS	Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation
KAs	Knowledge Areas
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MPL	Mozilla Public License
NDAs	Non-disclosure Agreements
OER	Open Educational Resources
POLIMI	Politécnico de Milano
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
QTZ	Quantum Technology Competence
RTO	Research and Technology
SBS	Small Business Standards
SBS	Small Business Standards
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SDOs	Standard Development Organizations
SEPs	Standard-essential Patents
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
stand-EUVI	Standardisation in line with EU values and interests
TBT	Technical Barriers to Trade
TD	Teaching Description
TEU	Treat European Union
TiU	Tilburg University
TU/e	Eindhoven University of Technology

TUB	Technical University of Berlin
TUD	Delft University of Technology
UGZ	University of Graz
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
VU	Vilnius University
WP	Work Package
WTO	World Trade Organization

Keywords

Education, Standardisation, Teaching Concept, Knowledge Areas, Pilot design, EDU4Standards.eu

Disclaimer

EDU4Standards.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program under Grant Agreement No. 101135705. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Executive summary

EDU4Standards aims to innovate standardisation education within European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). To this end, the project Work Package 2 (WP2) has developed an Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) 1) defining a set of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) as detailed in the project deliverable D2.1 (Veljanova et al., 2024); 2) identifying and categorizing existing contents and methods for teaching standardisation and specifying the gaps, as detailed in the deliverable D2.2 (Fomin et al., 2024); and, 3) producing a hierarchical model of ILOs in accordance with the competencies and skills needed by the industry and other organisations, as detailed in the deliverable D2.3 (Mijatovic et al., 2025).

This document reports the project efforts to design the pilots that will implement and validate the ITCoS. It begins by describing the methodology used in designing the pilots, including the application of a self-assessment template with key performance indicators (KPIs) to ensure design quality from the outset. It also shows how the pilots respond to the gaps identified by incorporating European values, addressing gender-related issues, and facilitating the sharing of teaching materials to promote standardisation education across HEIs. To this end, the report describes the functionalities of the EDU4Standards Teaching Support Tool, which serves as a central repository for instructors to share teaching materials—such as videos, case studies, lectures, and serious games—to promote the teaching of standardisation. The report further highlights the importance of using serious games in education and provides guidance for their integration into standardisation teaching.

The templates for eight pilots have been designed, amounting to a total of 236 hours of standardisation instruction delivered to diverse target audiences. These pilots will be implemented not only by universities across Europe but also by companies, engaging a wide range of educational contexts and stakeholders. The pilots include:

- One pilot at the bachelor's level (to be implemented by UB).
- Two pilots at the master's level (to be implemented by TUD and TUB).
- Two extracurricular pilots (to be implemented by POLIMI and UGZ).
- Two in-company training pilots (to be implemented by TU/e and SBS – the latter being an additional pilot not included in the Grant Agreement).
- One Pan-European pilot addressing researchers of EARTO (to be implemented by FhG).

Finally, the report provides details on the conditions for the upcoming EDU4Standards.eu open call for new pilots, aiming to expand and strengthen standardisation teaching through the reuse of methodologies, resources, and best practices.

Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	8
2	APPLYING THE INNOVATIVE TEACHING CONCEPT OF STANDARDIZATION	11
2.1	BRIDGING WP2 OUTCOMES WITH PILOT DESIGN	11
2.2	APPLYING THE ITCOS IN PILOT DESIGN	14
2.3	ADDRESSING THE DETECTED GAPS THROUGH PILOTS DESIGN	15
2.4	SERIOUS GAMES FOR TEACHING STANDARDISATION	24
2.4.1	<i>The role of serious games in standardisation education.....</i>	24
2.4.2	<i>Implementing serious games in teaching standardisation.</i>	26
2.5	OPEN TEACHING RESOURCES FOR STANDARDISATION	27
2.5.1	<i>Teaching Materials Available for Use and Sharing</i>	28
2.5.2	<i>EDU4Standards Teaching Support Tool.....</i>	29
2.5.3	<i>License of outcomes from the pilots</i>	35
3	PILOTS DESIGN	37
3.1	PILOTS' DESIGN METHODOLOGY	37
3.1.1	<i>Pilots' Design Template.....</i>	39
3.2	DESIGNING PILOTS.....	44
3.2.1	<i>Pilot at university B.Sc. level</i>	45
3.2.2	<i>Pilot at university M.Sc. level.....</i>	56
3.2.2.1	Pilot at university M.Sc. - Technology battles - TUD.....	56
3.2.2.2	Pilot at university M.Sc. level – Standardisation and Sustainability - TUB	60
3.2.3	<i>Extra-curricular Pilots</i>	66
3.2.3.1	Summer school Pilot Design	66
3.2.3.2	Extra-curricular pilot Design	77
3.2.4	<i>In-company training Pilot</i>	83
3.2.4.1	In-company lifelong learning pilot design.....	83
3.2.4.2	Standards for SME pilot	89
3.2.5	<i>Pilot of lifelong learning: the Pan-European EARTO pilot Design</i>	96
3.3	PILOT INDICATORS (KPI) AND SELF-ASSESSMENT	103
3.3.1	<i>Pilot indicators.....</i>	103
3.3.2	<i>Pilot self-assessment.....</i>	105
3.4	OPEN CALL FOR PILOTS.....	110
4	CONCLUSIONS	112
	APPENDIX 1 OPEN CALL FOR PILOTS.	114
	APPENDIX 2 PILOTS LEADER SURVEY -BRIDGING WP2 RESULTS WITH WP3	119
	APPENDIX 3 PILOT SELF-ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE, INDICATORS AND OVERVIEW.....	121
	BIBLIOGRAPHY	129

Table of Figures

<i>Figure 2-1. Connecting WP2 outcomes to WP3 design</i>	12
<i>Figure 2-2 ITCoS Conceptual model</i>	14
<i>Figure 2-3 The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation Education (ITCoS) (Mijatovic et al., 2025)</i> ..	30
<i>Figure 2-4. The EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool first page</i>	32
<i>Figure 2-5. Knowledge Area (KA) 1: Basic Knowledge of Standardisation for Raising Awareness</i>	32
<i>Figure 2-6. Some topics within Knowledge Area (KA) 1</i>	33
<i>Figure 2-7. Topic 3.1. Users of Standards</i>	33
<i>Figure 2-8. Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games within Topic 8.1. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation</i>	34
<i>Figure 2-9 Recommended Sources within Topic 8.1. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation</i>	34
<i>Figure 3-1. Pilot design template</i>	39

Table of Tables

<i>Table 2-1. Findings from the Initial Survey Conducted by Pilot Leaders</i>	13
<i>Table 2-2 Summary of Pilot Strategies for Addressing Educational Gaps in Standardisation</i>	23
<i>Table 2-3. Structure of the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool (Mijatovic et al., 2025)</i>	31
<i>Table 3-1 Pilot design overview</i>	44
<i>Table 3-2. Sample Measures of I1 Attractiveness</i>	105
<i>Table 3-3 Table Sample Measures of I2 Multi-/Interdisciplinarity</i>	105
<i>Table 3-4. Example of Pilot Self-Assessment</i>	107
<i>Table 3-5. Coverage of the High-level indicators (HLIs) by the pilots</i>	108
<i>Table 3-6. Self-assessment overview: Coverage criteria by the pilots (example)</i>	108
<i>Table 3-7. Coverage of the criteria (summarized assessments)</i>	109
<i>Table 3-8. Coverage of the sub-criteria by the pilots (extract: lowest coverage)</i>	110

1 Introduction

EDU4Standards aims to innovate standardisation education within European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). To this end, the project Work Package 2 (WP2) has developed an Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) 1) defining a set of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) as detailed in the project deliverable D2.1 (Veljanova et al., 2024); 2) identifying and categorizing existing contents and methods for teaching standardisation and specifying the gaps, as detailed in the deliverable D2.2 (Fomin et al., 2024); and, 3) producing a hierarchical model of ILOs in accordance with the competencies and skills needed by the industry and other organisations, as detailed in the deliverable D2.3 (Mijatovic et al., 2025).

Within EDU4Standards WP3, Task 3.1 is crucial in bridging the ITCoS with its practical implementation in standardisation courses: It has translated the general findings and outputs of EDU4Standards WP2 into specific pilot designs, ensuring that the educational content aligns with the real-world needs of different HEIs and diverse learning contexts. In this way, Task 3.1 directly supports the EDU4Standards project's objective to engage HEIs across the EU in standardisation education.

To achieve this, Task 3.1, as the initial stage of WP3, focused on designing pilot programs that incorporate innovative teaching content. This design process begins with the EDU4Standards value-based ILOs framework, which provides a hierarchical structure of intended learning outcomes for standardisation in alignment with EU interests and values. The design also considers the teaching contents and methods, and the industry requirements to propose a roadmap that will allow the pilot's implementation. In this way, T3.1 supports some of the specific objectives and special goals of the Edu4Standard project such as:

- *“HEI adopting the innovative teaching concept including the developed content.*
- *Increase number of teachers offering courses and students attending courses about standardisation;*
- *and the implementation of pilot programs covering courses for a. Bachelors, b. Masters, c. In company training, d. extra-curricular formats, e. seasonal school, f. Pan-EU EARTO organized and launched, including online courses and downloadable resources”.*

The standardisation teaching within the pilots will vary across multiple dimensions, including educational levels, institutions, disciplines, national contexts, and course scope. The pilot programs will align with the three-cycle system for higher education in the EU, such as the first cycle (Bachelor level), the second cycle (Master level), and at postgraduate level. It also considers extracurricular and in-company programs. These pilots are selected to evaluate the effectiveness of ITCoS in diverse teaching environments. As a result, the following eight pilots are expected:

- A **Bachelor Pilot** is intended to develop a curriculum framework for a one-semester standardisation course for business or management schools. The course will be implemented at the University of Belgrade, featuring a set of 4-hour modules following the blended learning approach, and including online components and serious games.
- Two pilots at the **Master level** will address the needs of second-year M.Sc. students. These pilots propose a redesign of M.Sc. standardisation courses, following the teaching concept developed in WP2. The pilots will be implemented in the Netherlands by the Delft University of Technology and in Germany by the Technical University of Berlin.
- Two **extracurricular** pilots. The first one will focus on standardisation certification based on 25 academic training hours for engineering students from Politecnico di Milano. The second pilot will organize a Summer School for teachers from the University of Graz in Austria, following a hybrid approach combining online sessions (2 weeks) and five face-to-face sessions (5 days).
- **Two in-company training pilots.** The first one led by the Technical University of Eindhoven, this pilot will provide tailored training for professionals whose work requires standardisation knowledge. The pilot will deliver in-company courses and professional learning sessions within the European high-tech semiconductor sector, in collaboration with NXP. The second in-company training pilot, **although not originally planned in the Grant Agreement, the SME pilot in-company training (developed in cooperation with SBS) emerged as an additional outcome of the project.** This pilot will target the specific needs of small and medium-sized enterprises. It will build on the in-company pilot and introduce a flexible, modular training format designed to make standardisation more accessible and relevant to SMEs. The course will use real-life examples and interactive methods to support practical understanding and encourage SME engagement in standardisation processes.
- **A pilot addressing lifelong learning: the Pan-European EARTO pilot.** This pilot will organize webinars tailored to researchers employed at EARTO member organisations for three levels: beginners, intermediate learners, and advanced experts.

This deliverable D3.1 presents the results of the pilots' design as carried out within Task 3.1. The pilots will be carried out in the project Tasks 3.2-3.6 from M16 (April 2025) to M34 (October 2026), and their implementation will be reported in the deliverable D3.2 by M34 (October 2026). The pilots' evaluation will be carried out in Task 3.7, and the results will be reported in the deliverable D3.3 by M35 (November 2026).

The remaining document is organized as follows: Chapter 3 details the bridge between the WP2 outcomes and the implementation of the pilots. Chapter 4 describes the methodology used to design the pilots. It also presents the framework applied in their design, outlines the indicators for monitoring and evaluation, and

introduces the upcoming call for new pilots. Chapter 5 concludes the report and proposes a set of future steps to continue engaging European HEIs in standardisation teaching.

This report serves as a foundational document for the implementation phase of WP3, ensuring that the EDU4Standards innovative teaching concept is effectively applied across the pilot programs.

2 Applying the Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardization

Designing courses on standardisation requires a structured approach that considers professional profiles, knowledge levels, and necessary skills to align with the European strategy. Blind and Drechsler (2017) identify a gap in standardisation-related competencies, which are not sufficiently integrated into higher education curricula, underscoring the need to incorporate these skills at various educational levels. To address this, Choi and de Vries (2011) propose a framework for standardisation education, emphasizing the interdependence of target groups, learning objectives, responsible institutions, course content, and teaching methodologies. One key challenge is ensuring coherence among these elements. According to Olomi and Sabokwigina (2010), the target audience shapes the objectives, content, and teaching methods, while these, in turn, determine the learning outcomes.

Since different audiences require distinct learning outcomes, Bloom's taxonomy provides a useful classification, ranging from knowledge acquisition to higher-order cognitive skills such as analysis, evaluation, and creation. (Čudanov, Mijatović, & Săvoiu, 2013) (Sosniak, 1994) (Krathwohl, 2002). Consequently, the selection of teaching methods and content should be aligned with the expected learning outcomes to ensure effective knowledge transfer.

Consequently, the selection of teaching methods and content should be aligned with the expected learning outcomes to ensure an effective knowledge transfer and skills acquisition. In this line in the Edu4Standard project, the WP2 proposes the ITCoS, which integrates competency-based learning frameworks, teaching methodologies, and industry-driven knowledge areas. This way the WP2 outcomes (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3) provide a common framework to support the pilots designs and to promote teaching standardisation into HEI from EU.

2.1 Bridging WP2 Outcomes with Pilot Design

Figure 2-1 provides a structured relationship between Work Package 2 (WP2) and Task 3.1 (WP3). It shows how the Innovative Teaching Concept (ITCoS) developed in WP2 is operationalized through the design of pilots in Task 3.1. Thus, the Edu4Standard ILOs/Levels serve as the foundation for structuring pilots. These Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) (D2.1) ensure that education on standardisation is aligned with skill requirements across different educational levels. Deliverable D2.2 provides a guide for mapping ILOs to content and teaching methods, forming the basis for curriculum development in the pilots. It includes structured methodologies for active learning, case studies, best practices, and serious games. Finally, D2.3 links knowledge areas and industry needs, ensuring that the pilots reflect real-world competencies in standardisation. D2.3 supports the selection of relevant topics and learning materials that will be tested in the pilots. It provides examples of how to select the contents, methods and teaching materials to teach topics.

Figure 2-1. Connecting WP2 outcomes to WP3 design

Mapping this conceptual model into practical pilot designs presents a significant challenge. To address this, T3.1 contributors initially completed a survey (Appendix 2) intended to bridge the outcomes of WP2 with WP3. The pilot leaders filled out the survey based on the previous partners' experience on teaching standardisation. The survey aimed to obtain a baseline from which to align the pilot designs with the ITCOs by identifying key knowledge areas, skills, European values, teaching materials for each pilot. This effort helped to align the pilot planning with the broader project objectives and the European educational and industrial needs identified in WP2. The primary areas addressed in the survey included:

- **Identification of specific ILOs** according to the qualification level to be achieved in each pilot.

- **Selection of key topics and knowledge areas** that learners are expected to acquire.
- **Identification of teaching materials and learning methods** considered most appropriate for delivering the selected skills.
- **Mapping of selected skills** to European values (e.g., democracy, rule of law, gender equality) and strategic challenges (e.g., green and digital transitions).

Table 2-1. Findings from the Initial Survey Conducted by Pilot Leaders

Pilot	ILO Level(s)	Knowledge	Skill	Teaching Methods	Materials
University B.Sc. (UB)	Level 6, 7 (for S7.X)	K6.1, K6.2, K6.3	S6.1, S6.2, S6.4, S6.6, S7.7, S7.8	Active teaching learning, Business case studies	Book on Standardisation (2019), Abdelkafi et al. (2021);
Master (TU Berlin)	Level 5, 6, 7	K5.1, K5.2, K5.3, K6.1	S5.1, S5.2, S5.5, S7.7, S7.8, S7.10	Interactive teaching, Games	Abdelkafi et al. (2021); ISO (2021, 2022); Blind & Heß (2023); Heß (2020); Wiegmann et al. (2017) and further articles
Master (TUD)	Level 5, 6, 7	K5.1, K6.1, K7.1	S5.2, S7.3, S7.7	Existing teaching game, New teaching game and case development	Scientific Articles
Summer School / Extra-curricular (POLIMI)	Level 5, 6, 7, 8	K5.1, K6.1, K7.1, K8.1	S5.1, S5.2, S5.4, S5.6, S6.1, S7.3, S7.7, S7.8, S7.10, S8.1	Presentations, Textbook-based learning	Abdelkafi et al. (2021); (Understanding ICT Standardisation), ETSI Slide Set (2023)
Lifelong Learning (EARTO)	Level 5, 6, 7, 8	K5.1, K5.2, K5.3	S5.1, S5.2, S5.3, S5.5, S5.6, S5.8, S6.6, S7.2, S7.6, S7.7, S7.8, S8.8	Not explicitly stated (inferred: case-based or mixed)	Abdelkafi et al. (2021); ISO Reports (2021, 2022); Blind & Heß (2023); Heß (2020); Wiegmann et al. (2017)

Table 3-1 presents the main findings from the initial survey carried out by Pilot Leaders as input for starting the T3.1 activities. A key finding was that many pilot leaders found it challenging to explicitly map European values to ILOs, though most recognized their implicit presence. Some pilots demonstrated ambitious integration of EU values and challenges, while others maintained a more pragmatic or foundational focus. Among the common materials identified were books on standardisation (e.g., ETSI publications), ISO reports, and research literature related to SDGs and innovation. Teaching methods that are most often chosen include case-based learning, active learning strategies, and the use of games to enhance engagement. The survey also highlights the need to adapt content and teaching approaches to the specific academic level, knowledge, skill and institutional context of each pilot.

The varied approaches observed among pilot leaders in developing and preparing their programs emphasize the necessity for a unified framework to guide the design of standardisation courses. Such a framework

should not only meet industry requirements aligned with European values but also facilitate the development of comprehensive curricula, materials, and teaching methods that will be shared across Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) throughout the European Union. The ITCoS framework, developed as an outcome of WP2, addresses this need by providing a conceptual model that pilot owners can follow in designing the pilot's courses.

2.2 Applying the ITCoS in Pilot Design

Figure 2-2 ITCoS Conceptual model

The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) conceptual model illustrates the relationships between the outcomes of Work Package 2 (WP2) and provides a comprehensive framework for the design and implementation of pilot standardisation courses across different educational levels.

As shown in Figure 2-2, ITCoS consists of several interrelated components that support the integration of learning outcomes, teaching content, and pedagogical methods into the course programs that are aligned with industry needs.

The learning outcomes serve as a structured framework for defining the sets of knowledge and skills expected at each educational level within the domain of standardisation. These outcomes are directly mapped to specific industry requirements, which are organised into distinct knowledge areas. Each knowledge area is associated with one or more specific skills, which are then developed through targeted course topics.

Once the course topics are defined, the appropriate content, teaching materials, and teaching methods can be selected (ranging from short readings and slide presentations to case studies, instructional videos, and

serious games). This approach ensures that pilots are not only relevant to their intended audience and educational level but also aligned with industry expectations and reflective of core European Union values.

From a design perspective, the ITCoS model facilitates comprehensive planning by addressing what is taught, how it is taught, where, when, why and to whom. Figure 3-2 serves as a visual guide to help pilot designers understand the relationships among ITCoS elements (D2.1, D2.2 y D2.3) and apply them effectively in the design of pilots.

2.3 Addressing the Detected Gaps through Pilots Design

Based on the self-assessment results provided by the pilot partners, we can conclude that most of the identified gaps are being addressed. However, some rows in the assessment tables remain unmarked, indicating some areas that still require attention (gaps). These gaps should be explicitly tackled in the design of the upcoming pilots.

We have grouped these gaps into five main categories:

- **Gaps in teaching methods:** Certain approaches, such as the use of serious games or simulations, are still underutilised in standardisation education.
- **Gaps in teaching content:** Some important content areas remain insufficiently covered.
- **Lack of certification:** Education in standardisation rarely leads to formal recognition or certification as a standards professional.
- **Gender perspective:** Gender-related issues are generally not incorporated into standardisation teaching practices.
- **Lack of reflection on values and European interests:** Societal values and EU policy objectives are often not adequately addressed in course content or discussions.

After the pilot self-assessment activity, the Pilots' leaders were required to complete a structured questionnaire to indicate how these gaps should be addressed in the pilots. In general, all pilots addressed the pointed gaps in the pilot design (section 4) according to the level, pilot audience, and specific level at which the pilot will be implemented. Below, we summarize the responses provided by the pilots in the questionnaire.

Gaps in teaching methods.

In the Standardisation **Bachelor pilot** design from UB, address this gap by using active teaching methods designed to engage learners and activate their learning potential. Three methods will be emphasized:

- **Problem-Based Learning:** using real news stories as a starting point to explore topics through the lens of standards and standardization.
- **Teaching Case Studies:** bringing real-world standardization practices into the classroom.
- **Gamification:** focusing on skill development through interactive methods.

The Bachelor pilot will incorporate specially written teaching case studies developed for this course (12 of which are published in the textbook Mijatovic (2019)) as well as new one created for the EDU4Standards.eu project.

The team in charge of designing and implementing the pilot (UB) also has experience in developing and using standardization-themed serious games. Two of these games, The Serious Smiley Game and the DIN Game, will be included in the pilot. In addition, the pilot will integrate gamification elements into the classroom activities themselves.

The Technology Battles pilot (TUD, master level) will develop a game that will be played during the class. Students will apply strategies for standards dominance in this way thereby applying knowledge in an active manner. Also, the course will be made blended by, e.g., incorporating teaching videos.

The other **master level pilot (TUB)** uses several innovative teaching methods. For one, it integrates a game that teaches the standardization and patents developed by DIN. Further, we include student presentations into our pilot.

Traditional lecture-based approaches do not actively engage students or promote a deep understanding of standardisation. **The Extracurricular pilot Standardisation for Engineers (POLIMI)** addresses this issue by employing a range of interactive and participatory teaching methods. These include quizzes, game, and case studies, as well as teaching approaches such as “teaching by questions” and “teaching by examples.” These approaches should foster critical thinking and active learning, thus enabling students to apply theoretical concepts in practical and meaningful ways. By engaging students through real-world scenarios and encouraging them to explore the implications of standardisation in different contexts, the pilot provides an applied understanding of the topic.

The summer school Extracurricular pilot (UGZ) actively addressed underused methods in standardisation education by integrating role-play, games (e.g., value cards, DIN simulation, TECHETHOS), micro-teaching, and peer feedback within a flipped classroom framework. Unique informal methods (such as open talks, shared

meals, evening discussions, and a mid-week hike (if the weather is appropriate) were used as pedagogical strategies to foster deeper reflection and cross-disciplinary exchange. Future iterations could improve by adding a meta-methods session and clearer scaffolding for reflective practice.

Both the A1 and the A2 courses of **the in-company training pilot (TU/e)** will incorporate a game. In the A1 pilot, this will be the “Lost at Sea” game developed by ISO. In the A2 pilot, this will be a game developed in partnership with House of Knowledge.

Standardisation is rarely included in education and training programmes, especially in formats tailored to the needs of SMEs. As a result, there is a gap not only in content but also in the use of appropriate, innovative teaching methods that support real-world application. **SME pilot in-company training (SBS) emerged during the project as an additional initiative. Although it was not planned in the original Grant Agreement, it has become an additional outcome of the project.** This pilot seeks to address this by introducing a modular, scalable, and flexible approach designed to fit the operational constraints of SMEs. Instead of traditional, abstract lecture-based delivery, the course prioritises short, focused learning. The course uses case-based learning to present real-world challenges and solutions relevant to SMEs. It also fosters knowledge exchange by linking participants with experienced professionals. These approaches are intended to help SMEs relate standardisation more directly to their daily operations and decision-making.

Since the **EARTO pilot** will be online, the option of applying interactive and participatory teaching method will be limited. However, case studies should help to foster critical thinking and active learning, thus enabling the researchers to apply theoretical concepts in practical and meaningful ways. In addition, we involve guest lecturers, which are experts in their field, like Open Source. Finally, the use of a game depends on the availability of an online game to be developed and provided by the EDU4Standards partner House of Knowledge.

Gaps in teaching content

In the standardisation **Bachelor pilot design from UB**, there is generally a lack of real-world examples of standards development (such as who participated and what motivated their involvement). The focus of this pilot is on the business aspects of standardisation, primarily from the perspective of companies. We aim to include videos on these topics (such as [Rudi Bekker's video](#) (Bekkers, n.d.), which is included in the next subsection) and case studies related to green transport.

Whereas previous research has investigated factors that affect standards dominance, the strategies that firms can apply to influence those factors have not been addressed in education which will be done in the course **The Technology Battles pilot, developed at the master's level by TU Delft.**

TUB believes that many of the standards-related content areas fail to adequately address contemporary technological trends, such as blockchain technology, as well as broader societal goals like the pursuit of sustainability. Therefore, the **TUB pilot** aims to integrate a broad range of perspectives and technological trends into our pilot, while also keeping a specific emphasis on European values in standardization.

The Extracurricular pilot *Standardisation for Engineers (POLIMI)* offers a broad view on standardisation. Among the contents of the pilot, there are topics such as strategic relevance of standardisation for businesses, its role in innovation and relationship with intellectual property. Moreover, the pilot integrates real-world examples, fundamental principles such as those of the World Trade Organization's Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) principles, as well as the case study related to the revision of accessibility standards in Spain. By incorporating the intersection of standardisation with European values and interest, the pilot content reflects better EU policy requirements and the project's objectives.

The summer school Extracurricular pilot (UGZ) addressed the strategic and value-laden dimensions of standardisation but noted ongoing content gaps in global perspectives, tech-related standards (e.g., AI), and underrepresented disciplines like humanities and social sciences. Future versions will explore comparative models, develop new case studies, and deepen interdisciplinary relevance.

The in-company training pilot (TU/e) consists of two one-day courses for different audiences (junior engineers without experience in standardisation and mid-level engineers with some experience in standardisation) and a two-hour session for more senior managers still to be developed. The limited time available to teach the pilot requires a focus on topics relevant to the audience, as indicated in the pilot design template.

SMEs face major barriers in accessing, understanding, and applying standardisation knowledge. The **SME pilot in-company training (SBS)** addresses gaps by focusing on demystifying standards and their relevance to SME operations and products. The course covers foundational knowledge, sector-specific guidance, and highlights the value of participating in the development of standards. In many cases, there is not much information available on how standards apply in specific sectors or how to use them in day-to-day business. Our course puts a strong focus on practical examples and real situations that SMEs can relate to. By filling this gap, the course helps SMEs see how standardisation can support their work and become part of their regular business and planning.

Many researchers face problems in accessing, understanding, and applying standardisation knowledge. The **EARTO pilot (FHG)** offers a broad view for researchers with a strong focus on standardisation and less on the implementation of standards, which is of lower relevance for them. Among the contents of the pilot, there are topics such as the standardisation landscape, the types and functions of standards, their interface with

research, the relationship with intellectual property including open source and the geopolitical dimensions of standardisation. Moreover, the pilot integrates real-world examples. By already incorporating the fundamental principles such as those of the World Trade Organization's Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) principles, but also the EU regulation 1025/2012, we have starting points for the intersection of standardisation with European values and interest and the pilot content reflects already EU policy requirements and the project's objectives.

Lack of certification

Currently, there is a lack of formal recognition of standardisation knowledge and skills. **The Extracurricular pilot *Standardisation for Engineers (POLIMI)*** would raise students' standardisation competencies from below EQF Level 4 to Level 4 or 5. By defining clear, competency-based learning outcomes, this pilot lays the groundwork for future micro-credentials or professional certifications in standardisation. While participation in the pilot is not mandatory for completing their master degrees, students who successfully complete it will receive a grade that will be included in their final diploma.

The **TUB pilot** provides a certificate issued by DIN that testifies completion of an introductory course into standardization. We think that formal certification or recognition is beneficial as it provides an additional incentive for students to complete standards-related courses by awarding proof of standards-related knowledge that can be used in job applications.

Currently, **the summer school Extracurricular pilot (UGZ)** provides a certificate of participation based on the EDU4Standards.eu logo. The "Teaching Documents" and the planned 3-Minute Thesis presentation serve as reflective artefacts, but there is no formal professional certification. Micro-credentials or integration with national continuing education frameworks may be explored for future scaling.

Regarding this gap, participants in **the in-company training pilot (TU/e)** will receive a certificate of attendance from Eindhoven University of Technology.

The SME pilot in-company training (SBS) course provides a certificate of attendance to acknowledge participants' engagement. While this is not a formal certification, it supports initial recognition of standardisation-related learning, especially valuable for SMEs, where such training is rare. We are aware of the growing interest in micro-credentials across Europe and see potential to align with emerging initiatives that offer more formal, modular certification. We believe that stronger collaboration among educational institutions, SME associations and standards organisations could help build recognised learning pathways in standardisation.

The **EARTO pilot** provides a certificate of attendance to acknowledge participants' engagement. While this is not a formal certification, it supports initial recognition of standardisation-related learning, especially valuable for researchers, where such training is rare. We are aware of the growing interest in micro-credentials across Europe and see potential to align with emerging initiatives, e.g. of the HLF. We believe that stronger collaboration among educational institutions and EARTO members, even including standard development organisations could help build recognised learning pathways in standardisation.

Regarding this gap the Standardisation both **Bachelor pilot design the certification and the Technology Battles pilot, developed at the master's level by TU Delft** point out that this gap does not apply to them.

Gender Perspective

A critical shortcoming in traditional standardisation education is the lack of attention to gender inclusivity and the unintended biases that may be embedded in technical standards. Pilot leaders have identified various approaches to address this gap, as outlined below.

The Standardisation **Bachelor pilot design** is considering the gender-related issues on the example of the study of women in Eastern European countries and standards certification based on study (Riillo, Mijatovic & de Vries2022).

Gender-related issues are also included in **the Technology Battles pilot (TU Delft)** as this is about strategies that affect standards dominance, and the goal therein of companies is to try to reach the highest amount of market share, thereby also targeting women explicitly.

The **TUB pilot** covers gender equality through standardization by incorporating several examples into our lectures. We aim to elaborate on the essentiality of standardization for gender-related issues to our students by using real-world examples.

The Extracurricular pilot *Standardisation for Engineers (POLIMI)* addresses this issue explicitly by including an example that illustrates how standardisation can unintentionally reinforce gender biases. The discussion of airbag standards historically designed around average male body dimensions leads students to think more critically about the inclusiveness of the standard design. By encouraging students to reflect on the consequences of design decisions, the pilot promotes awareness of the need for diverse perspectives in the development of standards.

Gender equality is explicitly addressed by **the summer school Extracurricular pilot (UGZ)** in Module 0 and throughout the TD process. Over 50% of the trainers are women, and teaching methods include value-mapping and stakeholder reflection on inclusion. That said, the pilot may become aware of a need to further develop intersectional content and gender-sensitive case studies.

Gender is not a dedicated topic on the teaching plan of **the in-company training pilot (TU/e)**, due to the limited time available for the course. It will be addressed as part of the module on European Values, e.g., when discussing the case of standards for airbags not sufficiently addressing differences in anatomy between men and women.

The SME pilot in-company training (SBS) course acknowledges the importance of gender perspectives in standardisation and integrates inclusivity into its overall approach. While the course targets SMEs broadly, it will incorporate gender-balanced examples and encourage inclusive participation in standardisation processes. Moreover, the course will introduce the concept of gender-responsive standards, highlighting how standards can have different impacts on women and men, and why it is essential to ensure that standard-setting processes reflect diverse perspectives. This is particularly relevant if the pilot addresses SMEs in areas such as personal protective equipment (PPE), healthcare, construction, and transport—where design and safety requirements need to account for different body types, physical needs, and usage contexts. By using examples from these sectors, the course will raise awareness about the implications of standards if these aspects are not considered.

The EARTO pilot acknowledges the importance of gender perspectives in standardisation and integrates inclusivity into its overall approach. While the course targets researchers broadly, it will incorporate gender-balanced examples and address inclusive participation in standardisation processes. Moreover, the course will introduce the concept of gender-responsive standards, highlighting how standards can have different impacts on women and men, and why it is essential to ensure that standard-setting processes reflect diverse perspectives. By using examples, the course will raise awareness about the implications of standards if these aspects are not considered.

Lack of reflection on values and European interests

The Standardisation **Bachelor pilot** is planned to reflect on European values and delve deeper into their connection with standardization. It will address topics such as **green** and **digital transitions** and **competitiveness**. Special attention will be given to **sustainability, responsibility, and accountability** through standardization (examining the role of standards in society and their social impact) and within the standardization process itself. These aspects are already incorporated in *The Serious Smiley Game*.

One important part of **the Technology Battles pilot (TU Delft)** is discussing what constitutes a standard's success. In prior editions of the course, dominance in terms of market share was emphasized. However, acceptance and acceptability of standards might also positively affect their success. This will be included in the course. Additionally, the course will cover recent research on responsible standardization (e.g., taking values into account during the standardization process).

The **TUB pilot** addresses these dimensions by creating a unique lecture on “*Ethics and Standardization*” and further including a plethora of examples of European values and standardization in the other lectures.

The Extracurricular pilot *Standardisation for Engineers (POLIMI)* addresses the gap concerning reflection on values and European interests within standardisation. It emphasizes the role of standardisation in advancing key European Union values such as human dignity, democracy, equality, and respect for human rights. Through the exploration of standards’ societal impacts and the principles governing the standardisation process, students are encouraged to critically evaluate how standards can uphold (or undermine) European values. Attention is given to the European regulatory framework, including Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012, and how it seeks to align the standardisation system with EU policies and legislation. The pilot also teaches students to distinguish between the values embedded in specific standards and the values governing the standardisation process itself.

This is the core strength of **the summer school Extracurricular pilot (UGZ)**. The stand-EUVI approach forms the course’s backbone, framing standardisation through EU values and interests. Participants critically reflect on societal dimensions, policy alignment, and ethical tensions throughout the course. Further activities such as value-conflict clinics and discipline-specific mapping tools are under consideration. Similarly, **the in-company training pilot (TU/e)** includes a module on European Values and Interests.

The SME pilot in-company training (SBS) course introduces European values and interests in a practical way, linking them to each module. Participants learn how standards reflect EU goals like safety, sustainability, accessibility and fairness—especially in relation to legislation and market access. Sector-specific examples will help SMEs see how these values appear in real-world standards, while the module on participation will encourage them to contribute to making standards more inclusive and relevant to their needs.

The EARTO pilot considers first the WTO principles related to standardisation and then starts to introduce European values and interests. Attention is given to the European regulatory framework, including EU regulation 1025/2012, and how it seeks to align the standardisation system with EU policies and legislation. Participants learn how standards can reflect EU goals, like safety or sustainability, and encourage them to make the relevant contributions to standardisation processes.

To conclude, Table 2-2 provides a consolidated overview of how each pilot addresses the identified gaps in standardisation education, emphasizing strategies in teaching methods, content focus, certification, gender inclusivity, and European values. This summary presents the diverse approaches and targeted actions incorporated into the pilot designs to foster comprehensive and inclusive standardisation education.

Table 2-2 Summary of Pilot Strategies for Addressing Educational Gaps in Standardisation

Pilot	Addressed Detected Gaps				
	Teaching Methods	Teaching Content	Lack of Certification	Gender Perspective	Values and European Interests
Standardisation Bachelor - UB	Problem-Based Learning, Teaching Case Studies, Gamification	Videos on Real-world examples of standards development and case studies on green transport	Not Applicable	Considering gender-related issues through the example of a study on women in Eastern Europe and standards.	Focus on Green/Digital Transitions and competitiveness, with emphasis on sustainability, responsibility, and accountability through standardisation.
Technology Battles (Master pilot, TU Delft)	Game Development, Blended Learning (Incorporating teaching videos)	Strategies for standards dominance	Not Applicable	Indirectly by targeting Market Share (includes women)	Covering recent research on responsible standardization, including the integration of values in the standardization process.
Master pilot, TUB	DIN Game, Student Presentations	Incorporating a broad range of perspectives and technological trends: Standards-related content to address: Blockchain Technology, Sustainability	DIN Certificate that testifies completion of an introductory course into standardization	Incorporating examples of Gender Equality in Lectures (requiring students to elaborate on the essentiality of standardization for gender-related issues)	Creating a lecture on "Ethics and Standardization" and integrating various examples of European values throughout the course content.
Extracurricular pilot- POLIMI	Including a range of interactive and participatory teaching methods: Quizzes, Teaching by Questions and examples, Case Studies.	Integrating real-world examples on: WTO TBT Principles, EU Values, the revision of accessibility standards in Spain.	Grade included in the Diploma.	Including an example that illustrates how standardisation can unintentionally reinforce gender biases (e.g., Airbag Standards and Gender Bias case study).	Emphasizes EU values (human dignity, democracy, equality, human rights) through societal impact, EU Regulation 1025/2012, and distinguishing between embedded values in standards and the values guiding the standardisation process.
Summer School pilot - UGZ	Role-play, Games, micro-teaching, Peer Feedback with a Flipped Classroom.	Addressing strategic dimensions of standardisation while highlighting gaps in global perspectives, tech standards (e.g., AI), and underrepresented disciplines (humanities and social sciences)	Certificate of Participation based on the EDU4Standards.eu logo	Value Mapping and Stakeholder Reflection on Inclusion. The pilot may further explore intersectional content and develop gender-sensitive case studies.	Framework centered on EU values and interests, with critical reflection on societal impact, policy alignment, and ethical tensions. Potential future activities: value-conflict clinics and mapping tools.
In-company Training pilot - TU/e	ISO 'Lost at Sea' Game, House of Knowledge Game	Focus on topics relevant to (junior engineers without experience in standardisation, middle engineer and senior managers) Sector-Specific Standards (see section 4.4.1)	Certificate of Attendance from Eindhoven University of Technology	Addressed in the EU Values Module through case examples, e.g., airbag standards not accounting for anatomical differences between men and women	Includes a dedicated module on European Values and Interests.

SME In-company Training pilot - SBS	Case-Based Learning, Knowledge Exchange	Content focus on demystifying standards and their relevance to SME operations and products. Topics cover foundational knowledge, sector-specific guidance, and highlight the value of participating in standard development.	Certificate of Attendance (no formal certification)	Integrating inclusivity into the overall approach by introducing gender-responsive standards, highlighting their differential impact on men and women and emphasizing diverse perspectives in standard-setting.	Integrates EU values (safety, sustainability, accessibility, fairness) in a practical, sector-specific context, encouraging SMEs to contribute to inclusive standardisation.
EARTO Pilot (FHG)	Guest Lecturers, Online Games	Broad focus on standardisation for researchers, covering the standardisation landscape, research interface, intellectual property (including open source), and geopolitical dimensions, integrating real-world examples.	Certificate of Attendance (no formal certification)	The pilot integrates inclusivity into its overall approach. Integrates inclusivity through gender-balanced examples and inclusive participation in standardisation processes. Highlights implications of neglecting gender considerations using targeted examples.	Introduces WTO principles and EU values, focusing on EU Regulation 1025/2012 and aligning standards with EU policy objectives (e.g., safety, sustainability).

Most pilots incorporate serious games not only to address educational gaps but also to enhance the appeal of content and teaching on standardisation, thereby increasing engagement. The next section presents a guideline on how to effectively implement this strategy.

2.4 Serious Games for Teaching Standardisation

Standardisation is a crucial but often overlooked aspect of education, which, despite its importance, is often regarded as an unattractive and challenging subject to teach. Many institutions hesitate to incorporate standardisation into their curricula, as it is perceived as abstract, complex, and not directly relevant to students' immediate career prospects. To address this reluctance and improve engagement, serious games – games with a primary purpose beyond entertainment – are a promising educational tool. By making learning interactive and dynamic, serious games can improve standardisation education, making it more practical, engaging, and effective. Games that promote meaningful interaction between players, collaborative serious games, are especially fruitful (Van den Bossche et al., 2022; Almås, 2025; Hofstede et al., 2010; Zambrano et al., 2023).

2.4.1 The role of serious games in standardisation education.

Serious games have demonstrated their potential in various fields of education, showing improved learning outcomes and increased engagement. They enable experiential and situated learning by placing students in simulated environments where they must apply theoretical knowledge in practice and draw on existing experiences to succeed (Gee, 2008; Rigby & Ryan, 2011; Coghlan et al., 2019). In the context of standardisation, serious games can be beneficial for both students and educators by:

- **Teaching key concepts:** Serious games can elaborate complex ideas by embedding them in a structured game environment that encourages exploration and discovery. Allowing students to see the practical applicability of concepts immediately upon their introduction makes it easier to fit pieces of the puzzle together and relate them to prior knowledge (Almås, 2025; Gee, 2008; Slof et al., 2021).
- **Developing processual and tacit knowledge:** Understanding standardisation involves not only theoretical knowledge but also process-based and tacit knowledge that can be best acquired through experience. Through the simulated process, serious games enable students to more readily spot how constituent elements of the standardisation process, for instance, fit together (Duke & Geurts, 2004; Almås & Giæver, 2024).
- **Reinforcing Learning:** Games enable iterative learning, where students can revisit and refine their understanding of standardisation either through playing gradually more complex games or by combining play with more traditional educational approaches.
- **Fostering shared learning:** Whenever adults engage in learning endeavours, they rely on their existing knowledge, experiences, perspectives, and beliefs to guide them through the learning process and organize new knowledge. Collaborative serious games excel at making this a shared process, letting players draw from and reflect on each other's understanding (Almås & Giæver, 2024; Fyhn et al., 2023).
- **Building soft skills:** Standardisation often requires collaboration/teamwork, negotiation, and decision-making skills, all of which can be practiced and honed through serious games. In fact, a key benefit of using serious games is that play offers a way of engaging in meaningful collaboration (Vasconcelos et al., 2022; Almås et al., 2023) – fostering a kind of interactive learning experience which is often missing in higher education.
- **Increasing engagement:** Interactive gameplay fosters curiosity and motivation, making standardisation more appealing to students and educators alike. The novelty and extraordinary nature of play demarcate it from everyday life and most approaches to teaching, creating an engaging experience (Hofstede et al., 2010; Wouters et al., 2013; Hamari et al., 2016).
- **Providing a safe environment for interaction:** Serious games allow students to experiment without fear of real-world consequences. Moreover, there are no vested interests or established hierarchies in the game world, which fosters a safe environment for meaningful interaction, creativity, and deep learning (Wonica, 2017; Staaby, 2021; Fyhn et al., 2022).

2.4.2 Implementing serious games in teaching standardisation.

To successfully integrate serious games into standardisation education, educators should consider the following:

- **Choosing the right game:** Serious games can be used for diverging purposes, but educators must select games that align with their course objectives and learning outcomes, as well as the students' level of existing knowledge. Some key use cases include:
 - Using serious games to introduce students to the purpose of standards and standardisation in an engaging manner, showcasing importance and sparking interest.
 - Incorporating serious games as tools for experiential learning, allowing students to practice standardisation in a safe, simulated setting.
 - Using games to reinforce knowledge acquired through traditional lectures, readings, or case studies.
- **Integrating play into the course:** Approaching games with a 'one-and-done' mentality rarely reaps the full benefit of play. By being conscious about the expected outcome of play, the game can more easily be integrated into the wider course structure. Often, the joint reflection or debriefing that follows play is as important as play itself – and using learning from the game in subsequent lectures further reinforces this.
- **Enhancing lecture dynamics:** Relatedly, serious games can transform traditionally static learning materials into interactive experiences. By combining serious games with traditional lectures, a more dynamic and interactive classroom experience is created. As such, for educators engaged in courses on standards or related topics, implementing serious games does not mean foregoing existing course content but can rather be considered an additional feature.
- **Using student assistants as facilitators.** Collaborative serious games often require a certain level of assistance from trained facilitators, both for providing learning support and for ensuring a functioning group dynamic. Luckily, not all facilitators have to be subject-matter experts – student assistants can help facilitate gameplay, acting as mediators to ensure that learning objectives are met and that students remain engaged.

Best practices for pilots using serious games: When developing courses that incorporate serious games for standardisation education, the following guidelines should be considered:

- **Define clear learning objectives:** The game should align with the course's intended learning outcomes and students' level of mastery.

- **Ensure practical relevance:** The game should mirror real-world standardisation challenges and decision-making processes. Rather than solely looking at the depth of theoretical coverage, reflecting on how well facets of practical relevance are incorporated is often fruitful.
- **Encourage collaboration:** Standardisation processes frequently involve consensus-building and teamwork. The serious games chosen may also promote cooperative problem-solving when they align with the course's learning objectives.
- **Conduct faculty training:** Train educators on the pedagogical value of serious games and how to facilitate them effectively. Educators know how to teach, of course, but the process of play often requires some additional training, nonetheless.
- **Incorporate a safe learning environment:** Serious games allow students to experiment without fear of real-world consequences, fostering creativity and deeper learning.
- **Flexibility and adaptability:** For learning at any level beyond the introductory, the serious game should accommodate different levels and areas of preexisting knowledge. Games that rely on the students to provide most of the input themselves excel at this, and thus support customisation based on the needs of various student groups.

Serious games present a valuable opportunity to enhance the teaching and learning of standardisation in HEIs. By making the subject more engaging, interactive, and practical, they can help overcome the reluctance of **educators** and students alike. Additionally, by fostering experiential learning, collaboration, and critical thinking, serious games contribute to a deeper understanding of standardisation processes and their real-world applications. For institutions and educators committed to improving standardisation education, serious games provide an innovative and effective pedagogical tool. Implementing them with careful planning and adherence to best practices will ensure their successful integration into the curriculum, benefiting both students and the wider academic and professional community.

2.5 Open Teaching Resources for Standardisation

To share teaching materials for standardisation education, the pilots will use open-access resources available online, especially the resources from [EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool | EDU4Standards](#), and [Teaching repositories | EDU4Standards](#). During the implementation of the pilots, the pilot leaders will complement these materials by developing and providing access to additional resources (by uploading new materials (such as videos, use cases, etc.) to the EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool.) they consider useful for teaching key concepts in a remote or distance-learning format.

2.5.1 Teaching Materials Available for Use and Sharing

The **SME and EARTO pilots** will provide relevant sector-specific examples and inputs from external experts or SME partners, tailored to the needs of participants. In some cases, these expert contributions may not be shareable due to copyright or confidentiality constraints. However, any original material developed in-house will be made available and shared via the EDU4Standards platform or upon request. This approach ensures broad access to core content while respecting the rights and contributions of guest experts.

The **TUB pilot** will design a variety of lectures, such as “*Standardization and ICT*” and “*Ethics and Standardization*,” and upload them to the EDU4Standard repositories, making them available to the partners.

The **extra-curricular pilot from POLIMI** primarily utilizes the ETSI teaching material. This material will be enriched by integrating thought-provoking questions designed to facilitate the co-construction of the content together with the students. These questions aim to connect standardisation to real-life scenarios and encourage students to reflect on both the opportunities and challenges that may arise within the standardisation process. Through questioning, the course will enhance students’ awareness of the subject and highlight the relevance and impact of standardisation in engineering, management, and society.

To complement the course materials, the **UGZ pilot** will use adapted “*TECHETHOS for stand-EUVI*” slides, selected participant-created teaching documents (as examples), the EDU4Standards.eu *Teaching Document Template*, and other uploaded materials. All of these resources will be available in the EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool and repositories under a CC BY-NC-SA license.

The **in-company pilot** notes that teaching materials are still being developed and will be made available where they do not violate the copyright of third parties. However, the pilot leader, Rudi Bekkers, has contributed to the teaching of patents and standards in Europe by recording a series of expert interviews aimed at students in this field. In these videos, professionals from industry, public organizations, and government institutions talk about their work on these topics and important developments and leave a personal message to students at the end of each interview (video).

These educational videos could be reused under a Creative Commons CC BY-ND license, basically meaning that anyone is free to use and re-publish these videos, as long as proper reference is made to the maker, and the video is re-published in its entirety (so not edited, changed, or shortened).

Below is a list of the educational videos on patents and standards provided by Bekkers (n.d.):

- [Octrooicentrum Nederland](#) (The Dutch patent office) In this video Hans Helsloot talks about the patent system and how small- and medium-sized companies can get engaged in patenting.

- [AOMB Intellectual Property](#) In this video, Arie Blokland, Teun van Berkel, and Tim Korsten explain how patent attorneys help companies as well as private inventors to turn ideas into actual patent applications.
- [Taylor Wessing](#): In this video, Wim Maas and Eelco Bergman talk about how it works when companies get end up being in a dispute and end up in court.

Education videos on standards and standardisation (provided by Bekkers (n.d.)):

- [CEN-CENELEC](#) In this video, Andrea Gulasci of CEN-CENELEC, explains the role of two of the three European Standards Organisations (ESOs).
- [ETSI](#) In this video, Claire d'Esclercs of ETSI explains how telecommunications standards are developed in Europe by the third European Standards Organisation (ESO).
- [European Commission \(EC\)](#) In this video, Sophie Mueller and Gabriella Sestini talk about the standardisation policy of the European Commission.
- [Small Business Standards \(SBS\)](#) In this video, Maitane Olabarria provides insight into the challenges and opportunities of small and medium-sized companies in standardisation.
- [DIGITALEUROPE](#) A talk on standardisation with Omar Dhaher of DigitalEurope, an organisation that represents digital industries across Europe.
- [Forum Standaardisatie \(Netherlands government\)](#) Ludwig Oberendorff explains the policy developed by the Dutch government for the use of standards by governmental agencies for internal use, communications to businesses, and to citizens.
- [PTB Quantum Technology Competence](#) Standards also play a key role at the frontiers of science. In this video, Nicolas Spethmann of the Quantum Technology Competence (QTZ) of the German National Metrology Institute (PTB) explains how badly standards are needed for qubits.
- [PON \(mobility services\)](#) With some 14,000 employees in 34 countries, PON is a large mobility company. In this video, Raymond Gense explains how such a sector is impacted by standards and regulations.

2.5.2 EDU4Standards Teaching Support Tool

The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation Education (ITCoS) is a multidimensional approach intended to effectively guide the development of new educational curricula (or their parts) and content while benchmarking the existing ones. It aims to support versatile, attractive, and high-quality standardisation education, making it the most comprehensive and effective approach in the field. The ITCoS is based on industry needs and social expectations. The KAs are defined according to studies of industry needs on education about standardisation and social expectations, which are related to the EU values (see more in D2.1 (Veljanova et al., 2024)), enhancing competitiveness through innovation in a sustainable environment,

thus focusing on green and digital transition (Figure 2-3). The collegial support and the exchange of experience or recommendations can significantly motivate teachers to include content from standardisation in their courses. The role of peer support is also to establish a network of teachers teaching standardisation who will continue to share experiences (connected with activities in WP4). For more information about ITCoS see D2.3 (Mijatovic et al., 2025).

KAs in the ITCoS enable a way to systematize knowledge and skills related to standardisation, as well as, topics, existing teaching material (recommended books and research papers, teaching case studies, serious games, video material) and teachers' experiences (good practice). The ITCoS is based on four KAs:

- KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness
- KA2. Standardisation interdependencies with other areas and roles in specific contexts
- KA3. Strategic use of standards
- KA4. Strategic participation in standards development

Figure 2-3 The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation Education (ITCoS) (Mijatovic et al., 2025)

The ITCoS is a starting point for the development of the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool based on the web platform (EDU4Standards, n.d.). The EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool aims to:

- Enable continual improvements of the ITCoS and provide the development of new topics.
- Become a focal point or central hub – the foundation for exchanging information, good practices, experiences, and teaching materials (related to standardisation).
- Support educators in improving existing courses (or parts of them) on standardisation or integrating standardisation-related topics/content into their courses across various disciplines.
- Provides key topics and concepts, recommended sources, support materials, and good practices for tailoring part of the course or the whole course on standardisation.

The format for developing topics of the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool is presented in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3. Structure of the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool (Mijatovic et al., 2025)

Structure of the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool	Explanation
1. Topic	Topics are chosen to represent a unit that the educators can combine with other units of their choice. The topics are intertwined. It is recommended that all topics have SGD (social/green/digital) examples.
2. Short instruction	Short instructions elaborate on why understanding a specific topic is important or relevant
3. The ILOs examples	In this section is explained the connection with ILOs published in D2.1
4. Recommended Teaching Case studies / Serious games / Other	The teaching case studies do not have to be written (although that would be good), but they can be described in a few sentences, and a list of sources can be given for a specific case (for example, HD vs Blue Ray). Sharing teaching case studies used in a classroom is a practice we must support.
5. Good practice	Good practice is a description of educators' experience in working with students/trainees. All partners and pilots should contribute to this part.
6. Recommended sources	It lists literature (books, papers) that is recommended to someone who wants to start teaching standardisation or to improve existing classes.

To learn more about the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool, please visit the following link:

<https://EDU4Standards.eu/teacher-support-tool>

Educators can explore the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool by clicking on the KAs (Figure 2-4).

Figure 2-4. The EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool first page

After selecting one of the KA, the description of the selected KA is shown (Figure 2-5).

Figure 2-5. Knowledge Area (KA) 1: Basic Knowledge of Standardisation for Raising Awareness

After selecting the KA, educators can choose from the list of topics available within the selected KA (Figure 2-6).

1.1. The Strategic Importance of Standards and Standardisation 18 February 2025
1.2 Technical, economic, legal, and societal implications and impact of standards implementation and participation in standards development (the European point of view) 13 March 2025
1.3 History of Standardisation 13 March 2025
2.1. Concept of Standards and Standardisation 14 March 2025
2.2. General objectives of standardisation, roles and domains of standardisation 18 March 2025
2.3. Types of Standardisation and Classification of Standards 18 March 2025

Figure 2-6. Some topics within Knowledge Area (KA) 1

Within each topic, short instruction is given, along with the ILOs examples, recommended teaching cases/serious games, good practices, and recommended sources to learn more/teach about the topic (Figure 2-7).

3.1. Users of standards

Home » EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool » Knowledge Area KA1: Basic Knowledge of Standardization for Raising Awareness

Short instruction

Generally, there are two types of standard users: direct and indirect. Direct users are those who implement the standards – organizations or individuals who apply standards across a wide range of activities. Indirect users are those affected by the application of standards, such as consumers of products and services that comply with standards. Two aspects of standard users are receiving increased attention: the participation of indirect users in standards development and the influence of indirect users on the evolution of standards implementation. Standards are developed to be used, and a successful standard is one that is widely accepted in the market. Most experts involved in developing standards represent organizations that also implement them. However, the pool of direct users of standards (those who implement them) is larger than the pool of those who develop them. Gaining insight into the users of standards could be pivotal in understanding the needs of a particular standard. Yet, identifying who uses specific standards is not straightforward. Formal standardisation bodies do not collect data on who uses the standards, how they are used, or under what conditions.

The ILOs examples

K6.1, K6.2, K7.1

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious games/Other

1. Case study

Case Study: Why do we use QWERTY| You're Doing it Wrong! Episode 5 | BBC Ideas:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AB9-qdPOIEg>

2. NSB material

Many NSBs provide free access to standards to educational institutions.
 Please contact your NSBs for more details, the complete list of the European NSBs can be found here: <https://sbs-sme.eu/standards-and-smes/standardisation-bodies/>

Good practice

To increase understanding of the role and power of users of standards the case on QWERTY keyboard can be used. The same case can be used for other topics too. The case QWERTY keyboard is good for explaining concepts installed base (in standardisation), dominant design, lock-in, and bandwagon effect.

Recommended sources

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

Figure 2-7. Topic 3.1. Users of Standards

Figure 2-8 shows an example of recommended teaching cases/serious games.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious games/Other

1.Serious Game: The World of Standardisation (DIN)

Keywords: Standardisation & Innovations

About: The World of Standardisation (DIN) is interactive board game with objective to develop a strategic understanding about standardisation in innovation context. Storyline: Congrats, for you innovation you won the Innovation Trophy! It comes with some time and money. The game offers different choices: patent, standard national/ European/ international, specifications; and combinations are possible. Decisions to be made within the team. The game provides real-life-inspired standardisation situations, and it is designed to inspire questions.

Details:

- Time to play: according to decisions Ca. 30 min per round.
- Group size: played in teams of 2-5, max. 2 teams per board.
- Target group: students, founders
- Languages: English, German
- Contact: amelie.leipprand@din.de

Figure 2-8. Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games within Topic 8.1. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation

Figure 2-9 shows an example of recommended sources.

Recommended sources

- Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Boita, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice. ETSI (Vol. 2). (especially, Chapter 5 on standardisation and innovation, Section 5.3 on standardisation and research, and Chapter 7 on standardisation and IPR).
- Bekkers, R. (2017). Where patents and standards come together. In: R. Hawkins (ed.) Handbook of Standards and Innovation. Edward Elgar Publishing. DOI: 10.4337/9781783470082.
- Hawkins (ed.) Handbook of Standards and Innovation. Edward Elgar Publishing. DOI: 10.4337/9781783470082.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- Baron, J., Spulber, D.F. (2018). Technology Standards and Standard Setting Organizations: Introduction to the Searle Center Database. Journal of Economics and Management Strategy, 27(3), pp. 462–503
- Bekkers, R., & Updegrave, A. (2013). A study of IPR policies and practices of a representative group of Standards Setting Organizations worldwide. Updated version. Washington, DC: National Academies of Science. Available at http://www.nap.edu/catalog.php?record_id=18510
- Bekkers, R., Blind, K., Coenen, H., Iverson, E. Jacobs, K., Hossain, K. (2006). Case studies on the interface between research and standardisation, and case studies on patent pools as a coordination mechanism. Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme, STREP, Priority 8, Contract 503 594.
- Bekkers, R., Duysters, G. & Verspagen, B. (2002). Intellectual property rights, strategic technology agreements and market structure: The case of GSM. In: Research Policy 31(7) 141-161. DOI: 10.1016/S0048-7333(01)00189-5.
- Bekkers, R., Henkel, J., Tur, E.M., Vorst, T. v.d., Driesse, M., Kang, B., Martinelli, A., Maas, W., Nijhof, B., Raiteri, E., Teubner, L. (2020). Pilot study for essentiality assessment of Standard Essential Patents, Thumm, N. editor(s), EUR 30111 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, JRC119894, doi:10.2760/68906, ISBN 978-92-76-16666-5.
- Bekkers, R., Tur, Elena M., Henkel, Joachim, Vorst, Tommy van der, Driesse, Menno, Contreras, Jorge L. (2022). Overcoming inefficiencies in patent licensing: A method to assess patent essentiality for technical standards. Research Policy 51(10). DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2022.104590.
- Blind, K., Baldan, F., Tardos, G., Kromer, L. et al., (2024). European standardisation panel survey – Final report, Baldan, F., Tardos, G. editor(s). Publications Office of the European Union, ISBN 978-92-68-12065-1, doi:10.2777/643814.
- Blind, K., Gauch, S. (2009): Research and standardisation in nanotechnology: Evidence from Germany. The Journal of Technology Transfer, 34(3), 320-342.
- Blind, K., Fenton, A. (2022). Standard-relevant publications: evidence, processes and influencing factors. Scientometrics (2022) 127:577–602. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-021-04210-8.
- Blind, K., Jungmittag, A., & Mangelsdorf, A. (2010). The Economic Benefits of Standardisation: An update of the study carried out by DIN in 2000. Berlin: DIN. <https://www.din.de/resource/blob/89552/88849fab0eaaaf56c5a3f5ee9959c5/economic-benefits-of-standardisation-en-data.pdf>.
- Blind, K., Kenney, M., Leiponen, A., Simcoe, T. (2023). Standards and innovation: A review and introduction to the special issue. Research Policy, Vol. 52(8), pp. 104830. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2023.104830.

Figure 2-9 Recommended Sources within Topic 8.1. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation

One of the most important part of the EDU4Standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool is sharing experience in teaching standardisation.

2.5.3 License of outcomes from the pilots

The design and implementation of each pilot in the EDU4Standards.eu project aim to fulfil and adhere to the new standard for dissemination of knowledge and new skills across European societies that has been set by the Horizon Europe (European Commission, 2021). Design and conduct of each pilot is informed by the data management plan (D1.2) that has been developed for the EDU4Standards.eu project with detailed recommendations for ensuring appropriate data processing and maintenance of all digital assets being created (European Union, 2023), obtained, used, shared, and archived during conduct of the project.

To the extent possible, each pilot will adhere to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles to comply with important goals of Horizon Europe (European Commission, 2021). Related to each pilot, a range of different digital assets (European Union, 2023) will be created, obtained, used, shared, and archived.

Digital assets created and obtained for use in pilots include documents (standards, lecture notes, books, book chapters, peer-reviewed articles, and other types of learning and teaching material), pre-recorded presentations (audio and video files), serious games (e.g. software applications with associated assets), software projects that implement standards (Gamalielsson et al., 2024) (Lundell, Persson, & Lings, 2007) (e.g. source code for software that highlights software implementations of standards, and other types of software applications), data sets (e.g. data and metadata data about standards, data sets provided as open content via public platforms, etc.). Data sets and source code for software systems, as well as software applications created and obtained for use in pilots may be provided for use in specific pilots via different distribution models under the FAIR principles, including: local use and scrutiny (on-premise), and as cloud services (e.g. via SaaS (Software-as-a-Service) solutions).

During design of each pilot, a range of different types of digital assets (including documents, pre-recorded presentations, software applications, data sets) will be created and made available according to the FAIR principles for use (and reuse) in specific pilots. To the extent possible, other (non-digital) assets to be used in pilots should also be provided under the FAIR principles (e.g. provided under an 'open hardware' licence). In acknowledging that such licencing may not be possible in all cases, the design of each pilot aims to ensure provision of all non-digital assets under terms and conditions that adhere to (at least some of) the FAIR principles (in particular the 'F' and 'A' principles of the FAIR principles).

For licensing of content, the EDU4Standards.eu project recommends use of two of the (totally six) different license types from version 4 of the International Creative Commons Licences (Creative Commons, n.d.). Specifically, the CC-BY 4.0 licence (Creative Commons-b, n.d.) and the CC-BY SA 4.0 license are the two recommended licence types for all content to be used for each digital asset that contains learning and

teaching content created during design of each pilot. Both CC-BY 4.0 and CC-BY SA 4.0 ensure appropriate attribution (of copyright holders and the EDU4Standards.eu project) and promote broad use and sharing of created digital assets. In addition, for promoting a continued openness of digital assets created during design of each pilot the CC-BY SA 4.0 is recommended as this licence type, with its so-called copyleft (Software Freedom Conservancy, n.d.) effect, requires that digital assets provided under 'SA' ('ShareAlike') must be distributed under the same licence.

For licensing of software, the EDU4Standards.eu project recommends use of the MPL-2.0 licence (Software Package Data Exchange [SPDX], n.d.) (Mozilla Public License 2.0). The MPL-2.0 licence is a software licence that complies with both the Free Software Definition (Free Software Foundation, 2025) and the Open Source Definition (Open Source Initiative, 2025). Hence, software provided under the MPL-2.0 licence is commonly referred to as FOSS (Free and Open Source Software). Provision of software under the MPL-2.0 licence promotes the FAIR principles and ensures compliance with the aim of promoting broad use, reuse, and sharing of developed software. Several studies, including a commissioned study from an EU (Blind et al., 2021), show that FOSS contributes significant values in the EU.

Use of the MPL-2.0 licence enables use and reuse of the software in both commercial and non-commercial contexts. The copyleft effect inherent in the MPL-2.0 licence ensures continued openness when the software is distributed for use in other contexts (e.g. in other pilots) (Lundell et al., 2022). However, in case there are strong reasons for providing software under some other Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) licence, for example in case there are good reasons for reusing already existing appropriate software components from other software projects that provide software under some other FOSS licence (e.g. the LGPL-2.1 licence), the EDU4Standards.eu project recommends using some other FOSS licence with a copyleft effect. In order to comply with the FAIR principles, there are strong reasons to use a software licence with a copyleft effect (namely to ensure continued openness after distribution of the software) (Lundell, 2020).

During the implementation of each pilot, many different types of digital assets will be used, shared, reused. To the extent possible, digital assets provided under terms and conditions that comply with the FAIR principles will be used.

3 Pilots Design

3.1 Pilots' Design Methodology

Task 3.1 focuses on designing pilots by translating the general findings and outputs of Work Package 2 (WP2) into specific pilot designs. The aim is to ensure that the educational content aligns with the real-world needs of various HEIs and diverse learning contexts.

Recognizing the challenges inherent in this task, the project consortium agreed that partners involved in WP2 would also participate in Task 3.1. to establish an effective bridge between WP2 and WP3. This collaboration ensures coherence and relevance in the pilot designs. To achieve this, task members have planned the following additional milestones to guide the task activities between months M11 (November 2024) and M17 (May 2025) of the project:

- WP2-WP3 Bridging, Madrid Workshop, November 2024
- Pilot design template definition: December 2024
- Pilot design template filling out, Initial draft: January 29th, 2025
- D3.1 report ToC Draft, Pilot design Second draft: February 22th – Graz Workshop, 2025
- D3.1 Report Partners contribution March 20th, 2025
- Pilot design – Peer review: March 20th, 2025
- D3.1 Report - first draft April 5th, 2025
- D3.1 report – Second draft: April 21st, 2025
- D3.1 report- Final version, May 5th, 2025
- D3.1 report – Reviewed: May 20th, 2025

We followed a structured approach to designing the pilots, ensuring that the educational content meets industry and academic needs while aligning with EU values and ensuring the bridging between the ITCoS and the pilots. The activities carried out are as follows:

- Survey: Edu4Standard – Bridging WP2 Results with WP3 (T3.1 Pilot Design Plan) (October 21st, 2024)
 - Objectives:
 - Identify expected student knowledge, relevant European values, and the initial set of materials and learning methods to be used in pilots for standardisation education.

- Collect useful information to map the WP2 outcomes to WP3 and to prepare the WP2-WP3 workshop (Madrid).WP2 – WP3 Workshop – Madrid 14 – 15 November 2024
- WP2 task leaders present WP2 outcomes to WP3 pilot owners and discuss how these results can be applied to meet the specific requirements of each pilot (Nov. 14).
- The pilots' leaders discussed the survey results and agreed on the initial draft of the pilot template design (Nov. 15).
- ILO Framework Operationalization Meeting (September 6, 2024)
 - Conducted with the Human Factor in Digital Transformation (HFDT) network, attended online by T3.1 members, to define the strategy the pilots should follow for selecting and implementing the ILOs.
- Monthly Follow-up Meetings
 - Regular Task 3.1 meetings to monitor progress and address challenges in pilot design.
 - Team meeting: 10/12/2024
 - Team meeting: 29/01/2025
- Workshop: University of Graz Trainer's School – Designing Course Methodologies (Feb. 21st, 2025)
 - Focused on developing effective teaching methodologies for standardisation courses.
- Workshop: Task 3.1 – Identifying Gaps and Selecting Materials (22/02/2025)
 - Objectives:
 - Identify gaps detected in WP2.
 - Define materials to be shared among pilots.
 - Select serious games for integration into standardisation teaching.
- Peer Review and Pilot Self-Assessment
 - Each pilot design template was assigned to a reviewer, who provided comments and suggestions to improve the quality of the pilot design.
 - T3.7 developed a self-assessment template to check whether the quality of their pilot set-up complies with edu4Standard.eu ideas.
- Survey on Identified Gaps in Standardisation Teaching and Sharing of Teaching Materials
 - Pilot leaders completed a survey to indicate how the identified gaps would be addressed through the pilot designs and to specify which materials they would be able to share to enhance standardisation teaching.

- D3.1 Pilot design report edition and review
 - The results of the above activities were incorporated into the table of contents of the report, which was adopted during the T3.1 Workshop in Graz. As a final step, the review process by the partners TUD, POLIMI, and FHG was carried out.

The expected results from Task 3.1 primarily concern the implementation of the Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) defined in WP2. This involves designing each pilot, identifying existing gaps and specifying how they will be addressed, and defining the teaching materials that each pilot can share with other pilots and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) for standardisation education, particularly in distance learning formats (shared through the EDU4Standards Teaching Support Tool (EDU4Standards, n.d.) or other online platforms).

However, additional important outcomes have also been achieved. Notably, the development of the Pilot Design Template (which will be used for designing future pilots in upcoming pilot calls) and the Pilot Self-Assessment Template (a useful tool for establishing pilot quality and monitoring pilot implementation) are among the key results.

3.1.1 Pilots' Design Template

The pilot design template (Figure 3-1) is based on the Study Guide Manual Course applied by TUD (Delft University of Technology, n.d.) and the Learning Guide (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, n.d.) used at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid to describe course contents and planning. A draft structure was discussed during the T3.1 meeting in December 2024 and approved with some modifications in January 2025. Afterward, the partners filled out the template with the EU specific contents for each pilot.

Pilot Design Template
Developing and Customizing Pilot Courses

University/School/Department: _____
Program: _____

Pilot Information

Course Code: _____
Course Name: _____
Semester: _____
ECTS credits: _____
Contact Hours: _____
Teacher: _____
Module manager/coordinator: _____
Course Language: _____
Course Format: _____
Course date: _____

Pilot Description

General course description: _____
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements): _____
Level(s) from the ILDs framework: _____

European Values and interests

Intended Learning Outcomes

Description of Course Content

List of topics to be covered:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
-

Practices and projects.

Timeline and Milestones

Week/ session	Lecture	Practice or Project	Format methods (Presential, online)	assessment exams activities
1	e.g. Introduction to Standardization (2 hrs.)	Case Study: Basics of IoT Standards	Presential	Participation and discussion e.g. planned Test (30 min)
2				
3				
....				

Assessment conditions

Teaching Methods

Teaching Materials and Resources

Evaluation

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

Confidentiality

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

Figure 3-1. Pilot design template.

Its value is twofold. On the one hand, it provides lecturers with a clear framework to define competencies, skills, contents, teaching methods, resources, assessment systems, and audience requirements. On the other hand, students can use it as a tool to plan their activities and manage the effort required for each course.

The pilot template includes the following details:

- **Academic information.** It describes the institution responsible for running the pilot. If the pilot is part of a formal program, then it also includes the program name.
- **The pilot information section** includes the name of the bachelor's or master's program to which the pilot belongs. If the pilot is not part of a formal degree program, please specify the relevant program type, such as lifelong learning, a summer school, or an Athens program. It also includes information on the semester when the course will be offered within the academic year, and the ECTS credits reflecting its workload and academic value. Contact hours indicate the total amount of direct instructional time between instructors and students. The course is delivered by designated teachers, with a module manager or coordinator overseeing its organization and administration. The language of instruction is specified to ensure accessibility for students, and the course format—whether in-person, online, or hybrid—defines the mode of delivery. Lastly, the course date marks the official start and end of the program, providing a clear timeline for its duration.
- **The pilot description section** provides an overview of the course, outlining its objectives, scope, and teaching approach. It defines the target audience, specifying the intended students and any prerequisites required for enrolment. To ensure a structured educational experience, it also specifies the level(s) of the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) addressed by the course.
- **European values and interests.** This section emphasizes how the pilot contents align with the EU's priorities in standardisation while fostering knowledge and skills that meet industry needs and regulatory frameworks. Although the primary focus is standardisation, the course also promotes fundamental European principles, reinforcing the EU's commitment to a fair, democratic, and sustainable global market.

In addition to conveying standardisation expertise, this section articulates how the pilots are designed to support standardisation in line with key European Union values, such as human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human rights, including those of minorities. This approach contributes to equipping students with the critical skills necessary to navigate the intersection of standardisation, governance, and social responsibility in an increasingly interconnected world.

- **Intended Learning Outcomes.** These outcomes define the knowledge, skills, and competencies participants will acquire upon completion (Veljanova et al., 2024). They should align with the educational objectives of the pilot curriculum and be measurable, ensuring that students develop theoretical understanding and practical expertise in standardisation.
- **Contents and Schedule.** This is a structured list of topics covered throughout the pilot, ensuring alignment with industry needs and knowledge areas as identified in D2.3 (Mijatovic et al., 2025). The course should incorporate relevant topics from the Initial Topics in Knowledge Areas table (D2.3), which defines the key subjects to be taught based on industry demands. Additionally, in accordance with the selected teaching methods, the pilot should integrate practical activities and projects that complement theoretical learning, reinforcing the application of standardisation concepts in real-world scenarios. A detailed schedule should be included, outlining the progression of the course, key activities, and milestones to ensure a well-structured and comprehensive learning experience.
- The **Timeline and Milestones** section provides a structured breakdown of the course content, drawing the weekly or session-based progression of lectures, practical activities, and assessments. This schedule ensures that learning objectives are met in a systematic and organized manner, balancing theoretical instruction with hands-on applications. Each session should specify the lecture topics, covering the theoretical foundations of standardisation, along with any practical activities or projects that complement the learning experience. The format and methods of instruction should also be clearly defined, indicating whether the session will be in-person, online, or hybrid. Additionally, this section should detail the assessment and exam activities, outlining when evaluations will take place and the methods used to assess student progress. Providing a comprehensive and structured schedule will help instructors and students track key milestones, thus ensuring that all course components are effectively delivered and aligned with the intended learning outcomes.
- **Students' Assessment and Grading.** It establishes the criteria and methods for evaluating the student's performance throughout the course. It provides a structured assessment framework, ensuring transparency in grading policies and the requirements for successful completion. The course should define the assessment methods, which may include written exams, project submissions, practical assignments, or other evaluation techniques that align with the intended learning outcomes.

Additionally, clear grading criteria should be outlined, specifying the minimum requirements for passing and how different components of the course contribute to the final grade. Participation requirements should also be explicitly stated, indicating whether attendance, active engagement, or

the completion of specific milestones are necessary for success. The course should establish submission deadlines for assignments, projects, or other deliverables to promote effective time management.

Moreover, the course should uphold academic integrity policies, ensuring assessment fairness and ethical standards. Finally, a certification of completion or a relevant standard skill certification should be defined for students who successfully fulfil the course requirements, formally recognizing their participation and achievement.

- **Teaching Methods.** It describes the pedagogical strategies and instructional methodologies employed in the course. Deliverables D2.2 (Fomin et al., 2025) and D2.3 (Mijatovic et al., 2025) provide a set of examples illustrating different teaching methods that align with the topics being taught, serving as a guide for selecting the most appropriate approaches. These methods should be carefully chosen to foster engagement, encourage active learning, and promote the practical application of standardisation concepts. The use of technology, including digital tools and online platforms, could enhance accessibility and flexibility in learning. Additionally, serious games and collaborative learning methodologies can be integrated to promote experiential learning, problem-solving, and teamwork.
- **Teaching Materials and Resources.** It provides a comprehensive list of the materials used to support the course, ensuring they cover the topics included in the course content section. These resources should facilitate effective learning and offer both theoretical foundations and practical applications in standardisation education. The course materials may include presentations, textbooks, research articles, case studies, instructional videos, and digital tools designed to enhance student engagement and comprehension. Special emphasis should be placed on resources and methodologies that address the gaps identified in WP2, ensuring that the contents developed within each pilot effectively meet industry and educational needs. Additionally, interactive and technology-enhanced learning materials, such as online simulations, serious games, and collaborative platforms, should be incorporated where applicable to promote active participation and experiential learning.
- **Course Evaluation.** It outlines the procedures for assessing the effectiveness of the course and measuring the students' satisfaction. At the end of the course, a comprehensive evaluation will be conducted with participants to gather feedback on whether the course met their expectations, what aspects were most beneficial, and what areas could be improved. This process may include student surveys, feedback forms, focus group discussions, and instructor reflections to collect qualitative and quantitative insights. Additionally, the evaluation should include or describe mechanisms to assess

the effectiveness of the teaching methods, course materials, and overall engagement to identify opportunities for refinement in future editions.

- **Reuse of Teaching Materials.** It defines the conditions under which course materials can be reused in other institutions or contexts. As EDU4Standards aims to scale up education on standardisation in Europe, the pilots should actively contribute to this goal by ensuring that the educational resources developed can be shared and utilized beyond the initial pilot implementation. Any material developed by EDU4Standards or its partners and used in the pilots may be made available for use elsewhere (e.g. uploaded to the EDU4Standards repository), unless subject to copyright restrictions. This section should specify which materials can be reused by third parties and under what conditions. It should also clearly state the associated copyright agreements, including whether materials are released under open licenses (e.g., Creative Commons) or if they are restricted to specific uses. If applicable, this section should also detail any permissions required for reproduction, distribution, or adaptation of the materials, ensuring transparent and responsible sharing of educational resources.
- **Confidentiality.** This section establishes the policies regarding the disclosure and protection of information used in the course. It should clearly define the confidentiality policies that apply to the course content, materials, and participant data. This includes specifying how sensitive information shared during the course - such as proprietary data, unpublished research, or personal information of participants - will be handled, stored, and protected. If certain materials are subject to non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) or institutional restrictions (e.g. from University or Industry), those conditions should be explicitly stated. Additionally, any limitations on the reuse or distribution of course-related information should be clearly stated to ensure compliance with ethical, legal, and institutional guidelines.
- **Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics.** It defines the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to evaluate the impact and effectiveness of the course pilot across different education levels (e.g., Master's, Bachelor's, Lifelong Learning, or Researcher Training). The evaluation should incorporate both quantitative and qualitative metrics to provide a comprehensive assessment of the pilot's success. Quantitative metrics may include enrolment numbers, completion rates, assessment results, and participant satisfaction scores. Qualitative insights should capture feedback from participants and instructors, observed challenges, and examples of best practices, offering a deeper understanding of the course's impact and areas for improvement. Ensuring that all collected data is accurate, contextualized, and aligned with course objectives will facilitate the evaluation of the course's effectiveness and impact.

This template will also serve as a tool for designing the upcoming call for pilots (see section 3.4).

3.2 Designing Pilots

This section describes the pilot design developed by the pilot leaders as part of the work conducted under Task 3.1. The design is based on the ITCoS framework developed in WP2. Each pilot's design includes elements such as intended learning outcomes (ILOs) tailored to the specific level and audience, as well as teaching methods, materials, and knowledge areas, among others. The quality of the design has been ensured through an internal peer review and self-assessment process, which provides feedback and establishes the basis for pilot evaluation.

Table 3-1 Pilot design overview

Pilot Name	Course Name / Audience	Contact Hours / course format	Course Date	ILOs Levels	Teaching methods and content
Bachelor – University of Belgrade	Standardisation (Standardizacija)	13 weeks 26 hours lectures & 26h practical work Format: Physical	March - June 2026	Bachelor Level (level 6)	Active learning methods based on class discussion, workshops, work on teaching case studies and serious games and assignments
Delft University Pilot	Technology Battles Master students of heterogenous backg	3h per week / 7weeks: 21h Format: Physical and online	Fall	Master Level (level 7)	blend of interactive teaching components including interactive lectures, real life examples, and presentations of students. Teaching game
Technical University Berlin	Standardization and Sustainability. Bachelor's and Master's students of heterogeneous backgrounds.	4 hours/week for 15 weeks	Oct 2025 - Feb 2026	Bachelor & Master (Level 6 & 7)	Lectures and exercises in class, serious games, presentations, excursions if possible
Passion in Action (POLIMI)	Engineering graduate students.	10 hours Format: Preferably in-presence (possible hybrid)	Sept-Dec 2025	Level 7	Teaching by questions Teaching by examples Quizzes, Case study approach and game
Summer School (UGZ)	Teaching Standardisation in line with EU values and interests for HEI teachers and lecturers from all academic fields	2 weeks online, 5 days in person (60 hours) Format: Online and in person	Fall 2025	Level 6,7, 8	Flipped Classroom, Problem-Based Learning, Peer Learning/Teaching, Micro-Inputs + Application, Games (DIN, ISO, else), Reflective Practice
In-Company Training Eindhoven University & Tilburg University	Standardisation in High-Tech for Practitioners	8 hrs (A1 & A2), 2 hrs (B1) (18 hours)	Spring/Summer 2025	Various (4-7)	Classroom teaching (with on-line component), and a serious game

In-Company Training SBS (Small Business Standards) Standards for SMEs	Younger engineers Mid-career engineers Senior, higher level managers	10 hours	Spring-Summer 2026	Level 4	Interactive methods integrating real life examples, SME case studies, and non-formal learning methods
EARTO Pilot - Fraunhofer ISI	Beginners “Research & Development and Standardisation” Intermediate experts “Effectively participating in standardisation bodies” Sophisticated experts “Strategic standardization for RTOs”	6 webinars; 4,5 hours	Starting in fall 2025	Level 4, 5, 6, 7	Online lectures with Q&A option

Table 4-1 presents an overview of the pilot designs, highlighting that the pilots cover levels 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 of the ILOs frameworks, with a total of 236 hours dedicated to teaching standardisation to different target audiences. Another important aspect to note is that the implementation of the pilots will be carried out not only by various universities across Europe, but also by companies. The following subsections present the final pilot designs that will be implemented.

3.2.1 Pilot at university B.Sc. level

The *Standardisation* course, introduced in 1997 at the Faculty of Organisational Sciences, University of Belgrade (UB), forms part of the *Quality Management and Standardisation* module since its redefinition in 2015. The course focuses on the business-oriented aspects of standardisation, particularly from a company perspective. Under the leadership of Ivana Mijatović since 2011, the course content has been significantly enhanced, supported by a dedicated textbook first published in 2015 and updated in 2019.

The course aims to provide students with advanced knowledge of standardisation, its role, and its impact on modern business practices and global markets. Upon completion, students are expected to apply standardisation principles effectively, identify relevant standards and organisations, understand the implementation impact, and engage in standardisation processes.

Teaching is based on active learning methodologies, combining lectures, case studies, team projects, and interactive workshops to foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills in real-world business contexts.

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department:	University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organizational Sciences
Program:	Management and Organization (Bachelor program, 240 ECTS)

Pilot information

Course Code:	na
Course Name:	Standardisation (Standardizacija)
Semester:	Summer semester; 4th
ECTS credits:	5
Contact Hours:	Classes: Lectures (2 h per a week = total 26); Tutorials (exercises) (2 h per a week = total 26); Required literature 300 p (5p per h) = total 60 h Specific assignments & project paper = total 28 h
Teachers:	Ivana Mijatović (professor, lectures), Biljana Tošić and Sara Dimitrijević (teaching assistants, practical work)
Module manager/coordinator:	Ivana Mijatović
Course Language:	Serbian, (English tbd)
Course Format:	physical
Course date:	Summer semester, March to June 2026 (2025?)

Pilot Description

General course description:	<p>The Standardisation course was first introduced into the curriculum at the Faculty of Organizational Sciences UB in 1997 within the Quality Management module under the name Standardization System. In 2015, the module and department were renamed to Quality Management and Standardization.</p> <p>The Standardization course focuses on the business aspects of standardization. Since 2011, the course has been taught by Ivana Mijatović, who has significantly enhanced its content to emphasize the business aspects of standardization, particularly from a company perspective. The first textbook for this course was published in 2015, with a second edition released in 2019. It is main literature with others (see Resources), it is printed book publically available in school bookshop.</p> <p>The main objective of the course is to provide students with advanced academic knowledge in the field of standardization, helping them understand its importance, impact, and the application of standards in various markets and modern business practices.</p>
------------------------------------	--

	<p>An active student will be capable of effectively applying standardization concepts, recognizing their significance, and understanding their impact on diverse markets and contemporary business environments. Specifically, students will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search for and select appropriate standards, • Understand the general impact of standards' implementation • Recognize the need for participation in the standardization process, • Identify relevant standardization organizations for specific business contexts, • Apply methods for evaluating the effects of standard implementation ... <p>The course employs active learning methods through lectures and exercises, focusing on real-world problems and internationally recognized case studies. Students engage in discussions, interactive workshops, team-based problem-solving, and independent research.</p>
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):	Undergraduate level Bachelor students, second year of study with no previous knowledge on standardisation.
Level(s) from the ILOs framework:	Bachelor level (Level 6)

European Values and interests

<p>The approach to European values is twofold.</p> <p>First, it involves carefully nurturing human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human rights, including those of minorities, in both classroom teaching and all educational activities. This is our obligation, as the first article of the Constitution of the Republic of Serbia addresses these principles in its opening paragraph:</p> <p><i>“The Republic of Serbia is the state of the Serbian people and all citizens who live in it, based on the rule of law and social justice, the principles of civil democracy, human and minority rights and freedoms, and belonging to European principles and values.”</i> (https://www.srbija.gov.rs/tekst/en/130144/constitution-of-serbia.php)</p> <p>The second approach focuses on raising awareness among students about human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human and minority rights in the context of standardization. To achieve this, we incorporate serious games (e.g., <i>Serious Smiley Game</i> addressing freedom and democracy in the context of standardization) and carefully developed teaching case studies into standardization classes. We will follow Council Recommendation on Promoting Common Values, Inclusive Education, and the European Dimension</p>

of Teaching (2018/C 195/01). [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0607\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H0607(01)).

Intended Learning Outcomes

TABLE 1: Decomposition of the ILOs		
Topic (to be further adjusted)		On completion of this course (not separate topics), the student will be able to:
Topic 1	The importance of standards and standardization in modern business. Concept of standardization and standards. The connection between standardization and globalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain that the global market is the source of demand for standards; • discuss the different positions of countries in the context of standardization; • explain in what sense standardization can be defined as a process of regulation of industries; • elaborate why standards are the result of the agreement of stakeholders in the market and the achievement of agreement regarding the solution of a problem; • explain that there are many definitions and that different organizations define standardization and standards differently according to their activities and goals; • explain the rationale for and meaning of standardization definitions and standards used in voluntary consensus-based standardization • identify the reasons for the creation and meaning of general definitions for standardization and standards.
Topic 2	Users of the standard. General objectives of standardisation, roles and domains of standardization.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • differentiate who the direct and indirect users of the standard are; • discuss what the general objectives of standardization • name and discuss different standardization mechanisms and different types of standards and • identify some the links of standardization to other disciplines.
Topic 3	The interconnection between standardisation and the market. Mechanisms enabling the success of standards in the market. Dominant design, installed base, lock-in phenomenon and bandwagoning phenomenon.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • discuss the relationship between standards and markets • explain what the terms installed base and dominant design refer to, and what are the phenomena of lock-in and bandwagoning and what are the reasons for their occurrence

Topic 4	Types of standardization and classification of standards.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain that there are different types of standardization and that the classification of standards is not final; • explain the differences between anticipatory, retrospective and competitive standardization; • explain the differences between ex-ante and ex-post standardization; • explain the differences between formal and informal standardization and understand why this division can be questioned; • explain the difference between horizontal and vertical standards; • explain what de jure and de facto standards are and • explain that standards developed by industry associations, consortia or companies may become formal standards.
Topic 5	Significance and effects of the application of standards. Economic effects of applying standards that solve the problem of: compatibility, interoperability and interface establishment; minimum requirements for quality or safety; the existence of too many differences; information or measurements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain and demonstrate (based on the cases) why the implementation of standards is important for business; • elaborate of why the implementation of standards is important for business in transition and industrialized countries; • explain the links between standards and markets; • explain what are the key effects of applying standards that solve different groups of problems and • explain what information asymmetry is and how implementing standards can help reduce it.
Topic 6	History of standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain the roots of the connection between metrology and standardization; • explain that standardization has its roots in Ancient Greece and Ancient Egypt; • explain the role of standardization in the industrial revolution; • explain how the implementation of standards can be an obstacle to progress; • discuss that standardization as a separate discipline is still developing and • explain the emergence of standard inertia.
Topic 7	Voluntary consensus-based standardization. International, regional and national	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrate that standards are developed by a large number of organizations that often collaborate with each other;

	<p>standardization. Formal organizations for standardization.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain that standards are developed by companies, state institutions (interstate institutions); national, regional and international organizations for standardization; professional and industrial associations; business associations, consortia and forums; • compare the position of standardization organizations in relation to the global, regional or national market; • elaborate the reasons for the establishment and development of standardization organizations; • differentiate the different roles of governments in standardization and • understand the need for the establishment of specialized agencies of the United Nations that, among other things, deal with the development of standards.
Topic 8	<p>The European system of standardization. The role of standardization in the European common market. Connection of European directives and standards. CE mark</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain that each country arranges its standardization system according to the needs of its industry or its own capabilities; • discuss that differences in economic and industrial development, political differences and traditions significantly determine the standardization system and management of the largest countries; • explain why these differences exist and what caused the key reforms in them. • explain ESS, its origin and the role in single market. • explain the role of harmonized standards and CE mark
Topic 9	<p>Basics of the US standardization system. Basics of the PR China standardization system</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain the differences between the standardization systems of the European Union, the United States of America, and the People's Republic of China
Topic 10	<p>Consortia based standardization. Standardization in professional and/or industrial associations, business associations, consortia and forums. Effects of Consortia based standards on the market.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain market and industry needs to create new standards and new development mechanisms; • explain what business associations, consortia and forums are; • explain why standards developed within business associations and forums are important for the global market; • explain their pros and cons; • explain what is the phenomenon of standards battles and their pros and cons and

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain why and when business associations, consortia and forums develop open and/or proprietary standards.
Topic 11	Standardization at the level of a company. Internal standards development.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the company's motivations for developing its own standards; understand what forms standards developed in companies can take; understand how a standard developed by a company can become a sectoral or international standard; understand the benefits that the company has from active participation in standardization processes and explain what are the duties of the standardization manager in the company.
Topic 12	Standardization and technology transfer. The paradox of standardization and innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand the role of standardization in technology transfer understand the connection between standardization and innovation understand the concept and importance of patents that are essential to the SEP standards
Topic 13	The connection between standards and laws Ethical aspects of standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understand that the application of technical regulations is mandatory and the standards are voluntary; explain how the application of the standard can become mandatory; understand that there is no general or general regulation of standardization, but that the World Trade Organization acts in that context as well; understand the ways in which standards are referenced in legislation and understand that the legal statuses of national standardization organizations in different countries are different.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discuss the different ethical aspects on standardization, European values and WTO rules for development standards
--	--	---

Description of Course Content

<p>List of topics to be covered:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The importance of standards and standardization in modern business. Concept of standardization and standards. The connection between standardization and globalization Users of the standard. General objectives of standardisation, roles and domains of standardization. The interconnection between standardisation and the market. Mechanisms enabling the success of standards in the market. Dominant design, installed base, lock-in phenomenon and bandwagoning phenomenon. Types of standardization and classification of standards. Significance and effects of the application of standards. Economic effects of applying standards that solve the problem of: compatibility, interoperability and interface establishment; minimum requirements for quality or safety; the existence of too many differences; information or measurements. History of standardisation Voluntary consensus-based standardization. International, regional and national standardization. Formal organizations for standardization. The European system of standardization. The role of standardization in the European common market. Connection of European directives and standards. CE mark Basics of the US standardization system. Basics of the PR China standardization system. Consortia based standardization. Standardization in professional and/or industrial associations, business associations, consortia and forums. Effects of Consortia based standards on the market. Standardization at the level of the organization. Internal standards development model. Standardization and technology transfer. The paradox of standardization and innovation. The connection between standards and laws. Ways in which standards can be referenced in the regulation. <p>Practices and projects. 26 classes of practical work is dedicated to analysis of industries through the lenses of standardisation, work on teaching case studies and technical skills related to standardisation (e.g. how to find right standard).</p>
--

Timeline and Milestones

Week/ session	Lecture	Practice or Project	Format / methods (Presential, online)	assessment / exams activities
1	The importance of standards and		2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work	Participation and Class discussion

	standardization in modern business. Concept of standardization and standards. The connection between standardization and globalization			
2	Users of the standard. General objectives of standardisation, roles and domains of standardization.	<i>Workshop</i>	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
3	The interconnection between standardisation and the market. Mechanisms enabling the success of standards in the market.	Serious game: Standards and Exports	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
4	Types of standardization and classification of standards	Workshop	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	
5	Significance and effects of the application of standards. Economic effects of applying standards that solve the problem of: compatibility, interoperability and interface establishment; minimum requirements for quality or safety; the existence of too many differences; information or measurements.	Workshop: ISO methodology	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
6	History of standardisation	Workshop: ISO methodology	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
7	Coloquial Exam			Test
8	Voluntary consensus-based standardization. International, regional and national standardization. Formal	Serious Game	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>

	organizations for standardization.			
9	The European system of standardization. The role of standardization in the European common market. Connection of European directives and standards. CE mark	Case Study: Toys safety, AI Act	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
10	Basics of the US standardization system. Basics of the PR China standardization system	Case Study: JUGO in Amerika	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
11	Consortia based standardization. Standardization in professional and/or industrial associations, business associations, consortia and forums. Effects of Consortia based standards on the market.	Case Study: HD DVD vs Blu Ray	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
12	Standardization at the level of the organization. Internal standards development model.	Case Study: IKEA Standards	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	
13	Standardization and technology transfer. The paradox of standardization and innovation	Case Study: Green Transition supported by EasyStreets Serious Game: The world of Standards	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>
14	The connection between standards and laws. Ways in which standards can be referenced in the regulation.	Case study: Coca Cola and Pepsi in India	<i>2 classes of lecture 2 classes of practical work</i>	<i>Participation and Class discussion</i>

Assessment Conditions

Methods of Assessment: The **Colloquial Exam** (mid-course) and the **Final Exam** (end of course) are written exams and account for **60%** of the final grade, class scores, practical assignments and paper (40%)

Grading Criteria: the minimum requirement for passing is 51 out of 100 score

Participation Requirements: For successful completion participation in 60% of classes (lectures and practical work) is mandatory.

Academic Integrity is regulated by the University.

Certification (certificate that confirms that a participant has followed the course) – no such a certificate at the moment.

Teaching Methods

Active teaching methods based on class discussion, workshops, work on teaching case studies and serious games and assignments. The pilot should help us to develop attractive and engaging teaching approach appropriate for young bachelor students. We would like to pilot the student to student approach as well as flipping classroom.

Teaching Materials and Resources

1. Mijatović, I. Standardizacija 1, Fakultet organizacionih nauka, 2019. (text book in Serbian language)
2. Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition.
3. Murphy, C. N., Yates, J.A., The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) : global governance through voluntary consensus, Taylor & Francis, 2009.
4. Hesser W., Feilzer A., & De Vries H. (2010). *Standardisation in Companies and Markets*, Helmut Schmidt University Germany, Erasmus University of Rotterdam, the Netherlands.
5. Yates J., & Murphy C. N. (2019). *Engineering Rules: Global Standard Setting since 1880*. Hagley Library Studies in Business, Technology, and Politics. Johns Hopkins University Press. Baltimore.
6. Serious Games: Serious Smiley Game (UB, HSbooster.eu) and the World of Standardisation (DIN).

Evaluation

Anonymous survey and subsequent in-class discussion

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

Planned to develop two EDU4standard.eu teaching cases on EU competition, green and digital transition.

Confidentiality

n/a

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

Number of enrolled students: about 280
 Completion rate: 95%
 Satisfaction rate: >4 (out of 5)
 Assessment results: Average score 75

3.2.2 Pilot at university M.Sc. level

At the master level, two pilots have been designed. The first, proposed by Delft University of Technology, is intended for Master's students in Management of Technology, who come from heterogeneous academic backgrounds. The second, proposed by the Technical University of Berlin, targets both Bachelor's and Master's students, also with diverse educational profiles.

3.2.2.1 Pilot at university M.Sc.- Technology battles- TUD

This course provides students with foundational knowledge of the three main stages of the standardization process: committee-based standardization, market-based standardization, and standards adoption. It examines the motivations behind firms' engagement and sustained commitment to standardization efforts.

In particular, the course emphasizes the strategic approaches firms may adopt to succeed in market-based standardization and explores the key factors influencing the adoption of standards. By understanding these factors, students gain insight into how to avoid scenarios such as lock-in to suboptimal technological standards.

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department:	Delft University of Technology
Program:	Management of Technology

Pilot information

Course Code:	TPM959A
Course Name:	Technology battles
Semester:	Fall
ECTS credits:	

Contact Hours:	3 hours per week for 7 weeks
Teachers:	Geerten van de Kaa
Module manager/coordinator:	Geerten van de Kaa
Course Language:	
Course Format:	Physical and online
Course date:	September 2026 – November – 2026

Pilot Description

General course description:	<p>This course teaches students the basic background of two main stages involved in the standardization process: committee-based standardization and market-based standardization. It teaches students why firms engage in standardization and why they keep being committed to the process.</p> <p>For market-based standardization, the course focuses on the strategies that firms can apply in order to reach success with their standards. Also, the course studies factors for the adoption of standards.</p> <p>By teaching students these factors, they also better understand how to e.g. avoid a situation of locking in unfavorable technological standards.</p> <p>standardization three stages; committee-based standardization, market-based standardization and Standards adoption.</p>
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):	Master students of heterogenous backgrounds
Level(s) from the ILOs framework:	Master (level 7)

European Values and interests

In our course on technology battles, we explicitly incorporate key European values such as democracy, equality, and freedom. Democracy is addressed by teaching students about the committee-based standardization process, in which all relevant stakeholders are invited to participate and consensus is reached through open, inclusive dialogue. This process also reflects the value of equality, as it emphasizes equal opportunity for input from diverse actors. Furthermore, equality is reinforced by discussing how successful standards should be accessible to all, ensuring fair use and benefit across society. Freedom is embedded in the course by encouraging students to think critically, and choose a case study of a standards battle that they study in depth. Moreover, the programs to which the course is attached explicitly aim for diversity in the student population.

Intended Learning Outcomes

After the course students are able to understand the theoretical background of standardization and they are able to understand how firms can direct the standardization process in its different stages. The most recent academic contributions are implemented in the course so that the learner will have highly specialised knowledge which is at the forefront of knowledge in standardization (which relates to K7.1 (“to have highly specialised knowledge, some of which is at the forefront of knowledge in standards and standardisation within one’s field and at the interface between different fields, as the basis for original thinking and/or research“ (see deliverable 2.1)).

Furthermore, by the end of the course, students understand how firms can achieve consensus during standard development (which relates to S7.6 (“lead standardisation committees” (see deliverable 2.1)), how firms can achieve standards dominance and which factors affect standards adoption. This gives them the toolkit for understanding how the process can be influenced in a certain direction (that is favourable for society) (which related to S7.3 “understand the key determinants of successful standardisation” (see deliverable 2.1)).

In the course, also more specific topics are addressed including the relationship between standardization and innovation (relating to S7.7; deliverable 2.1)

Description of Course Content

Duration: 6 sessions of two hours, 1 session with student presentations

Format: Lecture-based learning with interactive elements (teaching game)

- Basic background of standardization (K7.1)
 - Functions of standards
 - Forms of standardization and related coordination mechanisms
 - Standards vs dominant designs vs platforms
 - Tensions involved in standardization
- Standardization and institutions (S7.3)
 - Standardization institutional infrastructure
 - Standardization stakeholder identification and salience determination
- Standards development
 - Reasons for engaging in standardization (S7.6)
 - Standards vs patents (S7.6)
 - Incentives for cooperative behaviour during decision making (S7.6)
- Factors for standards selection (S7.3)
 - Market mechanisms: Network effects, path dependencies, and lockin
 - Complementary assets and strategies
- Interorganizational relationships for standardization (S7.3)
 - The effect of network composition on standards success
 - The effect of network structure on standards success

- Factors for standards adoption (S7.3)
 - Institutional pressures
 - Market mechanisms
 - stakeholder characteristics
 - standards compatibility
- Specific topics (dependent upon recent research) (K7.1; S7.7)
 - Standardisation and innovation

Practices and projects: Teaching case and game

Timeline and Milestones

Week/ session	Lecture	Practice or Project	Format methods (Presential, online)	assessment / exams activities
1	Basic background of standardization	Assignment	Presential	Lecture and discussion
2	Standardization and institutions	Assignment	Presential	Lecture and discussion
3	Standards development	Assignment	Presential	Lecture and discussion
4	Factors for standards selection	Teaching game	Presential	Lecture and discussion
5	Interorganizational relationships for standardization	Assignment	Presential	Lecture and discussion
6	Factors for standards adoption	Assignment	Presential	Lecture and discussion
7	Specific topics	Assignment	Presential	Lecture and discussion

Assessment conditions

Students are assessed by evaluating an assignment that they write in groups. In this assignment they write a scientific report in which they perform an historical case study of a standards development trajectory, a standards battle or a standards adoption case. The central question is which factors contribute to successful development, selection or adoption where success is defined as the situation at which a standard has been established.

- Method of assessment: project submission
- Grading criteria: minimum: 5.75
- Participation requirements: no requirements
- Submission deadline: week 10.

Teaching Methods

The course will utilize a blend of interactive teaching components including interactive lectures, real life examples, and presentations of students. Also, a teaching game will be developed for session 4 in which students can learn how to apply factors for standards dominance to a real-life situation.

Teaching Materials and Resources

This course utilizes recent academic papers on standardization, and the material therefore changes every year. Furthermore, a teaching game will be developed (see under teaching methods)

Evaluation

Anonymous survey

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

Selected publications

Confidentiality

n/a

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

We will use the standard evaluation form for M.Sc. courses that is applied at Delft University of Technology

3.2.2.2 Pilot at university M.Sc. level – Standardisation and Sustainability- TUB

The course "*Standardization and Sustainability*" provides Bachelor's and Master's students with a comprehensive overview of the standardization process, its typologies (formal and informal), and its relevance for sustainability. It addresses key topics such as the ethics, geopolitics, and policy dimensions of standardization, particularly within the EU context. The course fosters interactive learning through

discussions and contributions from guest speakers from both public and private sectors, who may deliver up to 50% of the lectures. Upon completion, students acquire a solid understanding of the economic and strategic role of standards at both corporate and macroeconomic levels, as well as their contribution to sustainability and the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department:	Technical University Berlin / Chair of Innovation Economics
Program:	Variety of Bachelor's and Master's Degrees

Pilot information

Course Code:	70029
Course Name:	Standardization and Sustainability
Semester:	Winter Semester
ECTS credits:	6
Contact Hours:	4 hours/week for 15 weeks
Teachers:	Knut Blind, Sokol Tominaj, Guest lecturers
Module manager/coordinator:	Sokol Tominaj
Course Language:	English
Course Format:	In-person and online
Course date:	October 2025 – February 2026

Pilot Description

General course description:	<p>“Standardization and Sustainability” teaches Bachelor’s and Master’s students about the standardization process as a whole, the different types of standards (formal, informal, etc.) and the implications of standardization for sustainability.</p> <p>The course covers a broad range of topics that are connected to standardization, such as the ethics of standardization, geopolitics of standardization, standardization and sustainability, standardization policy in the EU etc.</p> <p>We strive for active discussions in class and invite a plethora of guest speakers from public institutions and the private sector to enrich our lectures. Depending on the availability of guest speakers, they will hold up to 50 percent of lectures in the semester. In conclusion,</p>
------------------------------------	---

	students who complete this curriculum will gain a good understanding of standardization and its economic impact at the corporate level as well as at the macro level of the national, European and global innovation landscape. They will also understand the role of standards and their relationship to sustainability and the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):	Bachelor's and Master's students of heterogenous backgrounds
Level(s) from the ILOs framework:	Bachelor & Master

European Values and interests

We will incorporate European values—such as freedom, democracy, sustainability, the rule of law, and human dignity—into every lecture and classroom discussion. In each session, we will explore examples that highlight the connection between standardization and these values. Guest lecturers will also be asked to focus specifically on the link between standardization and European values. During class discussions, we will encourage students to share examples from their personal lives that illustrate how standardization relates to European values.

Intended Learning Outcomes

Topic 1	Standardization & Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outline the effects and significance of standardization and standards for sustainability and the sustainable and ecological transition of the European economies Outline the significance of the 17 SDGs and their interrelation with ISO
Topic 2	Company Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain the relevance and scope of company standards Know the effect and advantages of company standards Understand management motives to standardize Illustrate the importance of European values for company standardization
Topic 3	Formal Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know the formal standardization process, define standards and understand basic terms like “consensus” Understand harmonized standards and the “new approach” Learn about formal standards and their effect on sustainability Demonstrate knowledge using specific examples such as USB-C cables
Topic 4	Ethics & Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know the collection of European values Discuss the different ethical aspects on standardization Explain how ethics must be integrated into standards and the standardization process
Topic 5	Standardization & Open Source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outline what “Open Source” is and its interconnectedness with standardization

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain the value of open source software for the global economy and why it contributes to maintaining and defending European values
Topic 6	Private Standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the concept of private standards and know how define them Outline the effect that private standards have on companies, consumers and global supply chains Explain the relationship between private standards and sustainability in different industries, for instance the food industry
Topic 7	Consortia Standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss and identify the role and impact of consortia standards Outline the implicit and explicit significance of European values for consortia standards
Topic 8	Quality Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand and define quality infrastructure Outline the economic importance of quality infrastructure management
Topic 9	Standardization and Geopolitics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the relevance and implications of standardization for geopolitics Navigate the geopolitical worldmap and analyze the rise of new “Standardization superpowers” Recognize the significance of European values for standardization and geopolitics
Topic 10	Standardization in GVCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outline the barriers and benefits of standards in global value chains Explain how GVC standards and European values interact Know examples of standards in GVCs
Topic 11	Multi-Mode Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain the three different modes of standardization Demonstrate knowledge of the properties of different modes of standardization
Topic 12	Standardization Policy in the EU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outline the EU standardization policy, its implications for national standardization bodies and the European economy Understand how values are incorporated into the EU standardization policy
Topic 143	Research, Innovation and Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the latest research on standardization Illustrate the role of innovation in the standardization process and standards Define what an innovation is and define different types of innovations Explain European values in the context of innovation and standardization research
Topic 14	Standardization and Sustainability in the Steel Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the how standardization and sustainability affect the steel industry Identify challenges of the European steel industry and demonstrate how standards can help to overcome them
Topic 15	Blockchain and Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate knowledge on the blockchain technology Analyze the efforts of standardization bodies on developing blockchain standards
Topic 16	AI and Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain the latest efforts on AI standardization Differentiate between different AI technologies and their applications Illustrate the ethical implications of AI and the relevance of standardization in the AI industry Connect European values to AI standardization and explain why European values matter for AI applications

Description of Course Content

List of topics to be covered:

1. Company Standards
2. Formal Standardization
3. Ethics and Standardization
4. Standardization and Open Source
5. Private Standards
6. Consortia Standards
7. Quality Infrastructure
8. Standardization and Geopolitics
9. Standardization in GVCs
10. Multi-Mode Standardization
11. Standardization Policy in the EU
12. Research, Innovation and Standardization
13. Standardization and Sustainability in the Steel Industry
14. Blockchain and Standardization
15. AI and Standardization

Practices and projects: Essays about a standardization relevant topic, presentation of a standard

Timeline and Milestones

Session	Lecture	Practice or Project	Format methods (Presential, online)	assessment / exams activities
1	Introduction to Standardization and Sustainability (2 hrs.)		In-person	Lecture and participation or discussion
1	Formal Standardization		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
2	Company Standards		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
3	Introduction to ISO		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
4	Private Standards		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
4	Consortia Standards		Online	Lecture incl. Discussion
5	Quality Infrastructure		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
5	Standardization and Geopolitics		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
6	Standardization in GVCs		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion

6	Multi-Mode Standardization		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
7	Mid-Term Presentations	Case study	In-person	Presentations
7	Ethics in Standardization		Online	Lecture incl. Discussion
8	Standardization Policy in the EU		Online	Lecture incl. Discussion
9	Standardization and Open Source		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
9	Research, Innovation and Standardization		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
10	Standardization Policy		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
10	Standardization and Sustainability in the Steel Industry		Online	Lecture incl. Discussion
11	Standardization and Sustainability		Online	Lecture incl. Discussion
11	Standardization in the Bioeconomy		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
12	Blockchain and Standardization		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
13	AI and Standardization		In-person	Lecture incl. Discussion
14	Final Exam	Case study	In-person	Final Exam
15	Essay Deadline	Essay project		Essays

Assessment conditions

Students are assessed based on a written exam, a presentation, handing in multiple choice questions based on topics presented by guest speakers and a 2000-word essay on a topic related to standardization and sustainability. To pass the course, students must achieve 50 percent of possible points overall. The exam accounts for 50 percent of all points, the essay for 30 percent, the MC questions and the presentation of a relevant standard for 10 percent each.

Teaching Methods

Lectures and exercises in class, serious games, presentations, excursions if possible

Teaching Materials and Resources

Combination of handbooks and other publications.

Evaluation

Anonymous survey and subsequent in-class discussion

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

Combination of handbooks (more specifically the ETSI Handbook, ISO publications), selected other publications (Blind & Gauch, 2009, Böhm & Eisape, 2021, Blind, 2024, etc.) including EDU4Standards deliverables (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3).

Confidentiality

N/A

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

We encourage students to evaluate the course after the semester ended using a survey and try to improve the course based on the feedback received. Further, we track metrics like the number of participants and the average points received in our class. After analyzing the evaluations, we present the results in the last class and discuss them with the students to understand their point of view."

3.2.3 Extra-curricular Pilots

Two extra-curricular pilots are designed to address distinct target audiences. The first, proposed by UGZ, is aimed at teachers from various disciplines who wish to integrate standardisation into their courses. The second, proposed by POLIMI, offers an open course for engineering graduate students interested in learning about standardisation.

3.2.3.1 Summer school Pilot Design

This Summer School is designed for Higher Education teachers from all disciplines who want to integrate standardisation into their teaching, aligned with EU values and interests (stand-EUVI). The course presents standardisation not only as a technical process but as a strategic tool to foster European competitiveness, sustainability, social inclusion, and responsible innovation. Participants will explore the standardisation

ecosystem — its institutions, processes, and key actors — and learn how to apply it in their teaching in line with fundamental EU values and evolving European priorities.

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department:	University of Graz
Program:	Teacher's summer school (working title: Educator Academy on stand-EUVI), University of Graz

Pilot information

Course Code:	No code at the moment
Course Name:	Teaching Standardisation in line with EU values and interests
Semester:	Extracurricular; HEI teachers only
ECTS credits:	25 work hours preparation; 100 work hours in presence
Contact Hours:	2 weeks online, 5 days in person
Teachers:	Elisabeth Staudegger, Barbara Reiter, Hristina Veljanova (more expected)
Module manager/coordinator:	Elisabeth Staudegger
Course Language:	English/German
Course Format:	2 weeks online preparation, 5 days in person
Course date:	Fall 2025

Pilot Description

General course description:	<p>This Summer School on Standardisation for HEI Teachers provides tailored support for Higher Education Institution (HEI) teachers from all disciplines who wish to enrich their teaching with standardisation in line with EU values and interests (stand-EUVI).</p> <p>Framed within the EDU4Standards.eu Innovative Teaching Concept on Standardisation (ITCoS) and its corresponding Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs), the course presents standardisation not only as a process involving technical experts, but as a value-driven, strategic tool to promote European competitiveness, sustainability, social inclusion, and responsible innovation.</p>
------------------------------------	--

	<p>Participants explore the standardisation ecosystem—its institutions, processes, and actors—while learning how to integrate stand-EUVI meaning standardisation in line with fundamental and stable EU values (based on Article 2 TEU) and more flexible European interests (green/digital transitions, gender equality; others like resilience ...) into their own teaching.</p>
<p>Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):</p>	<p>HEI teachers and lecturers from all academic fields; typically teaching at EQF Level 6, 7 or 8 with little or no prior experience in teaching about standardisation or EU policy integration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Including those with background in: • Standardisation but not EU values • Ethics/law but not standardisation • Neither, but willing to integrate stand-EUVI into future teaching
<p>Level(s) from the ILOs framework:</p>	<p>Level 6, 7; 8</p>

European Values and interests

<p>The summer school is grounded in the understanding that standardisation is not a neutral technical process, but a strategic field where European values and interests are negotiated, reflected, and implemented. This approach—referred to as stand-EUVI—places emphasis on the alignment of standardisation with the fundamental values of the European Union, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human dignity • Freedom • Democracy • Equality and gender equality • The rule of law • Respect for human rights, including the rights of people belonging to minorities <p>In addition, the summer school explicitly integrates key EU policy priorities and interests, which include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The European Green Deal and environmental sustainability • The EU Digital Strategy and digital transformation • The EU Gender Equality Strategy and inclusive innovation • The ambition to strengthen European competitiveness, technological sovereignty, and strategic autonomy through value-driven standardisation

Participants critically reflect on these values and interests in real-world standardisation contexts, identify value conflicts, and develop teaching strategies to help students navigate and contribute to **standardisation processes that are inclusive, ethical, and strategically aligned with EU priorities.**

Intended Learning Outcomes

The intended learning outcomes of the summer school reflect the **EDU4Standards.eu ILO framework** and are tailored to the context of **Higher Education Institution (HEI) teachers**, typically at **EQF Levels 6 and 7**. While participants may begin with little or no experience in standardisation or values-based teaching, the course supports them in progressing to a level where they can confidently **integrate stand-EUVI** into their own teaching practice.

Upon successful completion of the summer school, participants will be able to:

Knowledge & Understanding

- Understand the concept of **stand-EUVI** and distinguish it from purely technical notions of standardisation
- Explain how **value-based standardisation supports EU competitiveness**, particularly in the fields of **sustainability (Green Deal)**, **digital transformation (Digital Decade)**, and **gender equality**
- Demonstrate awareness of the **standardisation ecosystem**, including its institutional structures at national, European, and international levels
- Identify how **EU policy frameworks and interests** relate to standardisation in their teaching disciplines

Skills

- Reflect critically on **values and value conflicts** in standardisation processes
- Identify and implement **opportunities to integrate stand-EUVI** into diverse subject areas
- Apply the **EDU4Standards.eu ILOs and ITCoS concept** to design or revise their own teaching modules
- Select and adapt **educational tools and materials** (e.g. Standards Battle, ITCoS resources) to engage students with standardisation
- Communicate the significance of **stand-EUVI** clearly to students and colleagues
- Evaluate and offer feedback on existing standards or teaching content from a **values-based perspective**
- Collaborate across disciplines and **co-develop educational content** linked to EU priorities
- Promote the inclusion of **green, digital, and gender aspects** in their teaching and curriculum development

Autonomy & Reflection

- Manage their own learning and contribute actively to a shared, **value-driven educational approach**
- Serve as **multipliers** of the stand-EUVI concept within their institutions and networks

Description of Course Content

This summer school is structured as a blended learning programme combining a 14-day online preparatory phase and a 5-day in-person workshop. It is designed specifically for experienced HEI teachers who wish to enrich their teaching by integrating stand-EUVI. As multipliers within their institutions, teachers have the unique potential to embed value-driven standardisation across disciplines and generations through education. Their contribution is central to the success of the summer school: by sharing their diverse expertise, offering peer feedback, and co-creating teaching resources, they help create a collaborative learning culture. The course concept is intentionally designed to value and harness this potential—treating participants not only as learners but also as co-creators of the learning experience.

Preparatory Phase (Online | 2 weeks)

- **Input:** Introductory materials on standardisation, EU values and interests, and the EDU4Standards.eu framework
- **Activities:**
 - Task 1: Short statement of motivation and teaching background
 - Task 2: Completion of a Teaching Description (TD) template outlining existing teaching practices and potential entry points for stand-EUVI
 - Forum engagement and questions to trainers
- **Outcomes:**
 - Participants reflect on their own teaching context
 - Shared understanding of stand-EUVI basics
 - Prepared TD drafts ready for in-depth exploration

Module 0 – VALUES (Day 1)

- **Input:** Workshop on EU fundamental values and their relevance in standardisation (human dignity, democracy, gender equality, inclusion, etc.)
- **Activities:**
 - Value-mapping and identification of value conflicts
 - “My teaching” micro-presentations
 - Role-play and discussion of value tensions in standardisation
- **Outcomes:**
 - Participants experience personal and institutional value systems
 - Understanding of the role of values and value conflicts in standardisation

Module I – BASICS (Day 2)

- **Input:** Overview of the standardisation ecosystem, including SBs (e.g. ASI, DIN), types of standards, and processes
- **Activities:**
 - Identifying standards in everyday and subject-specific contexts
 - Standardisation simulation game (e.g. DIN simulation)
 - Micro-teaching: First mini-lecture on stand-EUVI
- **Outcomes:**
 - Participants understand key institutional actors and procedures
 - First hands-on experience in applying stand-EUVI to their field

Module II – REQUIREMENTS (Day 3)

- **Input:** Introduction to the EDU4Standards.eu ILO framework and guidance on integrating stand-EUVI into teaching
- **Activities:**
 - Group reflection on values and interests in teaching fields
 - Group work: strategies for integrating green, digital, and gender-sensitive elements
 - TD revision: enriching the original Teaching Description with stand-EUVI and ILO alignment
- **Outcomes:**
 - Participants are able to interpret and apply stand-EUVI ILOs
 - TDs are updated to reflect values- and interest-oriented standardisation education

Module III – MATCHING (Day 4)

- **Input:** Tour and demonstration of the EDU4Standards.eu ITCoS platform (resources, methods, games, templates)
- **Activities:**
 - Search and selection of materials matching individual disciplines and TDs
 - Final refinement of TDs to align methods, materials, and outcomes
 - Feedback rounds on concepts and platform tools
- **Outcomes:**
 - Participants identify suitable didactic tools for teaching stand-EUVI
 - Participants finalise first draft of their value-based teaching concept

Module IV – DEVELOPING (Day 5)

- **Input:** Session on curriculum design and strategic embedding of stand-EUVI in HEI programmes
- **Activities:**
 - Reflection and discussion of curriculum integration strategies
 - Group work: Development of EDU4Standards Call4Pilots proposals
 - Final presentations and peer feedback
- **Outcomes:**
 - Participants develop actionable plans to implement stand-EUVI in curricula

- o Preparedness to apply for the Call4Pilots or initiate teaching innovations locally

This structured progression should ensure that each HEI teacher not only gains conceptual and policy-based insights but also leaves with a practical, co-developed and peer-reviewed teaching plan ready for implementation in their own institutional context.

Yet today it is still work in progress and needs to be discussed and refined within the next weeks.

Timeline and Milestones

Week/ session	Lecture	Practice Project	Format methods (Presential, online)	assessment / exams activities
Prep Phase (Week -2 to 0)	Intro materials on standardisation, stand-EUVI, EDU4Standards	Complete Teaching Description (TD), motivation statement, forum interaction	Online (asynchronous)	Submission of TD (initial), forum contributions
Day 1 – Module 0: VALUES	Workshop on EU values and their relevance to standardisation	Value-mapping, personal reflections, micro-presentations, role play	Presential: interactive workshop, peer presentations	Participation, micro-presentation
Day 2 – Module I: BASICS	Introduction to standardisation systems, types, processes, SBs	Identify standards in teaching field, DIN simulation, micro-teaching	Presential: lecture, game-based learning, peer teaching	Micro-teaching input, reflection
Day 3 – Module II: REQUIREMENTS	Intro to EDU4Standards ILO framework and integration strategies	Group reflection, TD enrichment, ILO alignment	Presential: group work, applied reflection	Updated TD draft with ILOs
Day 4 – Module III: MATCHING	Tour of ITCoS platform, teaching tools, methods	Search & match methods/resources, refine TD, feedback rounds	Presential: hands-on ITCoS usage, collaborative refinement	Final draft TD, peer feedback
Day 5 – Module IV: DEVELOPING	Session on curriculum design, EDU4Standards Call4Pilots	Pilot proposal development, curriculum planning, peer feedback	Presential: project-based, strategic planning, presentations	Presentation of teaching plan and/or pilot proposal

Teaching Methods

Flipped Classroom (input is studied during the preparatory phase; in-person time focuses on applying knowledge)

Problem-Based Learning (participants start with their own teaching concept [TD] and enrich the form during the workshop days step by step)

Peer Learning/Teaching (participants explain concepts to one another)

Micro-Inputs + Application (short theoretical inputs, followed by direct application in group/pair work)

Games (DIN, ISO, else)

Reflective Practice (individual or group reflection to link new knowledge to their own teaching; plenary discussions)

Teaching Materials and Resources

ETSI textbook on standardization; trainer's material; EDU4Standards' teacher support platform

PPT-slides that have been developed for other courses/lectures at Uni Graz

The TECHETHOS game/Age of Impact (<https://publications.ait.ac.at/en/activities/the-techethos-game-ages-of-impact>)

DIN game

Others [tbc]

Evaluation

At the end of the course, the summer school will be evaluated together with the participants to assess whether it has met their expectations and how it might be improved. The evaluation will focus on both the **content and structure** of the course, as well as the **applicability of the EDU4Standards.eu concept** to participants' own teaching.

Participants will be asked to reflect on:

- The **relevance of the content** to their subject areas and roles as HEI teachers
- The **usefulness of the materials, methods, and platform tools**
- The **supportiveness of the format** (online preparation + in-person modules)
- Their ability to apply what they learned to develop or revise their teaching (via their Teaching Description)

Evaluation tools will include:

- **Daily informal feedback rounds**
- A **short written questionnaire** at the end of the summer school
- ...

The results will inform the **further development of the summer school format** and the refinement of the **EDU4Standards.eu ITCoS and ILOs**. Participants' feedback is therefore a valuable part of shaping the future of this training offer.

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

The purpose of EDU4Standards.eu is to **scale up education on standardisation in Europe**, and this pilot is intended to actively contribute to that mission. Therefore, any materials developed by EDU4Standards.eu or its partners and used within the pilot may be **used or made available for reuse by third parties**, unless restricted by copyright.

The following categories of teaching materials are intended for **reuse and possible wider dissemination**:

- EDU4Standards.eu **Teaching Description (TD) template**, ILO framework, and were possible the trainers's support platform content
- Trainer-developed handouts, worksheets, and slides (unless otherwise noted)
- Adapted or co-created content (e.g. TDs or lesson plans) developed by participants and voluntarily shared

Where possible, materials will be made available under an **open license**, such as **Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA)**. This will allow others to reproduce, adapt, and redistribute the content for non-commercial educational use, with proper attribution.

Participants will be informed about licensing options and invited to **voluntarily share** their outputs (e.g. revised TDs or pilot proposals) for publication or integration into the EDU4Standards repository. Sharing is **not mandatory** and subject to each participant's approval.

In cases where third-party material (e.g. images, proprietary slides, institutional documents) is used, those items will be **clearly marked** and remain subject to their respective copyright conditions.

Confidentiality

Data protection, respect for trade secrets, and compliance with any applicable **non-disclosure agreements (NDAs)** are fully guaranteed throughout the summer school.

At this time, **no specific further confidentiality issues** are foreseen.

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

This pilot summer school is implemented as a **lifelong learning course for experienced HEI teachers**. Its evaluation will rely on a combination of **quantitative indicators** and **qualitative insights** to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the course's reach, effectiveness, and future potential.

Quantitative Metrics (indicative targets for pilot phase)

- **Enrollment:** Approx. 8–12 participants from different disciplines and institutions
- **Completion Rate:** Target $\geq 90\%$, based on full attendance and submission of the revised Teaching Description (TD)
- **Participant Satisfaction:** Measured via a final evaluation form using a 5-point Likert scale
 - Target score ≥ 4.0 for overall satisfaction
 - Specific questions on content, methods, relevance, and perceived transferability
- **TD Submissions:** Number and quality of revised Teaching Descriptions developed during the course
- **Reusability of Materials:** Number of participants who voluntarily agree to share or adapt materials for future use (OER)

Qualitative Metrics

- **Participant Feedback:** Collected through:
 - Daily informal feedback rounds
 - Final group reflection session
 - Written post-course evaluation
- **Observed Engagement:** Reflections from trainers on participant interaction, collaboration, and peer learning
- **Challenges Noted:**
 - Balancing a diverse range of disciplines
 - Introducing complex policy/value frameworks in a short time
 - Navigating different levels of prior knowledge in standardisation and EU policy
- **Examples of Best Practice:**
 - Creative adaptations of stand-EUVI into varied teaching fields (e.g. law, technology, education)
 - Successful integration of EDU4Standards ILOs into existing HEI modules
 - Peer co-creation of lesson ideas and pilot concepts
- **Platform Use:** Feedback on the usability, relevance, and value of the EDU4Standards.eu platform for long-term teaching use

Contextual Notes

- Given the nature of the participants (experienced university teachers), the course places a strong emphasis on **peer exchange and qualitative transformation** rather

than standardised testing or grading. Assessment is based on active participation, application of course concepts in the TD, and individual reflection on teaching innovation.

- These indicators will serve both to **evaluate the pilot's effectiveness** and to **inform improvements** for future iterations, in line with the EDU4Standards.eu goal of scaling up high-quality education on standardisation across Europe.
-

The primary method for assessing whether **participants** achieve the intended learning outcomes (ILOs) of the summer school is the **analysis of individual Teaching Descriptions (TDs)** developed during the course. These TDs reflect each participant's subject area, teaching context, and pedagogical approach, and serve as a **concrete artefact of learning and integration**.

The following **High-Level Indicators (HLIs)** will be assessed qualitatively and semi-quantitatively through the **comparison of initial and final versions** of each TD:

TD-Based Assessment Criteria

1. **HLI 1 – Conceptual Integration**

At least 90% of final TDs include an accurate and context-relevant reference to **stand-EUVI**, showing understanding of its definition and educational relevance (linked to ILOs K6.1, K6.2).

2. **HLI 2 – Value & Interest Dimensions**

At least 80% of TDs reflect awareness of **EU interests and value areas**, such as sustainability, digital transformation, or gender equality, embedded in the teaching objectives or content (linked to K6.4, S6.1).

3. **HLI 3 – ILO Alignment**

All final TDs demonstrate alignment with at least **one EDU4Standards.eu ILO**, made explicit in the description of intended student learning (linked to S6.2, S6.3).

4. **HLI 4 – Methodological Matching**

At least 80% of TDs include appropriate **teaching methods or materials** drawn from the ITCoS platform or summer school resources, suited to the target audience and subject (linked to S6.4).

5. **HLI 5 – Reflective Transformation**

Each TD shows **qualitative progression** from the initial version, such as restructured learning objectives, added values dimension, inclusion of stakeholder or policy perspectives, or revised learning outcomes.

6. **HLI 6 – Transfer Potential**

At least 70% of TDs describe a **clear plan or intention** to implement the revised teaching activity in the next academic year and/or share it with colleagues (linked to S6.9, S6.8).

These indicators enable a **rich, practice-oriented evaluation** of the course outcomes while acknowledging the **autonomy and expertise of the participants**. They also provide a solid foundation for assessing the pilot's contribution to the EDU4Standards.eu mission.

Please **CONSIDER, THIS IS WORK in PROGRESS!!! Not final now. ;)**

3.2.3.2 Extra-curricular pilot Design

This course introduces engineering students to standardisation, highlighting its role in shaping industries, driving innovation, and supporting business strategy. Students will learn what standards are, how they are developed, and their impact on engineering, market access, interoperability, and regulatory compliance. The course also explores the link between standardisation and innovation, technology diffusion, and trade, as well as the relationship between standards and intellectual property, including patents and standard-essential patents (SEPs). It is open to engineering graduate students with an interest in learning (no prerequisites required).

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department:	Politecnico di Milano, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering
Program:	Passion in Action, Extra-Curricular Course at Politecnico di Milano

Pilot information

Course Code:	No code at the moment
Course Name:	Standardization for Engineers
Semester:	Master students in different semesters. The program is open to all engineering students at the Politecnico di Milano
ECTS credits:	1 ECTS
Contact Hours:	10 hours of teaching
Teachers:	Nizar Abdelkafi
Module manager/coordinator:	Nizar Abdelkafi
Course Language:	English
Course Format:	Preferably in-presence, but depending on the number of students that will participate and the availability of rooms at the Politecnico di Milano, the course may be hybrid or may be completely online
Course date:	Fall 2025 (September 25 – December 25)

Pilot Description

General course description:	This course provides an introduction to standardization for engineering students and highlights its role in shaping industries, fostering innovation, and supporting
------------------------------------	--

	<p>business strategy. It explores what standards are, why they exist, how they are developed, and their impact on engineering practice and the broader economy.</p> <p>Through this course, students will gain a foundational understanding of the standardization ecosystem, including key organizations, processes, and stakeholders involved in setting standards. They will also learn about the strategic importance of standards for companies, particularly in relation to market access, interoperability, regulatory compliance, and technological leadership.</p> <p>Furthermore, the course will cover the intersection between standardization and innovation, while emphasizing its role in enabling technology diffusion and reducing barriers to trade. The relationship between standards and intellectual property (IP)—especially with respect to patents and standard-essential patents (SEPs)—will be discussed to illustrate the dynamics between open and proprietary technologies in engineering.</p>
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):	Engineering graduate students. There are no course requirements, only interest to learn
Level(s) from the ILOs framework:	Level 7

European Values and interests

While this course focuses on standardization for engineers, it also emphasizes how the standardization process can be a powerful tool for promoting key European Union values, such as human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human rights, including those of minorities. Thus, standardization plays a crucial role in ensuring inclusivity, accessibility, sustainability, and fairness, making it a key enabler of ethical and responsible engineering practices.

Case Study: Revising a National Telecare Standard for ICT Accessibility

One example that illustrates how standards contribute to human dignity and inclusivity is the revision of a national standard on telecare from the perspective of ICT accessibility in Spain. Telecare services are essential for the elderly and persons with disabilities, as they provide remote health monitoring, emergency assistance, and social support. Ensuring that these services comply with accessibility standards for citizens (without and with disabilities) helps safeguard human dignity and equal access to essential healthcare and communication technologies.

By revising the standard with accessibility in mind, engineers and standardisation bodies directly contribute to EU values by fostering equality and non-discrimination. This example demonstrates that technical decisions in engineering and standardisation are not purely functional—they have social and ethical implications that align with European principles of fairness and inclusivity.

The TBT Principles and Their Alignment with EU Values

The course will also introduce students to the Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) principles of the World Trade Organisation, which govern the development of international standards. These principles—transparency, openness, impartiality, consensus, effectiveness, relevance, and coherence—are deeply aligned with EU fundamental values. They ensure that standardization is not used as an unfair trade barrier but rather as a means to promote cooperation, innovation, and fair competition in global markets. By understanding the TBT principles, students will see how standardisation reflects democratic values, as it is based on open participation, inclusivity, and consensus among stakeholders.

The Role of Sustainability in Standardization: The ISO Example

Another relevant case is ISO's ongoing efforts to incorporate sustainability into all its standards. The London Declaration of ISO refers to a commitment made by ISO in September 2021 to actively combat climate change through the development of international standards. Sustainability is a key EU value that relates to environmental protection, social responsibility, and economic development. By updating its standards to reflect sustainability concerns, ISO demonstrates how standardization can support global efforts to combat climate change and promote responsible resource use. This reinforces the idea that standardization is not just about technical specifications—it is also a tool for social and environmental responsibility.

Airbag Standards and the Challenge of Equality in Standardization

An important example of the unintended consequences of standardization is the case of airbag standards, which were historically designed for individuals of a certain height—typically based on the average male physique. This design choice excluded shorter individuals, particularly women and some minority groups, from the same level of safety protection.

This example highlights the need for a critical approach to standardization because engineers must be aware that standards can unintentionally reinforce inequalities if diverse perspectives are not considered during their development.

Distinguishing Between the Values Reflected in Standards and the Standardization Process Itself

A key takeaway from the course is the distinction between: (1) The ethical and societal impact of specific standards—whether they respect EU values such as inclusivity, human dignity, and sustainability, and (2) the fairness of the standardisation process—ensuring that it remains open, transparent, and aligned with the WTO principles, with the EU values as well as with EU regulation 1025/2012 that aims to ensure that the standardisation system is more inclusive, more efficient, and better in line with EU policies and legislation.

This distinction illustrates to students that while Europe can and should protect its industry and economic interests through standardisation, it must always do so in a way that aligns with its fundamental values. This means that standards should not create unfair barriers to trade, nor should they favor certain groups, e.g. large companies, while excluding others, e.g. consumer organisations. Instead, they should be developed with the broadest possible participation and consensus, while ensuring fairness, inclusivity, and innovation.

Consequently, by the end of this course, students will definitely learn that standardisation is a technical process that is strategic and can have a huge impact on industry and the economy. However, engineers involved in standardisation have a responsibility to respect EU values by ensuring that standards are developed and applied in a way that promotes fairness, inclusivity, and sustainability while enabling green and digital transition and still protecting European industrial and technological leadership.

Intended Learning Outcomes

This course is designed for master's level engineering students (EQF Level 7) who have little to no prior exposure to standardisation. While they are at an advanced stage in their engineering studies, their understanding of standardisation is at a beginner level (below EQF Level 4) at the start of the course. By completing this course, students will achieve Level 4 competencies in standardisation, with the potential to progress towards Level 5 through additional self-study.

By the end of the course, students will be able to:

1. Explain the fundamental concepts of standardization—including what standards are, why they exist, and their impact on engineering practice.
2. Identify key standardization bodies (e.g., ISO, IEC, CEN, CENELEC, ETSI, IEEE) and describe their roles in developing and maintaining standards.
3. Describe the standardisation process, including the stages of standard development, stakeholder involvement, and principles such as openness, transparency, and consensus.
4. Analyze the strategic importance of standards for companies, including market access, competitiveness, and regulatory compliance.
5. Understand the relationship between standardisation, Research and Development and innovation, including the role of patents and Standard-Essential Patents (SEPs).
6. Evaluate the role of standards in promoting European values, including human dignity, equality and inclusivity.
7. Recognize challenges in standardisation, such as unintended biases in standards (e.g., airbag height requirements) and the need for continuous standard revisions, but also opportunities in standardisation such as market access and innovation diffusion.

Description of Course Content

Duration (Planned) : 10 hours (3 sessions of 4 academic hours each)

Format: Lecture-based learning with interactive elements (quizzes, case study, game)

List of topics to be covered:

1. Introduction to standardization
2. The standardization ecosystem
3. The standardization process
4. Strategic importance of standardization
5. Standardization and innovation
6. Standardization and Intellectual Property
7. Standardization & EU values
8. Challenges & opportunities

Practices and projects. Quizzes, case study, game

Timeline and Milestones

Week/ session	Lecture	Practice Project	or Format methods (Presential, online)	/ assessment / exams activities
1	<i>Introduction to standardization and standards ecosystem</i>	<i>Quizzes</i>	<i>Presential (preferable)</i>	<i>Lecture and discussion</i>
2	<i>The standardization process, strategic importance and standardization & innovation</i>	<i>Case study</i>	<i>Presential (preferable)</i>	<i>Lecture and discussion</i>
3	<i>Standardization & Intellectual property, Standardization & EU values, challenges and opportunities</i>	<i>Game</i>	<i>Presential (preferable)</i>	<i>Lecture and discussion</i>
4	<i>Self-study</i>			

Assessment conditions

To evaluate students' understanding of standardization in engineering, the course will conclude with a 30-minute multiple-choice exam consisting of 30 questions. The exam will

cover key concepts, case studies, and practical applications of standardization as discussed throughout the course.

Teaching Methods

The course will be designed to actively engage students using interactive teaching methods that encourage critical thinking and participation. The methods will ensure that students, who are experts in their engineering field but new to standardization, can quickly grasp key concepts and develop a good/an applied understanding of the subject. In detail:

- Teaching by questions: Thought-provoking question before introducing key concepts
- Teaching by examples: Using real-world examples to illustrate the concepts and their interrelationships
- Quizzes, Case study approach and game

Teaching Materials and Resources

ETSI textbook on standardization, eventually the IEEE standardization game or another game as well as adapted PPT-slides that have been developed in parallel with the ETSI-book.

Evaluation

The course will be evaluated according to the evaluation methods/tools as designed in the EDU4Standards project.

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

The teaching materials provided by ETSI that will be used in this course are accessible to everyone interested in the topic without restrictions. The ETSI documents are extensive and contain a large number of slides. For the purpose of the current course, the slides will be adapted, e.g. to fulfill the teaching by questions objective, and will be reduced to a smaller number of slides.

Confidentiality

No confidentiality issues in this case.

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

- Level of participation/attendance in the course, also during the single sessions (Target number of students: 15-20 students)
- Level of satisfaction with the course captured by means of a survey distributed to students at the end of the course.
- Average grade of students in the final exam

3.2.4 In-company training Pilot

Initially, the project proposal included only one course (an in-company training programme proposed by TU/e). However, in order to better address the specific needs of SMEs, and based on the input provided by the participating SME organisations, a complementary initiative has been introduced: the *Standards for SMEs* pilot (proposed by Small Business Standards (SBS)). As a result, this section presents the design of two courses aimed at covering both in-company training and SME-focused learning. Both are intended to support in situ professional development sessions.

3.2.4.1 In-company lifelong learning pilot design

This pilot training programme offers three courses (A1, A2, B1) tailored to different company profiles:

- A1 introduces standardisation from a high-tech company perspective, providing essential knowledge for technical development.
- A2 focuses on building practical skills for effective participation in standardisation bodies.
- B1 targets senior managers, addressing strategic aspects of standardisation relevant to business and management

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department :	Eindhoven University of Technology & Tilburg University
Program:	In-company lifelong learning course

Pilot information

Course Code:	A1 / A2 / B1
Course Name:	Standardisation in high tech for practitioners A1: “Fundamentals of standardisation” A2: “Effectively participating in standardisation bodies” B1: “Strategic standardization for business and management”
Semester:	N/A (in-company course, at postgraduate level)

ECTS credits:	Three courses planned: A1 (younger engineers): 8 hours (intensive course) A2 (mid-career engineers): 8 hours (intensive course) B1 (senior, higher level managers): 2 hours (intensive course)
Contact Hours:	A1: 8 hours A2: 8 hours B1: 2 hours
Teachers:	Rudi Bekkers, Paul Wiegmann, Panos Delimatsis, Stephanie Bijlmakers, Irene Kamara
Module manager/coordinator:	Rudi Bekkers
Course Language:	English
Course Format:	Mixed format with some physical meeting plus an online component (In-person + Online)
Course date:	Spring/Summer 2025

Pilot Description

General course description:	<p>The pilot is a training programme, which consists of three courses (A1, A2, B1) addressing different audiences in the in-company context:</p> <p>The A1 “Standards and Standardization and technical development” course provides a concise yet in-depth understanding of standardisation as relevant from a high-tech company perspective.</p> <p>The follow-up A2 “Effectively participating in standardisation bodies” course addresses skills to operate in standards bodies.</p> <p>The B1 “Strategic standardization for business and management” high-level course, aimed at senior managers, offers a tailored format of standardisation topics for management level.</p>
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):	<p>A1: Younger engineers, in the beginning of their career. Professional background, mostly postgraduate university educated. No or minimal experience with standardisation.</p> <p>A2: Mid-career engineers, typically 6-10 years of experience. Participants have had practical experience of participating in standardisation but in most cases have not received formal training on the subject.</p>

	B1: Senior, higher level managers, e.g., board or marketing positions.
Level(s) from the ILOs framework:	<p>Note: the in-company audience is typically at postgraduate level, but in terms of standardisation-specific ILOs, we need to cover various preceding levels too:</p> <p>Course A1: Levels 4/5 Course A2: Levels 5/6 Course B1: Levels 6/7</p> <p>(see also at ILOs, below)</p>

European Values and interests

The pilot will discuss the inclusion in standards of “core EU democratic values and interests, as well as green and social principles.” (p. 4 of EC (2022). Communication From The Commission [...]: An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting Global Standards in Support of a Resilient, Green and Digital EU Single Market. COM(2022) 31 Final. European Commission. EC.).

It will do so by:

1. Discussing how standards, as technical solutions, are seldom neutral, using following four examples: (1) the examples of the development of the meter, (2) The requirements for airbags, (3) AI-based recommender systems for university enrolment decisions resulting in structural bias towards certain groups of individuals and (4) The ‘new internet’ as proposed by Chinese actors in the 2020s
2. A hot group exercise, in which participants will working in small groups will identify specific values at stake in their own field of technology. After that, the outcomes of the groups will be discussed, whereas the trainer has also prepared a number of examples (should the groups fail to come up with enough themselves)
3. A critical discussion of also the questions raised by including values in standards.

Intended Learning Outcomes

The below refers to the ILOs as defined in document D2.1, Table 5.

Note: given the short duration of these intensive courses, the learning goal must be in line with what is actually feasible and corresponds to the participants’ previous knowledge base. Hence the following proposal for ILOs.

Course A1: Levels 4/5

K4.1: to have a factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts regarding standardisation

K4.3: to have factual and theoretical knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation

S4.1: demonstrate knowledge in digital and ICT standards

S4.2: identify strategies to ensure more respectful cooperation in standardization processes
 S4.4: determine which form of standardisation (formal vs. informal) is appropriate
 S5.2: assess the need for getting involved in standardisation

Course A2: Levels 5/6

S5.1: analyse the interactions between standards and the regulatory landscape for ICT
 S5.6: outline the professional activities of a standardisation expert during committee meetings, between organisation meetings, inside his/her own organisation, further activities as a national delegate
 S5.7: be passively involved in standardisation processes (observer)
 S5.8: implement standards in product or process development
 S6.1: be actively involved in standardisation processes (participant)

Course B1: Levels 6/7

S6.2: illustrate the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework
 S7.2: strategically influence the agenda in standardisation processes

Description of Course Content

Content covered in A1:

Time slot	Activity	Topics (not exhaustive)
9:00 – 9:15	Welcome / introduction	Organisation of the day, introduction of trainers and participants
9:15 – 9:45	1. Standards and their role in society and industry	Introduction to standards, the benefits of standards for stakeholders, how standards can be a strategic tool for industry objectives; general standardisation strategies and outcomes (e.g., standards battles)
10:00 – 10:30	2. Standard setting organisations	Formal standard setting organisations (SSOs) and consortia, their scope, processes, rules, and culture. Searching, reading and applying standards
10:45 – 11:15	3. Policy and legal aspects of standards and standardisation	Balancing interests, anti-competitive behaviour; Status of and differences between formal and informal SSOs; data protection issues; Harmonised Standards, European values. The EU regulatory framework (illustrated via examples like the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) and AI Act) and the EC Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation (AUWP)
11:30 – 12:00	4. Standards and patents	Standard-essential patents from an industry, SSO, and policy perspective
12:00 – 13:30	<i>Lunch</i>	
13:30 – 14:30	5. Serious game 'Lost at Sea'	Practice yourself how using consensus works out in practice in this role-playing game developed by ISO
14:45 – 15:15	6. Standardisation from the NXP perspective	The organisation of standardisation involvement within NXP; Standardisation activities relevant to NXP (<i>module by NXP staff</i>)
15:30 – 16:00	7. Start participating yourself in standard-setting	Different types of standardisation meetings, roles (chairperson, conveyer, etc.), contributing proposals, how standardisation works in practice, being part of decision-making (do's and don'ts)

16:00 – 16:20	Closing, wrap-up, experiences, evaluation	A short survey among the participants will be done during the meeting (online, using a QR code)
---------------	---	---

Content covered in A2:

Time slot	Activity	Topics (not exhaustive)
9:00 – 9:30	Welcome / introduction	Organisation of the day, introduction of trainers. Participants share their own roles and experiences in standardisation
9:30 – 10:00	1. Standard organisations setting	Formal standard setting organisations (SSOs) and consortia, their scope, processes, rules, and culture. Searching, reading and applying standards
10:15 – 10:45	2. Policy and legal aspects of standards and standardisation	Balancing interests, anti-competitive behaviour. Differences between formal and informal SSOs; data protection issues; Harmonised Standards, European values. The EU regulatory framework (illustrated via examples like the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) and AI Act) and the EC Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation (AUWP). Standard essential patents from an industry, SSO and policy perspective.
11:00 – 11:30	3. Standards and trade in a global perspective	Legal value of harmonised standards in the EU legal order & WTO; standardisation policies in other parts of the world
11:45 – 12:15	4. Competences and skills for participating in standardisation	What set of competences are required, how you can build these competences; bringing proposals into standardisation bodies; decision making in standardisation consensus and voting
	Lunch	
13:15 – 15:15	5. Serious game	Develop your standardisation competences with this role-playing game organized by a specialized supplier in standardisation gamification
15:30 – 16:00	6. Standardisation from the NXP perspective	The organisation of standardisation involvement within NXP; Standardisation activities relevant to NXP (<i>module by NXP staff</i>)
16:00 – 16:20	Closing, wrap-up, experiences, evaluation.	A short survey among the participants will be done during the meeting (online, using a QR code)

Content of B1 still t.b.d.

Timeline and Milestones

The A1 and A2 levels will be held as intensive one-day in-person courses. They have been provisionally scheduled to take place on 26 and 28 May 2025. See the tables above for a provisional planning of the day.

The B1 level will be held as an intensive 2-hour training session. We expect that it will take place in September 2025 (exact date still tbd).

The specific modules and planning of each course still need to be determined. We will report back once the planning has been finalised.

Assessment conditions

Because of the context of this course (in-company) and the position expressed by the company itself, individual participants will not be assessed in terms of reaching learning objectives. Participants will receive a certificate of participation.

The course itself, however, will be evaluated with the participants.

Teaching Methods

Classroom teaching (with on-line component), and a serious game (highlighted in the description of course content above). Considerable amount of interactivity: the content of Course B1, for instance, is largely based on previous input obtained from participants about what dimensions they want to learn about.

Teaching Materials and Resources

Combination of handbooks (such as the ETSI Handbook), selected other publications (selection of sources provided in D2.2), and legal texts, where necessary. Exact materials used still tbd.

Evaluation

At the end of the course, we will evaluate it with participants (whether it met their expectations, what could be improved). We will use the evaluation methods/tools as designed in the EDU4Standards project.

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

Any material developed by EDU4Standards or its partners and used for this in-company pilot may be used elsewhere or made available to third parties for use elsewhere (unless other parties have rights on them, like the ETSI book).

Any such material made available to others shall however not have any business confidential information specific to the company where the pilot took place, such as relating to its own business, its standardization strategy, its IPR strategy, etc. Therefore, the company will have the possibility to review the material intended for reuse and object against the use of materials that fall within these categories.

Confidentiality

We encourage participants in the pilot to share experiences from their own practice, engage in discussion, share thoughts, etc., to create a lively and good learning experience. The involved teachers from EDU4Standards will act as it can be normally expected according to general standards of academic and professional integrity. As teachers, we will respect the Chatham house rules (in short: not to link any statement or view to an individual or affiliated company).

We expect, however, that the company where the pilot takes place will not share any information that it considers to be trade secret or confidential. If the company or its employees accidentally or not did share any such information, we should as soon as possible be informed about this, including a clear explanation what information exactly that was shared was confidential.

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

Quantitative metrics:

- enrolment numbers
- participant satisfaction scores

Qualitative insights:

- feedback from participants and instructors
- observed challenges

3.2.4.2 Standards for SME pilot

The pilot will offer a training programme structured into four modules—Basic I, Basic II, Intermediate I, and Intermediate II—the latter being optional. **Basic I** is designed to help SMEs engage with a topic often perceived as complex or remote by introducing the fundamental concepts of standards and standardisation, illustrated through practical examples that highlight their relevance and potential benefits. **Basic II** explores the relationship between standards, European legislation, market access, and conformity assessment, with particular emphasis on the role of harmonised standards in supporting compliance and fostering business growth. **Intermediate I** takes a sector-specific or cross-sectoral approach, depending on the target audience, to examine the application of standards in fields such as sustainability, digitalisation, or cybersecurity. The optional module, **Intermediate II**, focuses on the strategic use of standards to improve quality, compliance, and innovation, and outlines how SMEs can actively participate in standardisation processes to ensure their interests are represented.

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department/Participating Organisations:	Eindhoven University of Technology & Tilburg University (TBC), SBS, SME organisation (TBD)
Program:	Lifelong training course (in cooperation with SME association)

Pilot information

Important note: This pilot was not foreseen in the original project proposal and is now being developed as a complementary initiative to the in-company pilot, specifically tailored to the SME context. Still in the early design phase, the pilot will integrate the needs identified by the participating SME organisation, as well as participants feedback and lessons learned from the in-company experience. Consequently, the details presented in this document are subject to change.

Course Code:	N/A
Course Name:	Standards for SMEs: Practical insights and application It will be divided in different modules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic I: Standards and standardisation: key concepts explained • Basic II: Standards, legislation and market access • Intermediate I: Applying standards in [sector]* • Intermediate II: Strategic use of standards and how to get involved in standardisation (optional) <p><i>* This module would be a sector specific module that could be adapted according to the group of SMEs targeted. It could also be adapted to cover a horizontal topic (digitalisation, sustainability) relevant to different sectors.</i></p>
Semester:	N/A
ECTS credits:	One day/ One day and a half depending on modules selected
Contact Hours:	Basic I – 2,5 hours Basic II – 2,5 hours Intermediate I – 2,5 hours Intermediate II – 2,5 hours
Teachers:	TBD
Module manager/coordinator:	TBD
Course Language:	TBD (depending on country/region of implementation)
Course Format:	Hybrid, possibly in person if conditions allow.
Course date:	Spring-Summer 2026

Pilot Description

General course description:	<p>The pilot will consist of a training programme, composed of four modules, the last one being optional:</p> <p>Basic I – Standards and standardisation: key concepts explained: Introduces SMEs to the fundamentals of standards and standardisation, their potential benefits are explained through practical examples and common business challenges. The module focuses on clear, practical explanations, helping SMEs engage with a topic that is often perceived as complex or distant.</p> <p>Basic II – Standards, legislation and market access: Explores the links between standards, European legislation, market access and conformity assessment. It highlights the role of harmonised standards for compliance and the opportunities they create for business growth.</p> <p>Intermediate I – Applying standards in [sector/area]: Depending on the audience, this module will be tailored to reflect sector-specific needs or cover horizontal topics relevant to different sectors e.g. sustainability, digitalisation, cybersecurity, etc.</p> <p>Intermediate II – Strategic use of standards and how to get involved in standardisation (optional): Explains in more detail how SMEs can effectively make use of standards to improve quality, compliance, and innovation capacity. It also presents ways SMEs can actively participate in standards development processes, ensuring their interests are represented.</p>
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):	SMEs No prior knowledge of standardisation required
Level(s) from the ILOs framework:	Level 4

European Values and interests

The pilot introduces European values and interests in a practical, applied way by embedding them directly into the content of each module. Rather than addressing values as an abstract topic, the course shows how standards support EU goals such as safety, sustainability, accessibility, fairness, and gender equality through real-world examples relevant to SMEs.

In the basic modules, participants will explore how values like health, safety, consumer protection and environmental sustainability are embedded in EU legislation and expressed through harmonised standards—especially in relation to market access and regulatory compliance.

The sector-specific module will include tailored examples showing how EU priorities such as green transition, digitalisation or gender equality are reflected in standards relevant to the given sector.

By connecting values to concrete business and compliance challenges, the course aims to make EU principles both visible and actionable for SMEs. In addition, the course promotes inclusivity in the standardisation process itself, highlighting how SMEs can play an active role in shaping standards that reflect diverse perspectives and needs.

Intended Learning Outcomes

Given the short duration of these courses, the learning outcome must be flexible and in line with feasibility and participants' previous knowledge base. Anyhow, the course corresponds to Level 4 of the ILOs framework (Post-secondary, non-tertiary education), as described by the project in [D2.1 – Intended Learning Outcomes \(ILOs\) for Standardisation Education](#).

The learner is expected: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K4.1: to have a factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts of values in standardisation within one's field • K4.2: to have factual and theoretical knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation within one's field 	The learner is able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S4.1: analyse, interpret and evaluate the value "sustainability" in different standardisation scenarios and (industry) sectors • S4.2: identify strategies to ensure more inclusion of green aspects in standardisation • S4.3: identify cases of unsustainable aspects in existing standards 	The learner is able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S4.1: demonstrate knowledge in digital and ICT standards • S4.2: search for and select appropriate digital and ICT standards for different scenarios and contexts • S4.3: analyse, interpret and evaluate values in different ICT standardisation scenarios and (industry) sectors • S4.4: identify strategies to ensure more responsible, respectful and ethical dealing with digital tools • S4.5: manage more complex tasks that demand more complex information research, data creation and analysis. 	The learner is able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S4.1: interpret and evaluate the value "gender equality" in different standardisation scenarios and (industry) sectors • S4.2: identify strategies to ensure more gender-inclusive participation in standardisation • S4.3: identify cases of gender-bias and discrimination in existing standards 	The learner can take responsibility for planning and managing their learning process. At the same time, they can participate actively in collaborative projects by providing meaningful contribution.
---	--	--	---	---

Description of Course Content

General course content (can be subject to change depending on participants needs):

Basic I – Standards and standardisation: key concepts explained

- What standards are and how they support business performance
- Examples of different types of standards
- Why standards matter for SMEs: efficiency, trust, innovation, and access to new opportunities

- What is standardisation? Basics of how it works including standard development bodies, development processes and key stakeholders
- Real-life SME examples of using standards to address everyday business challenges
- Debunking common myths and misunderstandings about standards
- Basics on where to find relevant standards and support for SMEs

Basic II – Standards, legislation and market access:

- Understanding the legal status of standards and what it means for SMEs (voluntary vs. mandatory use)
- Relationship between standards and EU legislation (New Legislative Framework)
- Role of Harmonised Standards in meeting legal requirements
- Introduction to CE marking and the use of standards in conformity assessment
- Practical implications of using standards to demonstrate compliance with EU directives and regulations
- SME responsibilities and opportunities when using standards under EU law
- Examples of standards supporting market entry in regulated sectors
- Access to international markets and international standards

Intermediate I – Applying standards in [sector/ area]:

- The role and importance of standards in the [sector]: relation with EU legislation, how they shape products, services, safety, interoperability, or sustainability
- Overview of the key standardisation bodies, committees and technical groups relevant to the sector
- How to find the most relevant standards for your sector or business activity
- Examples of how standards are used and applied in the sector: case studies from SMEs or real market practices
- Introduction to emerging issues or trends in the sector and standardisation (e.g. AI in manufacturing, sustainability in construction, food traceability)
- Where to find tools, guides, and support to help with implementation of standards
- Hands-on activity: Identify relevant standards for your own business

Intermediate II – Strategic use of standards and how to get involved in standardisation (optional):

- How SMEs can strategically use European and international standards to improve quality, compliance, and competitiveness
- Understanding the standardisation process and where input is possible: from proposal stage to public enquiry, technical work, and final vote
- Different ways SMEs can participate in standardisation (directly, indirectly via SME associations, contributing to enquiries at national level)
- First steps to get involved: where to start, who to contact

- Examples of successful SME involvement and what made it work
- Overview of specific support measures for SME participation and to get engaged in standardisation

Timeline and Milestones

[to be defined at a later stage]

Week/ session	Lecture	Practice or Project	Format methods (Presential, online)	/ assessment / exams activities
.....				

Assessment conditions

Individual participants will not be assessed in terms of reaching learning objectives. Participants will receive a certificate of participation. The course itself, however, will be evaluated with the participants.

Teaching Methods

The course will follow the methods outlined in the projects deliverables [D2.3 – Innovative Teaching Concept on Standardisation – Use Guide for Standardisation Education](#), and will include a considerable amount of interactivity, integrating real life examples, SME case studies, and non-formal learning methods.

Teaching Materials and Resources

The course will rely on open access material which is available online, especially the resources from [EDU4Standards Teacher Support Tool | EDU4Standards](#), and [Teaching repositories | EDU4Standards](#).

Evaluation

At the end of the course, we will evaluate it with participants (whether it met their expectations, what could be improved). We will use the evaluation methods/tools as designed in the EDU4Standards project.

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

Any material developed by EDU4Standards or its partners and used for this in-company pilot may be used elsewhere or made available to third parties for use elsewhere (unless other parties have rights on them). Any such material made available to others shall however not have any confidential or business confidential information.

Confidentiality

We encourage participants in the pilot to share experiences from their own practice, engage in discussion, share thoughts, etc., to create a lively and good learning experience. The involved teachers from EDU4Standards will act as it can be normally expected according to general standards of academic and professional integrity. As teachers, we will respect the Chatham House Rules (meaning that comments or views shared during the course will not be attributed to individuals or their organisations).

At the same time, we will ask SMEs and other participants not to disclose any information they consider to be commercially sensitive, confidential, or a trade secret during the sessions. If such information is shared inadvertently, participants will be requested to notify the organisers promptly so that appropriate discretion can be maintained.

Any material or insights gathered through the pilot for evaluation or reporting purposes will be anonymised and used only in aggregated form, in line with the objectives of the EDU4Standards project.

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

Quantitative metrics:

- enrolment numbers
- participant satisfaction scores

Qualitative insights:

- feedback from participants and instructors
observed challenges

3.2.5 Pilot of lifelong learning: the Pan-European EARTO pilot Design

The training programme offers three levels of courses on standardisation from a Research and Technology Organisation (RTO) perspective:

- Beginners learn the fundamentals of standardisation relevant to R&D.
- Intermediate experts develop practical skills to participate effectively in standardisation bodies.
- Advanced experts —senior researchers and managers— explore strategic standardisation topics linked to RTO business models, including IPRs, SEPs, and Open Source.

A pilot of this EARTO with a series of six webinars addressing Fraunhofer researchers interested and active in standardisation has been started in May 2025 and will be closed in July 2025

Developing and Customizing Pilots

University/School/Department:	Fraunhofer ISI
Program:	Pilot of lifelong learning: the Pan-European EARTO pilot

Pilot information

Course Code:	n/a (EARTO course)
Course Name:	Standardisation in research and technology for practitioners
Semester:	N/A (EARTO course, at postgraduate level)
ECTS credits:	N/A
Contact Hours:	6 webinars; 4,5 hours
Teachers:	Knut Blind
Module manager/coordinator:	Knut Blind
Course Language:	English
Course Format:	Online (MOOC, SPOC)
Course date:	Starting in Fall 2025

Pilot Description

General course description:	Beginners “Research & Development and Standardisation” course provides a concise yet in-depth understanding of standardisation as relevant from an Research and Technology (RTO) perspective.
------------------------------------	---

	<p>Intermediate experts “Effectively participating in standardisation bodies” course addresses skills to operate in standards bodies.</p> <p>Sophisticated experts “Strategic standardization for RTOs” high-level course, aimed at senior researchers, offers a tailored format for standardisation topics for management level also related to RTO’s business models (e.g. IPRs, SEPs, Open Source)</p>
Target audience (Attendance & Course Requirements):	<p>Beginners: Younger researchers, in the beginning of their career. Professional background, mostly postgraduate university educated. They may get involved in future standardization activities.</p> <p>Intermediate experts: Mid-career researchers, typically 6-10 years of experience as postdocs. They may get involved in future standardization activities.</p> <p>Sophisticated experts: Senior, higher level researchers, e.g., head of units or departments.</p>
Level(s) from the ILOs framework:	<p>Note: the EARTO audience is typically at postgraduate level, but in terms of standardisation-specific ILOs, we need to cover various preceding levels too:</p> <p>Course Beginners: Levels 1 to 4/5 Course Intermediates: Levels 5/6 Course Sophisticated experts: Levels 6/7</p> <p>(see also at ILOs, below)</p>

European Values and interests

European competitiveness European technological sovereignty and open strategic autonomy Digital and green transition of EU industries European values: inclusiveness and diversity in standardisation at ESOs, democratic values Transfer from research and innovation to standardisation

Intended Learning Outcomes

Modul	Intended Learning Outcomes The below refers to the ILOs as defined in document D2.1, Table 5.
--------------	--

Note: given the short duration of these online courses, the learning goal must be in line with what is actually feasible and corresponds to the participants' previous knowledge base. Hence the following proposal for ILOs.

Modul 1: Standardisation Landscape (Levels from 1 to 4/5)

- K1.1: to have a basic general knowledge of standards and standardisation
- K1.2: to have a basic general knowledge of values in standardisation
- S1.1: define the concept of standards and standardisation by using examples
- S1.2: outline the purpose of standards and standardisation (to ensure consistency, safety, understandability) and the benefits of having standardised products, services and processes in general
- K2.1: to have a basic factual knowledge of standardisation
- K2.2: to have a basic factual knowledge of values in standardisation
- S2.1: explain the basic concepts in the field of standardisation
- K3.1: to have knowledge of facts, principles, processes, general concepts and players regarding standardisation
- K3.2: to have knowledge of facts, principles, processes, general concepts and players related to values in standardisation
- K3.3: to have knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation
- S3.1: explain more complex concepts used in standards and standardisation
- S3.2: sketch the standardisation process (standards development) at a glance
- S3.3: analyse the standards ecosystem
- S3.4: compare the SDOs in terms of scope, geographical focus, decision-making processes, standards development processes, structure, types of standards etc.
- S3.7: explore the benefits and risks of standardisation
- S3.8: integrate green/digital/gender considerations to existing standards use cases
- S3.9: apply value-based concepts, terms and content to different industry-relevant or sector-specific contexts, scenarios
- K4.1: to have a factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts regarding standardisation
- K4.3: to have factual and theoretical knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation
- S4.1: explain the functions of standardisation institutions and their processes
- S4.2: select appropriate standardisation organisations
- S4.4: determine which form of standardisation (formal vs. informal) is appropriate

Modul 2: Types and Impacts of

- S3.5: explore the difference between various types of standards

Standards (Levels from 1 to 4/5)

Modul 3: Research and Standardisation (Levels 5/6)

- K5.1: to have comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge of standardisation within one's field and an awareness of the boundaries of that knowledge
- S5.2: assess the need for getting involved in standardisation
- S6.1: be actively involved in standardisation processes (participant)
- S6.6: promote green/digital/gender aspects in standardisation through active participation in various initiatives
- S7.2: strategically influence the agenda in standardisation processes
- S7.7: depict the interdependencies between standardisation and innovation
- S7.8: depict the relation between standardisation and IPR (relevance of patents, tension between patents and standards)

Modul 4: IPRs and Standardisation (Levels 5/6)

- S5.5: analyse the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework
- S6.2: illustrate the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework
- S7.7: depict the interdependencies between standardisation and innovation
- S7.8: depict the relation between standardisation and IPR (relevance of patents, tension between patents and standards)

Modul 5: Open Source and Standardisation (Levels 6/7)

- S7.7: depict the interdependencies between standardisation and innovation
- S7.8: depict the relation between standardisation and IPR (relevance of patents, tension between patents and standards)

Modul 6: Technological Sovereignty and Standardisation (Levels 6/7)

- K6.1: to have advanced knowledge of standards and standardisation within one's field, involving a critical understanding of theories and principles
- S7.1: evaluate existing policy documents on standardisation within one's field and at the interface between fields
- S7.2: strategically influence the agenda in standardisation processes

Description of Course Content

List of topics to be covered:

Beginners:

Modul 1: Standardisation Landscape:

Content:

1. Introduction
2. Basics of standardisation
3. Standards organisations
4. Standardisation Landscape
5. Linkages between standard development organisation

Specified ILOs:

- To understand and apply the different criteria for the classifications of Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) and documents
- To be able to describe the role of Standards Development Organisations (SDOs), recognised SDOs, and industrial consortia, as well as their interplay.
- To identify the characteristics of formal and de facto standardisation, and to be aware of the processes through which de facto standards are adopted by SDOs.
- To identify the main categories of standards and documents, including which type of documents may be produced by each organisation, and to get familiar with the naming conventions.
- To understand the differences among National, Regional and International organisations, the benefits derived of their coordination, and to be aware of the main agreements and procedures supporting it.
- To understand why standards are usually referenced by legislation, and the need to issue standardisation requests when a societal need is identified in a specific area.

Modul 2: Types and Impacts of Standards**Content:**

1. Introduction
2. Basics of standards
3. Effects of standards
4. Summary

Specified ILOs:

- To know the various functions of standards
- To understand Compatibility/ Interface Standards, Minimum Quality/ Safety Standards, Variety Reduction Standards, and Information/ Measurement Standards
- To be able to apply the different types of standards to specific topics

Intermediate experts:**Modul 3: Research and Standardisation****Content:**

1. Definition of R&D
2. Interlinkages between R&D and standardisation
3. Impacts of standards on research and innovation

Specified ILOs:

- Define research and its interface to standardisation
- Getting insights into the interdependencies between research and standardisation
- Understand how research and standardisation can benefit each other
- Understand how research insights can be integrated standardisation
- Know types of standards, which can support research

Modul 4: IPRs and Standardisation:**Content:**

4. Introduction
5. IPRs and its different forms
6. Ways in which IPRs can be relevant to standards and standardisation
7. Tension between patents and standards
8. IPR policies at SDOs
9. IPR, standards, and the legal system
10. Patent pools
11. Public interest and policy initiatives

Specified ILOs::

- Know different types of IPRs and its interface to standardisation
- Getting insights into the interdependencies between IPRs and standardisation
- Understand how IPRs and standardisation can benefit each other
- Understand how IPRs and standardisation can hinder each other

Sophisticated experts**Modul 5: Open Source and Standardisation****Content:**

1. Introduction
2. Open Standards
3. Free and Open Source and Standards
4. Practical Implications

Specified ILOs:

- Understand the mechanisms and governance of Open Source
- Getting insights into the interdependencies between Open Source and standardisation
- Understand how Open Source and standardisation can benefit each other
- Understand how Open Source and standardisation can hinder each other

Modul 6: Technological Sovereignty and Standardisation**Content:**

1. Introduction
2. Definition of Technological Sovereignty and basic understanding
3. Standardisation and standards safeguarding mechanisms for Technological Sovereignty
4. Mobile communication standardisation as an illustration
5. Recommendations
6. Challenges
7. Conclusion
8. References

Specified ILOs:

- Understand the geopolitical dimensions of standardisation
- Understand technological sovereignty
- Understand how standardisation can safeguard technological sovereignty
- Understand the challenges for standardisation to safeguard technological sovereignty

- Apply the role of standardisation to specific cases in order to secure technological sovereignty

Timeline and Milestones

Modul	Lecture	Practice or Project	Format methods (Presential, online)	assessment / exams activities
1	Standardisation Landscape (1 hrs.)	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Online</i>	<i>Participation and discussion; multiple choice test</i>
2	Types and Impacts of Standards (1 hrs.)	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Online</i>	<i>Participation and discussion; multiple choice test</i>
3	Research and Standardisation (1 hrs.)	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Online</i>	<i>Participation and discussion; multiple choice test</i>
4	IPRs and Standardisation (1 hrs.)	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Online</i>	<i>Participation and discussion; multiple choice test</i>
5	Open Source and Standardisation (1 hrs.)	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Online</i>	<i>Participation and discussion; multiple choice test</i>
6	Technological Sovereignty and Standardisation (1 hrs.)	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Online</i>	<i>Participation and discussion; multiple choice test</i>

Assessment conditions

Because of the context of this course (EARTO), individual participants will not be assessed in terms of reaching learning objectives. Participants will receive a certificate of participation after completing a brief multiple choice test. The course itself, however, will be evaluated with the participants.

Teaching Methods

Online lectures with Q&A option

Teaching Materials and Resources

Combination of handbooks (more specifically the ETSI Handbook, ISO publications), selected other publications (Blind & Gauch, 2009, Böhm & Eisape, 2021, Blind, 2024, etc.) considering EDU4Standards deliverables (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3).

Evaluation

At the end of the course, we will evaluate it with participants (whether it met their expectations, what could be improved). We will use the evaluation methods/tools as designed in the EDU4Standards project.

Reuse of the Teaching Materials

All the material should be accessible via the EDU4Standards repository.

Confidentiality

Not applicable

Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics

Quantitative metrics:

- enrolment numbers
- participant satisfaction scores

Qualitative insights:

- feedback from participants and instructors
- observed challenges

3.3 Pilot indicators (KPI) and self-assessment

3.3.1 Pilot indicators

The purpose of the pilot evaluation is to measure their compliance with standardisation education as suggested by the EDU4Standards.eu project based on the European Standardisation Strategy 2022 (European Commission, 2022). It is about to measure how best practices of existing standardisation education meet the new requirements on standardisation competences of future European Standardisation Experts. To this end, T2.1 has defined ILOs (D2.1), T2.2 has collected (international) best practices and identified gaps in D2.2, and T2.3 has developed an implementation guide and provided a teacher's support tool to design their own curricula (T2.3). T3.1 has built on these deliverables and added teaching material, serious games and distant

teaching modules to fill the gaps. Together they form a knowledge base, recommendations for its implementation into the different pilots, together with developed material.

In this context, it is important to mention that the pilot evaluation is not about assessing the quality of teachers and of the learners, as is the case with the general course evaluation; it is about the quality of implementation and the quality of knowledge and material provided to support the teaching. Findings by the evaluation will feed back for their improvement or, at if not possible, e.g. for lack of knowledge or at the end of the pilot phase, will feed the exploitation plan or the policy recommendations.

Building up on the knowledge, the implementation material and the designs, the indicators are now defined to measure how the pilots are meeting in their set-up, their execution and ex-post the different criteria which characterise the new European standardisation education.

These criteria should be further developed to a quality standard promoted as an EDU4Standards-label for the support, defragmentation and formalisation of standardisation education as suggested in the European Standardisation Strategy.

As mentioned above, it is important that the pilot set-up should already consider the criteria collected and presented in the knowledge base. To this end, they should perform a self-assessment, how they meet different criteria and suggest respective indicators for their measurement. The criteria and main indicators for their coverage which have been suggested by the consortium are the following:

I1 Attractiveness

I2 Multi-/Interdisciplinarity

I3 Practical aspects

I4 Internationalisation, international standardisation process

I5 European Standardisation process, European interests, European core values

I6 Teaching methods & material

I7 Advanced and pilot specific aspects

I8 Completeness

I9 Impact

For example, the following measures (I1.1, I1.2, I1.3) can already in the set-up contribute to the attractiveness of the teaching (I.4 is an indicator measured after the course). The pilot leader should now estimate on a

scale from 0 (no or insufficient coverage), 1 (little coverage), 2 (fair coverage), 3 (good coverage), 4 (very good coverage), to 5 (excellent coverage), how the attractiveness of his/her course is covered. Table 3-2 and Table 3-3 show a sample of how to evaluate the measures for criteria I1 and I2, the complete table can be found in Appendix 3.

I1 Attractiveness

Table 3-2. Sample Measures of I1 Attractiveness

I1.1	Inclusion of serious games	#hours spent for games
I1.2	Promotion material, outreach	#reached students/teachers
I1.3	Promotion of tangible benefits for graduates (recognition, jobs, (paid) internships)	#ECTS/#ECVET; #vacancies, internships
I1.4	Overall satisfaction by students/teachers	survey #marks

I2 Multi-/Interdisciplinarity

Table 3-3 Table Sample Measures of I2 Multi-/Interdisciplinarity

I2.1	Can be integrated in different disciplines;	#ECTS per discipline
I2.2	Participating teachers and students from different disciplines (including STEM/SSH)	students/teachers/disciplines
I2.3	Acquire sound knowledge about the perspective of the main discipline in standardisation	#ECTS
I2.4	Acquire knowledge about the perspectives of other disciplines in standardisation	#ECTS per discipline
I2.5	Coverage of technical and societal aspects of standardisation (HLI)	#academic hours/aspect

Indicator I2.5 is a so-called High-level indicator (HLI). This means this measure is suggested for all types of pilots. If I2.5 is not addressed, the whole criterion of Multi-/interdisciplinarity is not met. The score of assessment should be “0”.

3.3.2 Pilot self-assessment

Pilot leaders are invited for a self-assessment. Hand-in-hand with the pilot planning, he/she should determine by which means and how effectively the respective criteria are covered. To this end, for each criterion, a set of specific measures is suggested, which contribute to its coverage. The pilot leaders are asked to choose

among the measures that they want to use to cover the criterion. All together they perform the set of criteria/measures = sub-criteria, which are measured by indicators I# and I#.# respectively. Pilot leaders are free to define additional indicators for the coverage of the criterion.

Why is a self-assessment needed?

- Double check the set-up of your course, if it complies to EDU4Standards.eu-ideas
- Double check the appropriateness of indicators
- Prepare for evaluation of the (Call for) pilots
- Findings may contribute to the EDU4Standards-label

Sources of self-assessment?

- (International) best practices and suggestions to fill gaps for the education of standardisation experts analysed in D2.1, D2.2, D2.3 and D3.1.

How to do a self-assessment?

Already in the set-up, one can determine how far the pilot/course complies with the ideas of EDU4Standards.eu. E.g. one can enhance the practical aspects of your pilot if you include practitioners as guest lecturers in your course. This does not replace the pilot evaluation after the pilot execution is done by a third party.

Consequently, for each of the nine criteria/aspects (I1 – I9) measures rep. sub-criteria (I1.x – I9.y) are suggested, which would contribute to their coverage.

Against this background one should proceed as follows

1. Take the first criterion “I1 Attractiveness”
2. Go to the list of measures suggested for attractiveness (on the backside of the template)
3. Look which measure(s) for attractiveness are chosen (e.g. I1.1)
4. Put in the number(s) of the chosen measures in the column “...” in the cell next to attractiveness.
5. Indicate in the comment-box any measure which contribute to the given aspect, but is not in the list.
6. Estimate how well this criterion is covered by the measures: 0 = none or insufficient coverage¹; 1 = little coverage, 2 = fair coverage, 3 = good coverage, 4 = very good coverage, 5 = excellent coverage
7. Take the next criterion and repeat the process until I9.
8. You may comment your assessment or put any other observation in the comment box.

¹ Measures representing HLIs MUST be considered in the course, otherwise the coverage is insufficient

Table-3-4. Example of Pilot Self-Assessment

I#	Criterion	Assessment 0 (no) – 5 (excellent)	Measures/sub-criteria (indicate I#.# selected)
I1	Attractiveness	3	I1.1, I1.2
I2	Multi-/interdisciplinarity	0	I2.2 ²

The template and the result of the initial self-assessment can be seen in Appendix 3.

Conclusions

All pilot leaders agreed that the self-assessment template is a simple and useful tool to first check the quality of their pilot set-up if it complies with EDU4Standard.eu-ideas. The overview of all the results (Appendix 3) is also valuable for best practice exchange, on how a specific criterion or sub-criterion is addressed. In this first exercise, all the suggested criteria seemed reasonable and complete. No other (sub-)criterion has been suggested. This is a good starting point for the later evaluation, which will extend from the set-up to execution and follow-up of the pilots (see D3.3 Pilot evaluation report established in T3.7).

Specific observations and suggestions were made by each pilot to be considered for the improvement of the self-assessment tool:

- Make visible HLIs (e.g. colour, first position, legend)
- Introduce a column for explaining in words the assessment
- Some sub-criteria are not clearly formulated (HLIs, I3.4, I6.9, I7.4, I8.3)
- Some sub-criteria apply to the follow-up phase (e.g. internships)
- Introduce indicators explicitly referring to the usage of EDU4Standards.eu-deliverables and tools (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, Teachers support tool, D3.1 distant modules, serious games (to be developed); references to KAs, topics, gaps, best practices suggested needed).
- I3.4 Internship does not apply at this stage, maybe we can promise in a course that the best graduates get an internship; connection to StandICT of EDU4Standards.eu is promised in the contract. Both projects can mutually benefit from each other.
- Not all HLIs are covered by each pilot

Coverage of the High-level-indicators

High-level indicators are indicators which measure the coverage of sub-criteria which are compulsory for the teaching, as they contribute to achieve mandatory competences of future standardization experts. In the grant agreement, as a starting point the following is stipulated:

² I2.5 is a High-level indicator and not covered by the course; thus the coverage is insufficient i.e. "0"

“As a starting point, the high-level indicators relate to: 1) coverage of the standardisation under IEC, ISO, ITU-lead; 2) updates to global standardisation fora and consortia, 3) coverage of technical and societal aspects of standardisation (multidisciplinary orientation), 4) aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core-values, 5) green and digital skills through standardisation, 6) gender-responsive standardisation. The compliance with the teaching concept is measured in the # of academic hours dedicated to each of the five aspects.”

Table-3-5. Coverage of the High-level indicators (HLIs) by the pilots

I#.#	Criterion/Subcriterion	unit (Suggestion, pls. adapt)	Pilot 3.2 BSc	Pilot 3.3 MSc	Pilot 3.4.1 SSCH	3.4.2 PASSI ON	3.5 in- compa ny	Pilot 3.6 EARTO	course BATTLE S
12.5	Coverage of technical and societal aspects of standardisation (HLI3)	#academic hours/aspect	X	X	X		X	X	
14.1	Coverage of standardisation under IEC, ISO, ITU-lead (HLI1)	#academic hours	X	X	X	X	X	X	
14.2	Updates to global standardisation fora and consortia (HLI2)	#academic hours	X	X	X		X	X	
15.1	European standardisation process CEN/CENELEC/ETSI (suggestion HLI)	#academic hours	X		X	X	X	X	
15.8	Green and digital skills through standardisation (HLI5)	#academic hours		X	X		X		
15.9	Gender-responsive standardisation (HLI6)	#academic hours		X	X				
15.11	Aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core-values (HLI4)	#academic hours		X	X	X			
18.3	Addresses all HLIs* appropriately	#ECTS	X	X	X				

Table-3-5 shows that not all pilots in their initial set-up are addressing the HLIs. This might be due to the fact that not all pilots have the purpose of educating fully equipped standardization experts. The in-company-pilot is dedicated to professionals in companies as well as the EARTO-pilot (researchers). Yet it would be advisable to review the set-up in the next round. The course BATTLES informs about a specific aspect of standardization. As explained above, the criteria are covered differently. In particular, several sub-criteria are only addressed by a few pilots. Table 3-6 shows a coverage by max three out of six pilots and a course:

Coverage of the (sub-)criteria as a whole:

Table 3-6. Self-assessment overview: Coverage criteria by the pilots (example)

I#.#	Criterion/Subcriterion	unit (Suggestion, pls. adapt)	Pilot 3.2 BSc	Pilot 3.3 MSc	Pilot 3.4.1 SSCH	3.4.2 PASSI ON	3.5 in- compa ny	Pilot 3.6 EARTO	course BATTLE S	x times met
15	European aspects, European Standardisation Process, European interests, European core values		4	5	5	4	4	4	1	
15.1	European standardisation process CEN/CENELEC/ETSI (suggestion HLI)	#academic hours	X		X	X	X	X		5
15.8	Green and digital skills through standardisation (HLI5)	#academic hours		X	X		X			3
15.9	Gender-responsive standardisation (HLI6)	#academic hours		X	X					2
15.10	Teaching case for defending European interests	#academic hours		X						1
15.11	Aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core-values (HLI4)	#academic hours		X	X	X				3
15.12	Examples (e.g. trustworthy AI, supply chains)	#academic hours		X		X	X			3

Table 3-6 shows how the different pilot leaders address criterion 15 European aspects by choosing respective sub-criteria. This table can also serve for practice exchange among the pilot leaders on how they address a specific sub-criterion. The column “x times met” presents the number of pilots which meet the specific sub-criterion.

We see that the HLI (High level indicator) “15.8 Green and digital skills through standardization”, which is compulsory for all pilots to be addressed, is not covered by the “BSc-pilot” in the initial design, nor by the pilot “Passion”. They may consult other pilots on how they address these sub-criteria in the refinement stage.

Exploitation of synergies and complementarities among pilots by guest lecturers

In Table 3-6, one can also see that among pilot setups, there are synergies and complementarities that can be exploited. E.g. the course battles can be used by other pilots to enhance the scope. This also relates to the European standardization process, which is covered by pilot 3.1 but not by 3.2. Pilot 3.2 could include this aspect, for example, by engaging a guest lecturer from pilot 3.1. In exploitation, an institution can be used to offer education and can provide services related to guest lecturers. (see in D4.2).

Table 3-7. Coverage of the criteria (summarized assessments)

I#	Description	Summarized assessments
I7	Advanced & pilot specific aspects	19
I9	Impact	20
I8	Completeness	21
I1	Attractiveness	24
I3	Practical aspects, real-world oriented, practical problem solving	26
I4	International aspects: Internationalisation & International standardisation proce	27
I5	European aspects, European Standardisation Process, European interests, Euro	27
I2	Multi-/Interdisciplinary aspects	30
I6	Teaching methods & material	30
		(max= 35)

Table 3-7 shows how the self-assessments in total are covered by all pilots. Best addressed is in the opinion of the pilot leaders multi-/interdisciplinarity and teaching methods, the weakest are specific, advanced aspects, impact and completeness.

Table 3-8. Coverage of the sub-criteria by the pilots (extract: lowest coverage)

I#.#	Criterion/Subcriterion	x times met
I5.3	Proposal of new work items	0
I5.6	Propose new work item representing European interests	0
I5.7	Adapt to changes of European interests	0
I7.1	Propose new work items	0
I7.3	Propose new value-sensitive work items	0
I9.6	European Standardisation Certificate (HLF)	0
I3.4	Internships in companies and SDOs including STANDICT	1
I5.2	Funding opportunities in research, innovation and education EU and national	1
I5.10	Teaching case for defending European interests	1
I7.4	Graduated trainers can apply the diverse material and services of EDU4Standards.eu	1
I8.4	Graduates of the pilot are certified European standardisation experts or European standardisation teachers	1
I9.5	Standardisation Teaching award (CEN/CENELEC)	1
I3.2	Guest lecturers from SDOs	2
I5.9	Gender-responsive standardisation (HLI6)	2
I6.8	Covers all aspects of the course	2
I6.9	Openly available	2
I7.2	Transversal & 21st century skills: incl. 4 C's competences; negotiation in English, entrepreneurship, inter	2
I9.3	Certificate for course EDU4Standards-Label	2
I1.3	Promotion of tangible benefits for graduates (recognition, jobs, (paid) internships)	3
I2.1	Can be integrated in different disciplines;	3
I2.3	Acquire sound knowledge of the main discipline	3
I2.4	Acquire knowledge about the perspectives of other discipline in standardisation	3
I3.3	Guest lecturers from industry	3
I4.3	Students of different countries attending the course	3
I4.4	Teachers of different countries	3
I5.4	Identify policy objectives, priorities and standardisation (suggestion HLI)	3
I5.5	Identify areas which can be supported by standards	3
I5.8	Green and digital skills through standardisation (HLI5)	3
I5.11	Aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core-values (HLI4)	3
I5.12	Examples (e.g. trustworthy AI, supply chains)	3
I5.13	Example of incorporation of European core values as requirements in standards of products	3
I5.14	Identify value-sensitive aspects of products	3
I6.5	Contains Use of Technology	3
I6.7	Others (specify) e.g. collaborative learning	3
I8.3	Addresses all HLIs* appropriately	3
I9.4	Course published/accessed in https://academy.europa.eu/	3

How to read the Table 3-8:

I5.3 No graduate of any pilot has learned about “how to propose a new work item for standardization”.

I5.7 Graduates have not learned how to identify and adapt to changed European interests.

I5.2 Only one pilot is teaching how funds can be raised for standardization.

I3.2 Only two pilots will engage guest lecturers from SDO to enhance practical aspects.

I5.9 The High level indicator about gender-responsive standardization, which should appear in every teaching is only addressed by two pilots.

The whole ranking is presented in Appendix 3.

3.4 Open Call for pilots

The pilots performed by the consortium will test the extended knowledge, the implementation guide and the material and add to its quality and usefulness. They contribute to the impact of the new European standardisation education as suggested by the European Standardisation Strategy. Yet, there is an additional

need to broaden the scope by including additional new and existing teachers, institutions, pilot types, disciplines, subject matters and geographical representation. The Open Call for Pilots is the instrument of choice to realize this and to enhance the contribution to the ambitious expected outcomes and impact of the project.

Concretely, the Open Call for Pilots builds up on three policy pillars: 1) the Standardisation Strategy which defines the objectives of the EU in standardisation education, 2) the ERASMUS plus programme, which is about innovative teaching, curricula design and European interests and values, 3) the policy of the EU related to Open Science and Open Innovation as means to create awareness for research and enhance quality by using the knowledge of the crowd.

Applications for pilots will be called in two stages. The winners of the first stage will be invited to the second stage. The eligibility is like Horizon Europe and the evaluation will use evaluation criteria from ERASMUS+/Jean Monnet adapted to EDU4Standards.eu. Pilots are expected to run in 2026 and deliver a report about the usability of the respective EDU4Standards.eu-support, toolkits and knowledge base. To this end, deliverables D2.1, D2.2, D2.3 with the teachers support tool and drafts of D3.1 and D3.3 will be provided for use and assessment together with the respective templates and tools.

The findings will be used to:

- improve the deliverables and EDU4Standards-support and key exploitable results.
- find early adopters for these results and create awareness.
- extend the network of EDU4Standards.eu
- add to the KPIs of EDU4Standards (# of courses, institutions, graduates, disciplines, subject matters, sectors, teachers, students, etc.).

For the description of the Open Call for pilots refer to APPENDIX 1.

4 Conclusions

Designing a course on standardisation remains a challenging task, particularly in contexts where teaching materials are scarce, students often perceive the topic as boring or overly technical, and professors may be hesitant to engage with it. Task T3.1 "Pilot Design" has demonstrated that it is possible to overcome these challenges by applying a structured methodology that supports pilot leaders in designing standardisation courses aligned with the outcomes of EDU4Standards.eu WP2. The experience gained, along with the materials and teaching methods incorporated into the course designs, provides a solid foundation for promoting the teaching of standardisation in Higher Education Institutions across Europe.

The approach followed during the design process has yielded significant results, ensuring the quality of the pilots from the outset. The pilots' designs integrated serious games, innovative teaching methods, and addressed the gaps identified in WP2, while also supporting core European values. Pilot leaders dedicated time to analysing how the proposed designs met these requirements. Each course design included the following elements:

- Adoption of a design template that structured the course as a comprehensive planning guide.
- Clear identification of key course characteristics such as the course title, ECTS credits, contact hours, target audience, and course format.
- Alignment of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) and levels with the Knowledge Areas (KAs) defined in the ITCoS framework.
- Specification of teaching methods, course content, and topics.
- Establishment of a timeline for course implementation.
- Definition of assessment criteria and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for course evaluation.

The results achieved through this task validate the effectiveness of the proposed design methodology, which has proven both practical and adaptable. On the one hand, it has delivered high-quality pilot designs; on the other hand, it has operationalised the ITCoS conceptual model. The outcomes include:

- The design of eight pilots covering ILO levels 4 to 8, with a total of 236 teaching hours dedicated to standardisation across various target audiences:
 - One pilot at the university bachelor's level (UB)
 - Two pilots at the university master's level: *Technology Battles* (TUD) and *Standardisation and Sustainability* (TUB)
 - Two extracurricular pilots: *Standardisation for Engineers* (POLIMI) and *Summer School Pilot* (UGZ)

- Two in-company pilots: *Lifelong Learning Pilot* (TU/e) and *Standards for SMEs* (SBS) the latter of which emerged during the project as an additional initiative. Although it was not planned in the original Grant Agreement, it has become a valuable additional outcome of the project.
- One Pan-European pilot: *EARTO Pilot* (FHG)

Additional key outcomes of Task 3.1 include:

- Guidelines for the design and implementation of teaching games
- Description and functionality of the EDU4Standards Teaching Support Tool
- Development and sharing of teaching materials (e.g., videos, lectures) through the EDU4Standards repository and partner websites
- Specification of licensing conditions for the pilot outcomes
- Pilot self-assessment template and KPI framework (useful for both quality assurance and implementation evaluation)
- Pilot design template, to be reused in future calls for new pilots
- Detailed description of how each pilot addresses the identified gaps through both design and implementation

During the pilot's implementation stage, the Pilots Design presented in this report will be refined based on feedback gathered from the implementation and evaluation of the teaching pilots, as well as from ongoing project developments. In particular, the **Pilot Design Methodology for the Reuse of Teaching Materials** will be updated to include technical guidelines that facilitate content sharing and ensure interoperability. For example, by aligning with the **EC DCAT-AP** specifications and **Open Educational Resources (OER)** guidelines, as described in the **ITCoS Framework Model** in Deliverable D2.2 (Fomin et al., 2025).

Finally, this document itself serves as a comprehensive guide for translating the ITCoS framework into practice. It provides a structured approach to designing and implementing standardisation courses, ensuring alignment with European priorities and promoting the dissemination of best practices across educational institutions.

Appendix 1 Open Call for Pilots.

EDU4Standards Open Call for pilots

EDU4Standards is a European initiative aimed at enhancing education on standardisation by developing innovative teaching concepts, materials, and frameworks tailored to the needs of modern curricula.

EDU4Standards invites applications for a **two-stage Open Call** for pilots to test innovative approaches to standardisation aligned with the [European Strategy on Standardisation 2022](#). The call focuses on three core pillars:

- 1) **EDU4Standards outputs:** pilots will contribute to test in practice, validate and provide feedback for the project's (intermediate) results, in particular the project deliverables on Intended Learning Outcomes ([ILOs, D2.1](#)), innovative teaching concept (ITCOS, D2.3), pilot design (D3.1), pilot implementation (D3.2) and pilot evaluation (D3.3).
- 2) **Open Science and Open innovation:** Open Science is about *“early and open sharing of research”*³. Consequently, pilots need to openly cooperate and share knowledge and tools of EDU4Standards as early and widely as possible and to leverage both internal and external resources for researchers and others in the innovation ecosystem to unlock the latent economic value of ideas and knowledge⁴.
- 3) **Award criteria:** the call supports innovation in education in particular aligning with ERASMUS+ KA2 Curriculum design and Jean Monnet Modules. KA2 includes the development of innovative study programmes to ensure high quality and relevant education; designing innovative curricula and introducing innovative elements in the existing curricula; implementation of innovative learning and teaching methods⁵. Jean Monnet Modules allow for the development of short teaching programmes or courses in the field of European studies, promoting European values and interests⁶.

Expected Outcomes: Selected pilots are expected to contribute to all points below:

- Enhanced quality of EDU4Standards-deliverables by giving feedback and contribute to lessons learnt.
- Enhanced impact of EDU4Standards in terms of more HEIs, teachers and students participating in the new form of standardisation teaching.
- Enhanced impact in defragmentation of standardisation education according to EDU4Standards-criteria and mutual recognition (EDU4Standards-Label indicating best practices in Standardisation Teaching).
- Improvement and extension of teaching materials and methods in terms of teaching of European core values and interests related to standardisation, attract students to standardisation education, minimum requirements for standardisation.

Scope:

³ Horizon Europe Programme Guide, 1.5.2024; https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf; 16 Open Science pp38

⁴ G20 Ministerial Declaration Brazil, September 2024: [G20 agree on open innovation strategy and recommendations for diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility in science, technology and innovation - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

⁵ ERASMUS+ Programme Guide 2025 pp314

⁶ ERASMUS+ Programme Guide 2025 pp370

Applicants are encouraged to propose teaching activities about standardisation at EQF-levels 5: “Short-cycle Tertiary education”, 6: “Bachelor’s level”, 7: “Master’s level” or 8: “Doctoral level” and “non-formal education/continuing education/lifelong learning”^{7,8}. The teaching must:

- comply with the **Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)** as defined in D2.1 from EDU4Standards for the respective EQF level.
- follow the implementation guide of the **Innovative Teaching Concept (D2.3)** and give feedback for its further development.
- follow the **examples** of pilot **design** of a teaching module, provided in the draft deliverables D3.1 and D3.2 indicating a type, format, target group, (suggestions for) integration into existing study-programmes where appropriate (e.g. engineering, informatics, telecommunication, electronics, law, political sciences, philosophy, economics and others). The teaching module should be established, organised, executed and evaluated.
- define (minimum) requirements and indicators for the evaluation, measured in academic hours, ECTS or ECVET points where appropriate. These should include at least indicators related to 1) coverage of the standardisation under IEC, ISO, ITU-lead; 2) updates to global standardisation fora and consortia, 3) coverage of technical and societal aspects of standardisation (multidisciplinary orientation), 4) aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core-values, 5) green and digital skills through standardisation, 6) gender-responsive standardisation as mandatory indicators. In addition, specific indicators according to the type of pilots are expected.

Evaluation criteria:

The EDU4Standards-consortium will select in the first stage up to 24 pilots and in the second stage up to 12 pilots according to the following award criteria:

- **relevance to EDU4Standards objectives (25 points) (first stage criterion)**
- **quality of project design (25 points), (first and second stage criterion)**
- **quality of the partnership and cooperation arrangements (maximum score: 25 points), (first and second stage criterion)**
- **expected impact (25 points)⁹. (first and second stage criterion)**

The minimum overall threshold is 70 points, the minimum threshold per criterion is 15 points. In case of equal score, priority is given to achieve a country balance (e.g. countries not yet in the consortium) and for newcomers in standardisation teaching.

The evaluation is done in different **lots** according to the type of the pilot. The four (first stage) respectively two (second stage) best-ranked proposals per lot will be selected (one proposer can submit more proposals for different types):

1. BSc

⁷ [1] Council Recommendation of 22 May 2017 on the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning and repealing the recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2008 on the establishment of the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning (2017/C 189/03). Retrieved from: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017H0615\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017H0615(01))

⁸ See D2.1 p24 Table 3 The structure and the levels of the Edu4Standards.eu value-based ILOs framework

⁹ Cf Award Criteria Jean-Monnet Programme Guide [Jean Monnet actions in the field of higher education - Erasmus+ \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/erasmus-plus-program/jean-monnet-programme/guide)

2. MSc
3. PhD
4. Extra-curricular pilot
5. In-company training
6. Any other type of pilot

The evaluation in the first stage is based on the two-page pilot design template focussing on the concept of the pilot and the respective criterion relevance; the evaluation in the second stage is based on a detailed proposal of 15 pages where all evaluation criteria are queried.

Support provided by the EDU4Standards consortium:

Following Open Science principles, the EDU4Standards consortium will support selected pilots with:

- **Access to early results:** free access to draft project deliverables (D2.1, D2.3, D3.1, D3.2, D3.3).
- **Expert guidance:** tailored support from consortium members.
- **Recognition:** awarding of the **EDU4Standards Seal of Excellence** to recognise outstanding contributions.
- **Networking opportunities:** invitations to EDU4Standards events and access to a broader educational and standardisation network.

Eligibility:

This call is open to any European institution that fulfils the Horizon Europe eligibility criteria. New institutions that are currently not systematically educating standardisation are also encouraged to apply. Proposals can be made by one institution or by a couple of institutions (from one or different countries).

Funding and benefits: “Why should I apply for this call?”:

According to the principles of Open Science and Open Innovation, the participation is on a voluntary basis. There is no specific funding available. Proposers are encouraged to bring in their own funding sources or available resources.

The benefits for the selected project consortia are:

- Gaining free access to EDU4Standards resources and tools.
- Being included in a pioneering initiative, showcasing innovative standardisation teaching.
- Opportunities to influence and shape the future of standardisation education in Europe bringing in the perspectives of multiple countries and new players.
- Be invited in future joint follow-up projects and activities of EDU4Standards

Deadlines:

The call is open in the first stage from June 2025 to September 2025. The winners of stage 1 will be invited to the second stage to submit a more detailed proposal. The second stage will be open from 9 October 2025 until 1st December 2025. The Open Pilots are expected to start between 2 March 2026 and 30 September 2026. A report has to be submitted by 15 October 2026 with feedback on the usefulness of the material provided.

- **Intro webinar on the upcoming open call 4 June 2025 (tentative)**
- **Launch of Open call stage 1 and info and networking session at EURAS 19 June 2025: 19 June 2025**

- **Stage 1:** open from **19 June 2025** to **30 September 2025**
- **Results of stage 1:** announced by **7 October 2025**
- **Info webinar on open call stage 2:** **17 October 2025 (tentative)**
- **Stage 2:** open from **20 October 2025** to **15 November 2025**
- **Final results:** announced by **21 November 2025**
- **Pilots:** Between **5 December 2025** and **30 September 2026**
- **Pilot Report Submission:** **15 October 2026**

An information session is planned during the EURAS-conference in Madrid, June 2025.

Pre-publication:

The consortium of EDU4Standards.eu has developed an innovative teaching concept, related deliverables and an implementation guide (ITCOS) for education and training of future European standardisation experts. This will be tested in several pilots by members of the consortium.

To enhance the impact, the consortium invites all stakeholders, interested in this new form of education on standardisation. Teachers, groups of teachers or any other institutions from the EU or Associated countries, which want to set-up a pilot base on the ITCOS is welcomed to join our forces and to submit proposals for the Open Call for Pilots on Education for standardisation. Experience in standardisation teaching is not needed.

You are encouraged to acquire your own funding sources. From our network you will get active support and recognition.

The call's launch is planned for June 2025. An information session at the EURAS -conference and a webinar are in preparation.

The draft call documents can be found at the website of EDU4Standards and at the EURAS-website

EDU4StandardsTo increase the impact, the consortium invites all stakeholders interested in this new form of standardisation education: Teachers, groups of teachers or other institutions from the EU or Associated Countries wishing to set up a pilot based on ITCOS are welcome to join our forces and submit proposals to the Open Call for Pilots on Education for Standardisation. Experience in standardisation education is not required.

You are encouraged to find your own sources of funding. You will receive active support and recognition from our network.

The first stage of the call will be launched in June 2025 with a deadline of beginning of October. An information session at the EURAS conference in June 2025 and a webinar are in preparation.

Topic description:

Proposers should read the call document.

General conditions: Teachers/trainers, groups of teachers/trainers, institutions of any sector, all from the EU or (Horizon Europe) associated countries.

Budget overview: Proposers are encouraged to acquire their own budget. No financial resources from EDU4Standards.eu available.

Call documents:

Draft Deliverables (subject to the review in July 2025).

- D2.1 Intended Learning Outcomes for standardisation education
- D2.2 Topical and methodological map of standardisation education
- D2.3 Innovative concept of standardisation education with teachers support tool
- D3.1 Innovative concept of standardisation education with design template and self-assessment template.

Topic Q&As (in preparation). Your questions will be published with the answers.

Please submit your questions to

Appendix 2 Pilots leader Survey-Bridging WP2 Results with WP3

EDU4Standard: Bridging WP2 Results with WP3 (T3.1 Pilot Design Plan)

Select the pilot:

<input type="checkbox"/> T3.2. Pilot at university B.Sc. level.	<input type="checkbox"/> T3.3. Pilot at university M.Sc. level.
<input type="checkbox"/> T3.4. Summer school / extra-curricular pilot.	<input type="checkbox"/> T3.5. In-Company Pilot.
<input type="checkbox"/> T3.6. Pilot of lifelong learning: the Pan-European EARTO pilot.	

1. Select the knowledge the learner is expected:

(Move the mouse over each line into the box to select the desired option, and a dropdown list will appear)

Knowledge the learner is expected

Knowledge the learner is expected

Knowledge the learner is expected

2. Identify the European values that this skill supports or aligns with:

(Move the mouse over each line from the 'Skill' column to select the desired option, and a dropdown list will appear. Then, check the box. If necessary, you can add lines to the table.)

Skill	Human dignity	Freedom	Democracy	Equality	The rule of law
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Identify the European challenges that this skill supports or aligns with:

(Move the mouse over each line from the 'Skill' column to select the desired option, and a dropdown list will appear. Then, check the box. If necessary, you can add lines to the table.)

Skill	Energy transition	Green	Digital	Gender Equality
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choose an option.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Which materials and learning methods do you think are most appropriate for teaching the selected skills and achieving the selected knowledge?

Appendix 3 Pilot self-assessment template, indicators and overview.

Template for self-assessment

The self-assessment template is a tool for pilot leaders who are developing courses, to assess how their pilot meets the ideas and criteria of EDU4Standards.eu already in the set-up. On the right side you see the first page of the template.

The template includes the table below on page 3 and 4, which refers to the criteria which should be measured in each pilot and considered in the set-up of the respective pilot (see section 2.2). It serves as a starting point for evaluation and will later be refined in task 3.7 (D3.3). The table includes the number of the indicator, the name/measure, the unit of evaluation.

Pilot Template for self-assessment

Developing and Customizing Pilot Courses

University/School/Department:	
Program:	

Pilot information

Course Code:	
Course Name:	

Self assessment

I#	Criterion	Assessment 0 (no) – 5 (excellent)	Measures/sub- criteria (indicate I#.# selected)
I1	Attractiveness		
I2	Multi-/interdisciplinarity		
I3	Practical aspects		
I4	Internationalisation, international standardisation process		
I5	European Standardisation process, European interests, European core values		
I6	Teaching methods & material		
I7	Advanced and pilot specific aspects		
I8	Completeness		
I9	Impact		

*) 0 = no or insufficient, 1= little, 2 = fair, 3 = good, 4 = very good, 5 = excellent coverage of the criterion by your chosen measures

Comments or observations

The last page contains hints, how the self-assessment should be conducted.

Self-assessment guidelines

Why is a self-assessment needed?

- Double check the set-up of your course, if it complies to EDU4Standards.eu-ideas
- Double check the appropriateness of indicators
- Prepare for evaluation of the (Call for) pilots
- Findings may contribute to the EDU4Standards-label

Sources of self-assessment?

- (International) best practices and suggestions to fill gaps for the education of standardisation experts analysed in D2.1, D2.2, D2.3 and D3.1.

How to do a self-assessment?

Already in the set-up you can determine, how far your pilot/course complies to the ideas of EDU4Standards.eu. E.g. you can enhance the practical aspects of your pilot if you include practitioners as guest lecturers in your course. This does not replace the pilot evaluation after the pilot execution done by a third party.

Consequently, for each of the nine criteria/aspects (I1 – I9) measures (I1.x – I9.y) are suggested, which would contribute to their coverage.

Against this background do the following:

1. Take the first criterion “I1 Attractiveness”
2. Go to the list of measures suggested for attractiveness (on the backside of the template)
3. Look which measure(s) for attractiveness you have chosen (e.g. I1.1)
4. Put in the number(s) of the chosen measures in the column “...” in the cell next to attractiveness.
5. If you think, you have foreseen a measure which contributes to the given aspect, not in the list, you may note it in the comment-box.
6. Estimate by yourself, how well this criterion is covered by your measures: 0 = non or insufficient coverage¹; 1 = little coverage, 2 = fair coverage, 3 = good coverage, 4 = very good coverage, 5 = excellent coverage
7. Take the next criterion and repeat the process until I9.
8. You may comment your assessment or put any other observation in the comment box.

Example

I#	Criterion	Assessment 0 (no) – 5 (excellent)	Measures/sub-criteria (indicate I#.# selected)
I1	Attractiveness	3	I1.1, I1.2
I2	Multi-/interdisciplinarity	0	I2.2 ²

¹ Measures representing HLIs MUST be considered in the course, otherwise the coverage is insufficient

² I2.5 is a High-level indicator and not covered by the course; thus the coverage is insufficient i.e. “0”

Indicators for self-assessment

I1 Attractiveness

#.#	Name/measure/sub-criterion	Unit of measurement
I1.1	Inclusion of serious games	#academic hours
I1.2	Promotion material, outreach	#reached students/teachers
I1.3	Promotion of tangible benefits for graduates (recognition, jobs, (paid) internships)	#ECTS/#ECVET; #vacancies, internships
I1.4	Overall satisfaction by students/teachers	survey #marks

I2 Multi-/Interdisciplinarity

I2.1	Can be integrated in different disciplines;	#ECTS per discipline
I2.2	Participating teachers and students from different disciplines (including STEM/SSH)	students/teachers/disciplines
I2.3	Acquire sound knowledge of the main discipline	#ECTS
I2.4	Acquire knowledge about the perspectives of other disciplines in standardisation	#ECTS per discipline
I2.5	Coverage of technical and societal aspects of standardisation (HLI)	#academic hours/aspect

I3 Practical aspects

I3.1	Simulation of working groups and standard development	#academic hours
I3.2	Guest lecturers from SDOs	#academic hours
I3.3	Guest lecturers from industry	#academic hours
I3.4	Internships in companies and SDOs including STANDICT	#academic hours
I3.5	Practical work in working groups	#academic hours
I3.6	(Real life) teaching case	#academic hours

I4 Internationalisation, international standardisation process

I4.1	Coverage of standardisation under IEC, ISO, ITU-lead (HLI)	#academic hours
------	---	-----------------

14.2	Updates to global standardisation fora and consortia (HLI)	#academic hours
14.3	Students of different countries attending the course	#students/country
14.4	Teachers of different countries	#teachers/country

15 European Standardisation process, European interests, European core values

15.1	European standardisation process CEN/CENELEC/ETSI (suggestion HLI)	#academic hours
15.2	Funding opportunities in research, innovation and education EU and national	#academic hours
15.3	Proposal of new work items	#academic hours
15.4	Identify policy objectives, priorities and standardisation (suggestion HLI)	#academic hours
15.5	Identify areas which can be supported by standards	#academic hours
15.6	Propose new work item representing European interests	#academic hours
15.7	Adapt to changes of European interests	#academic hours
15.8	Green and digital skills through standardisation (HLI)	#academic hours
15.9	Gender-responsive standardisation	#academic hours
15.10	Teaching case for defending European interests	#academic hours
15.11	Aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core-values (HLI)	#academic hours
15.12	Examples (e.g. trustworthy AI, supply chains)	#academic hours
15.13	Example of incorporation of European core values as requirements in standards of products	#academic hours
15.14	Identify value-sensitive aspects of products	#academic hours

16 Teaching methods & material

16.1	Contains distant teaching parts	#academic hours
16.2	Contains direct teaching parts	#academic hours
16.3	Contains Interactive Lectures	#academic hours
16.4	Contains project-based learning	#academic hours
16.5	Contains Use of Technology	#academic hours
16.6	Includes Serious Games	#academic hours
16.7	Others (specify) e.g. collaborative learning	#academic hours
16.8	Covers all aspects of the course	#academic hours
16.9	Openly available	#academic hours

I7 Advanced and pilot specific aspects

17.1	Propose new work items	#academic hours
17.2	Transversal & 21st century skills: incl. 4 C's competences; negotiation in English, entrepreneurship, intercultural, fundraising	#academic hours
17.3	Propose new value-sensitive work items	#academic hours
17.4	Graduated trainers can apply the diverse material and services of EDU4Standards.eu	#academic hours
17.5	Appropriate for the target group (level, students/teachers/professionals)	#academic hours

I8 Completeness

18.1	Self-standing module/course	#ECTS
18.2	Implementation of the ITCOS related to KA, topic, teaching material, suggested games and literature	#ECTS
18.3	Addresses all HLIs appropriately	#ECTS
18.4	Graduates of the pilot are certified European standardisation experts or European standardisation teachers where appropriate	#ECTS

I9 Impact

19.1	Adoption by HEIs/companies/trainings institution	#institutions
19.2	Certificate for students/learners	yes/no
19.3	Certificate for course EDU4Standards-Label	yes/no
19.4	Course published/accessed in https://academy.europa.eu/ or on the EDU4Standards.eu-portal	#visitors
19.5	Standardisation Teaching award (CEN/CENELEC)	yes/no
19.6	European Standardisation Certificate (HLF)	yes/no

Overview of the preliminary self-assessment

I#.#	Criterion/Subcriterion	unit (Suggestion, pls. adapt)	Pilot 3.2 BSc	Pilot 3.3 MSc	Pilot 3.4.1 SSCH	3.4.2 PASSI ON	3.5 in- compa ny	Pilot 3.6 EARTO	course BATTLE S
I.1	Attractiveness		4	4	4	4	4	3?	4
I1.1	Inclusion of serious games	#academic hours	X	X	X	X	X		X
I1.2	Promotion material, outreach	#reached students/teachers		X	X		X	X	
I1.3	Promotion of tangible benefits for graduates (recognition, jobs, (paid) internships)	#ECTS/#ECVET; #vacancies, internships	X	X	X				
I1.4	Overall satisfaction by students/teachers	survey #marks	X	X	X	X			X
I2	Multi-/Interdisciplinary aspects		4	5	5	3	4	4	5
I2.1	Can be integrated in different disciplines;	#ECTS per discipline	X	X	X				
I2.2	Participating teachers and students from different disciplines (including STEM/SSH)	students/teachers/ disciplines	X	X	X	X	X		X
I2.3	Acquire sound knowledge of the main discipline	#ECTS	X	X					X
I2.4	Acquire knowledge about the perspectives of other discipline in standardisation	#ECTS per discipline	X	X	X				
I2.5	Coverage of technical and societal aspects of standardisation (HLI3)	#academic hours/aspect	X	X	X		X	X	
I3	Practical aspects, real-world oriented, practical problem solving		5	4	2	4	4	3	4
I3.1	Simulation of working groups and standard development	#academic hours	X		X	X	X		
I3.2	Guest lecturers from SDOs	#academic hours	X	X					
I3.3	Guest lecturers from industry	#academic hours	X	X			X		
I3.4	Internships in companies and SDOs including STANDICT	#academic hours	X						
I3.5	Practical work in working groups	#academic hours	X	X	X				X
I3.6	(Real life) teaching case	#academic hours	X	X	X		X	X	X
I4	International aspects: Internationalisation & International standardisation process		5	5	2	3	4	4	4
I4.1	Coverage of standardisation under IEC, ISO, ITU-lead (HLI1)	#academic hours	X	X	X	X	X	X	
I4.2	Updates to global standardisation fora and consortia (HLI2)	#academic hours	X	X	X		X	X	
I4.3	Students of different countries attending the course	#students/country	X	X					X
I4.4	Teachers of different countries	#teachers/country	X	X			X		
I5	European aspects, European Standardisation Process, European interests, European core values		4	5	5	4	4	4	1
I5.1	European standardisation process CEN/CENELEC/ETSI (suggestion HLI)	#academic hours	X		X	X	X	X	
I5.2	Funding opportunities in research, innovation and education EU and national	#academic hours	X						
I5.3	Proposal of new work items	#academic hours							
I5.4	Identify policy objectives, priorities and standardisation (suggestion HLI)	#academic hours		X	X		X		
I5.5	Identify areas which can be supported by standards	#academic hours	X	X			X		
I5.6	Propose new work item representing European interests	#academic hours							
I5.7	Adapt to changes of European interests	#academic hours							
I5.8	Green and digital skills through standardisation (HLI5)	#academic hours		X	X		X		
I5.9	Gender-responsive standardisation (HLI6)	#academic hours		X	X				
I5.10	Teaching case for defending European interests	#academic hours		X					
I5.11	Aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core- values (HLI4)	#academic hours		X	X	X			
I5.12	Examples (e.g. trustworthy AI, supply chains)	#academic hours		X		X	X		
I5.13	Example of incorporation of European core values as requirements in standards of products	#academic hours		X		X		(X)	
I5.14	Identify value-sensitive aspects of products	#academic hours		X			X	(X)	

I6	Teaching methods & material		5	5	5	4	4	3	4
I6.1	Contains distant teaching parts	#academic hours	X	X	X			X	
I6.2	Contains direct teaching parts	#academic hours	X	X	X	X	X		
I6.3	Contains Interactive Lectures	#academic hours	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
I6.4	Contains project-based learning	#academic hours	X	X	X				X
I6.5	Contains Use of Technology	#academic hours	X	X	X				
I6.6	Includes Serious Games	#academic hours	X	X	X	X	X	(X)	X
I6.7	Others (specify) e.g. collaborative learning	#academic hours	X	X	X				
I6.8	Covers all aspects of the course	#academic hours	X	X					
I6.9	Openly available	#academic hours	X	X					
I7	Advanced & pilot specific aspects		3	3	3	3	4		3
I7.1	Propose new work items	#academic hours							
I7.2	Transversal & 21st century skills: incl. 4 C's competences; negotiation in English, entrepreneurship, intercultural, fundraising	#academic hours	X			X			
I7.3	Propose new value-sensitive work items	#academic hours							
I7.4	Graduated trainers can apply the diverse material and services of EDU4Standards.eu	#academic hours			X				
I7.5	Appropriate for the target group (level, students/teachers/professionals)	#academic hours	X	X	X		X	X	X
I8	Completeness		4	3	3	4	4		3
I8.1	Self-standing module/course	#ECTS	X		X	X	X	X	X
I8.2	Implementation of the ITCOS related to KA, topic, teaching material, suggested games and literature	#ECTS	X	X?	X	X			
I8.3	Addresses all HLIs* appropriately	#ECTS	X	X	X				
I8.4	Graduates of the pilot are certified European standardisation experts or European standardisation teachers where appropriate	#ECTS	X						
I9	Impact		4	4	3	4	4		1
I9.1	Adoption by HEIs/companies/trainings institution	#institutions	X	X?	X		X	X	
I9.2	Certificate for students/learners	yes/no	X	X?	X	X		(X)	
I9.3	Certificate for course EDU4Standards-Label	yes/no		X?				(X)	
I9.4	Course published/accessed in https://academy.europa.eu/	#visitors	X		X			(X)	
I9.5	Standardisation Teaching award (CEN/CENELEC)	yes/no						(X)	
I9.6	European Standardisation Certificate (HLF)	yes/no							

Ranking of the (sub-)criteria covered by the pilots

I#.#	Criterion/Subcriterion	x times met
I5.3	Proposal of new work items	0
I5.6	Propose new work item representing European interests	0
I5.7	Adapt to changes of European interests	0
I7.1	Propose new work items	0
I7.3	Propose new value-sensitive work items	0
I9.6	European Standardisation Certificate (HLF)	0
I3.4	Internships in companies and SDOs including STANDICT	1
I5.2	Funding opportunities in research, innovation and education EU and national	1
I5.10	Teaching case for defending European interests	1
I7.4	Graduated trainers can apply the diverse material and services of EDU4Standards.eu	1
I8.4	Graduates of the pilot are certified European standardisation experts or European standardisation teachers	1
I9.5	Standardisation Teaching award (CEN/CENELEC)	1
I3.2	Guest lecturers from SDOs	2
I5.9	Gender-responsive standardisation (HLI6)	2
I6.8	Covers all aspects of the course	2
I6.9	Openly available	2
I7.2	Transversal & 21st century skills: incl. 4 C's competences; negotiation in English, entrepreneurship, inter	2
I9.3	Certificate for course EDU4Standards-Label	2
I1.3	Promotion of tangible benefits for graduates (recognition, jobs, (paid) internships)	3
I2.1	Can be integrated in different disciplines;	3
I2.3	Acquire sound knowledge of the main discipline	3
I2.4	Acquire knowledge about the perspectives of other discipline in standardisation	3
I3.3	Guest lecturers from industry	3
I4.3	Students of different countries attending the course	3
I4.4	Teachers of different countries	3
I5.4	Identify policy objectives, priorities and standardisation (suggestion HLI)	3
I5.5	Identify areas which can be supported by standards	3
I5.8	Green and digital skills through standardisation (HLI5)	3
I5.11	Aspects of human-centric standardisation, European core-values (HLI4)	3
I5.12	Examples (e.g. trustworthy AI, supply chains)	3
I5.13	Example of incorporation of European core values as requirements in standards of products	3
I5.14	Identify value-sensitive aspects of products	3
I6.5	Contains Use of Technology	3
I6.7	Others (specify) e.g. collaborative learning	3
I8.3	Addresses all HLIs* appropriately	3
I9.4	Course published/accessed in https://academy.europa.eu/	3
I1.2	Promotion material, outreach	4
I3.1	Simulation of working groups and standard development	4
I3.5	Practical work in working groups	4
I6.1	Contains distant teaching parts	4
I6.4	Contains project-based learning	4
I8.2	Implementation of the ITCOS related to KA, topic, teaching material, suggested games and literature	4
I1.4	Overall satisfaction by students/teachers	5
I2.5	Coverage of technical and societal aspects of standardisation (HLI3)	5
I4.2	Updates to global standardisation fora and consortia (HLI2)	5
I5.1	European standardisation process CEN/CENELEC/ETSI (suggestion HLI)	5
I6.2	Contains direct teaching parts	5
I9.1	Adoption by HEIs/companies/trainings institution	5
I9.2	Certificate for students/learners	5
I1.1	Inclusion of serious games	6
I2.2	Participating teachers and students from different disciplines (including STEM/SSH)	6
I3.6	(Real life) teaching case	6
I4.1	Coverage of standardisation under IEC, ISO, ITU-lead (HLI1)	6
I7.5	Appropriate for the target group (level, students/teachers/professionals)	6
I8.1	Self-standing module/course	6
I6.3	Contains Interactive Lectures	7
I6.6	Includes Serious Games	7

Bibliography

- Almås, H. (2025). Developing organizations using serious games: A qualitative study of learning through collaborative play [Tesis de maestría, NTNU, Trondheim]. <https://hdl.handle.net/11250/3173540>
- Almås, H., & Giæver, F. (2024). The emergence of collaboration in serious games: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Serious Games*, 11(3), 89–108. <https://doi.org/10.17083/ijsg.v11i3.739>
- Almås, H., Pinkow, F., & Giæver, F. (2023). Reimagining how to understand learning game experiences: A qualitative and exploratory case study. *Smart Learning Environments*, 10(14). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-023-00234-0>
- Bekkers, R. (n.d.). *Education videos on patents and standards*. Retrieved May 20, 2025, from <https://rudibekkers.com/videos/>
- Blind, K., & Drechsler, S. (2017). *European market needs for education in standardisation/standardisation-related competence*. Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (European Commission).
- Blind, K., Böhm, M., Grzegorzewska, P., Katz, A., Muto, S., Pätsch, S., & Schubert, T. (2021). *The impact of open source software and hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy: Final study report*. European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2759/430161>
- Choi, D. G., & de Vries, H. J. (2011). Standardization as emerging content in technology education at all levels of education. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 21(1), 111–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-009-9110-z>
- Coghlan, D., Shani, A. B. (Rami), & Hay, G. W. (2019). Toward a social science philosophy of organization development and change. En A. B. (Rami) Shani & D. A. Noumair (Eds.), *Research in Organizational Change and Development* (Vol. 27, pp. 1–29). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S0897-301620190000027003>
- Creative Commons. (n.d.). *About CC licenses*. <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses/>
- Creative Commons - b. (n.d.). *Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)*. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
- Čudanov, M., Mijatović, I., & Šavoiu, G. (2013). Multidisciplinary approach to ad hoc de facto standardization: Standards and organizational design. *Econophysics, Sociophysics & Other Multidisciplinary Sciences Journal (ESMSJ)*, 3(1), 46-52.
- Delft University of Technology. (n.d.). *Study Guide Manual*. https://filelist.tudelft.nl/BK/Studeren/Exchange_programme/Study_Guide_Manual.pdf
- Duke, R. D., & Geurts, J. L. A. (2004). *Policy games for strategic management: Pathways into the unknown*. Dutch University Press.
- EDU4Standards. (n.d.). *Teacher Support Tool*. Retrieved April 27, 2025, from <https://www.EDU4Standards.eu/teacher-support-tool>

- European Commission. (2021). *Horizon Europe, open science – Early knowledge and data sharing, and open collaboration*. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/18252>
- European Commission. (2022, February 1). *An EU Strategy on Standardisation. Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green and digital EU single market*. <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/48598>
- European Union. (2023). *Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act)*. Official Journal of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854/oj/eng>
- Fomin, V., Mosakas, K., Kuzmuk, O., Laužikas, R., Parada Gelvez, H.A., del Alamo, J.M., Bravo, S., Rodriguez Torado, D., Bekkers, R., Wiegmann, P., Abdelkafi, N., Bijlmakers, S., Kamara, I., Delimatsis, P., & Blind, K. (2025). *D.2.2 Topical and methodological map of standardisation education*. European Commission.
- Free Software Foundation. (2025). *What is free software?* <https://www.gnu.org/philosophy/free-sw.html.en>
- Fyhn, B., Bang, H., Sverdrup, T. E., & Schei, V. (2022). Safe among the unsafe: Psychological safety climate strength matters for team performance. *Small Group Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10464964221121273>
- Fyhn, B., Schei, V., & Sverdrup, T. E. (2023). Taking the emergent in team emergent states seriously: A review and preview. *Human Resource Management Review*, 33(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2022.100928>
- Gamalielsson, J., Lundell, B., Brax, C., Persson, T., Mattsson, A., Gustavsson, T., & Feist, J. (2024). Open source software reference implementations for standards issued by different standards setting organisations: Availability, perceptions and practices. *Journal of Standardisation*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.59490/jos.2024.7140>
- Gee, J. P. (2008). Game-like learning: An example of situated learning and implications for opportunity to learn. En P. A. Moss, D. C. Pullin, J. P. Gee, E. H. Haertel, & L. J. Young (Eds.), *Assessment, Equity, and Opportunity to Learn* (pp. 200–221). Cambridge University Press.
- Hamari, J., Shernoff, D. J., Rowe, E., Coller, B., Asbell-Clarke, J., & Edwards, T. (2016). Challenging games help students learn: An empirical study on engagement, flow and immersion in game-based learning. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 54, 170–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.07.045>
- Hofstede, G. J., de Caluwé, L., & Peters, V. (2010). Why simulation games work - In search of the active substance: A synthesis. *Simulation & Gaming*, 41(6), 824–843. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878110375596>
- Krathwohl, D. R. (2002). A revision of Bloom's taxonomy: An overview. *Theory into Practice*, 41(4), 212-218.
- Lundell, B., Persson, A., & Lings, B. (2007). Learning through practical involvement in the OSS ecosystem: Experiences from a master's assignment. In J. Feller, B. Fitzgerald, W. Scacchi, & A. Sillitti (Eds.), *Open source development, adoption and innovation* (Vol. 234, pp. 329–334). IFIP – The International Federation for Information Processing. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-72486-7_30

- Lundell, B. (2020). *Analys av DIGG:s policy för utveckling av programvara* (Version 1.0, 20 maj). Skövde University Studies in Informatics, 2020(1). University of Skövde. <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:his:diva-18895>
- Lundell, B., Butler, S., Fischer, T., Gamalielsson, J., Brax, C., Feist, J., Gustavsson, T., Katz, A., Kvarnström, B., Lönroth, E., & Mattsson, A. (2022). Effective strategies for using open source software and open standards in organizational contexts: Experiences from the primary and secondary software sectors. *IEEE Software*, 39(1), 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2021.3059036>
- Mijatovic, I., Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Blind, K., Gamalielsson, J., Hakvåg, M., Olabarria Uzquiano, M., Parada Gelvez, H. A., Van de Kaa, G., Veljanova, H., Tomic, B., & Wiegmann, P. (2025). *D2.3 – Innovative teaching concept on standardisation: Use guide for standardisation education* (Version 1.1) [Project deliverable]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14850705>
- Olomi, D. R., & Sabokwigina, D. (2010). *Entrepreneurship education in Tanzanian business schools: A nationwide survey*. 12th International Conference on African Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development (ICAESB), Zanzibar Beach Resort, Zanzibar, Tanzania.
- Open Source Initiative. (2025). *The Open Source Definition (Version 1.9)*. <https://opensource.org/osd/>
- Rigby, S., & Ryan, R. M. (2011). Glued to games: How video games draw us in and hold us spellbound. ABC-CLIO.
- Riillo, C. A. F., Mijatovic, I., & de Vries, H. J. (2022). Certification to compensate gender prejudice: Analysis on impact of management system certification on export. *Applied Economics*, 54(33), 3777–3794. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2021.1990842>
- Slof, B., van Leeuwen, A., Janssen, J., & Kirschner, P. A. (2021). Mine, ours, and yours: Whose engagement and prior knowledge affects individual achievement from online collaborative learning? *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 37(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12466>
- Sosniak, L. A. (1994). Bloom's taxonomy. In L. W. Anderson (Ed.), *University of Chicago Press*. Chicago, IL, USA.
- Software Freedom Conservancy. (n.d.). *Copyleft.org: A collaborative project to create and disseminate useful information, tutorial material, and new policy ideas about copyleft*. <https://copyleft.org/>
- Software Package Data Exchange (SPDX). (n.d.). *Mozilla Public License 2.0 (MPL-2.0)*. <https://spdx.org/licenses/MPL-2.0.html>
- Staaby, T. (2021). Still in another castle. Asking new questions about games, teaching and learning. *gamevironments*, (15). <https://doi.org/10.48783/GAMEVIRON.V15I15.146>
- Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. (n.d.). Signaling & Switching [Course syllabus]. Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería y Sistemas de Telecomunicación (ETSIST). https://www.etsist.upm.es/uploaded/1233/Signaling&Switching_Aut24.pdf
- Van den Bossche, P., Gabelica, C., & Koeslag-Kreunen, M. (2022). Team learning. En C. Harteis, D. Gijbels, & E. Kyndt (Eds.), *Research Approaches on Workplace Learning* (Vol. 31, pp. 201–218). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-89582-2_9
- Vasconcelos, L., Sousa, M., Ferreira, F., & Pinheiro, J. (2022). Collaborating: Modern board games and laboratories as a tool for capacity building. *SN Social Sciences*, 2(9). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-022-00472-y>

- Veljanova, H., Reiter, B., Staudegger, E., Wendt, H., & Savini, G. (2024). *D2.1 – Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) for standardisation education (Version v8)* [Project deliverable]. Zenodo Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14229235>
- Wonica, P. (2017). Learning to evaluate analog games for education. *Analog Game Studies*, 2, 61
- Wouters, P., van Nimwegen, C., van Oostendorp, H., & van der Spek, E. D. (2013). A meta-analysis of the cognitive and motivational effects of serious games. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 105(2), 249–265. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031311>
- Zambrano, J., Kirschner, F., Sweller, J., & Kirschner, P. A. (2023). Effect of task-based group experience on collaborative learning: Exploring the transaction activities. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, e12603. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12603>